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Guidance report on incorporating the objectives of the “do no significant harm” principle in R&I

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Executive Summary

The "Do No Significant Harm" (DNSH) principle originates from the EU Taxonomy Regulation (EU 2020/852), which requires that sustainable investments avoid adverse environmental impacts while pursuing specific goals. The Regulation defines six environmental objectives — (1) climate change mitigation, (2) climate change adaptation, (3) the sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources, (4) the transition to a circular economy, (5) pollution prevention and control, and (6) the protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems— and stipulates that progress toward any one objective must not come at the expense of the others. This principle sits at the heart of both the EU's Sustainable Finance Disclosure Regulation (SFDR) and the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) guidelines, serving as a cornerstone of credible, holistic sustainability.

This report begins by tracing the conceptual roots of DNSH in international law and examining how it is defined and operationalized across EU policy and research funding programmes. It further explores two key relationships that shape the principle's practical reach. First, it examines the relationship between DNSH and the Green Oath, arguing that while both instruments share the goal of embedding environmental responsibility into EU policymaking, they remain structurally misaligned — one operating as an ethical and aspirational political commitment, the other as a legal and technical compliance instrument — and that this tension creates a risk that formal procedural adherence to DNSH displaces rather than embodies the substantive environmental engagement the Oath was designed to cultivate. Second, it addresses DNSH's relationship to the precautionary principle, arguing that precaution should function as an upstream filter — activating harm scrutiny before evidence of damage is conclusive, and thereby transforming DNSH from a reactive procedural check into a genuinely protective mechanism capable of accounting for long-term, cumulative, and scientifically uncertain risks.

Despite the good intentions, DNSH comes with significant challenges, which are extensively addressed in the literature: gaps between formal guidance and practice, technocratic tendencies in assessment tools, limited capacity to handle ambiguity and uncertainty, accountability weaknesses, and an ecomodernist orientation that can overstate control over complex socio-ecological systems. These challenges reveal that DNSH falls short because the Technical Guidance and the application documents so far do not address explicitly the normative dimension of this principle. Concepts such as "harm," "significance," and even "nature" are value-laden notions shaped by ethical worldviews and cultural assumptions. These implicit foundations matter because they determine what harm assessments can "see"—and what they may systematically overlook—especially where impacts involve relational values, cultural integrity, distributive injustices, or long-term ecological feedbacks. Making these normative dimensions explicit is therefore essential for improving both the legitimacy and the effectiveness of DNSH in sustainability-oriented research.

The report's central argument is that the persistent gaps between DNSH's formal requirements and its practical implementation are not merely technical failures. They reflect a deeper conceptual limitation: a narrow, quantitative conception of harm that systematically excludes cultural loss, irreversibility, distributive injustice, and the moral claims of non-human

beings and Indigenous communities. Building on a critical analysis of DNSH's current limitations, the report integrates insights from the mapping of environmental and climate ethics in the context of sustainable transitions (Deliverable 1.1, WP1) and empirical evidence from participatory social labs (Deliverable 2.3, WP2). It further draws on environmental humanities, ecology, and transcultural perspectives — including Indigenous approaches and Eastern philosophical traditions — to broaden the conceptual understanding of harm. This expanded framework is complemented by a deductive semantic analysis of harm-related language in the Human Relations Area Files (e-HRAF), which illuminates cross-cultural patterns in how harm, responsibility, purity, and social order are articulated.

The report then turns to the practical question of what a more adequate operationalization of DNSH might look like within research programmes and governance contexts. Such contexts pose particular challenges that standard regulatory assessments are ill-equipped to address: research-related harms are often emergent, indirect, and difficult to anticipate in advance; they unfold across extended timeframes and diverse social and ecological settings; and they affect communities, knowledge systems, and living entities whose moral standing existing frameworks fail to capture. The over-reliance on quantitative risk-benefit assessments sidesteps normative questions about whose interests count — those of non-human animals, ecosystems, or future generations — and neglects the broader socio-political cultural and relational dimensions of harm.

Towards the end of the report, key recommendations addressed primarily to research funding bodies, programme managers, and governance actors responsible for designing and implementing DNSH frameworks are presented — with the overarching aim of making harm assessment more rigorous, more just, and more fully responsive to the complexity of what harm, in practice, means.

Introduction

The "Do No Significant Harm" (DNSH) principle originates from the EU Taxonomy Regulation (EU 2020/852), which requires that sustainable investments avoid adverse environmental impacts while pursuing specific goals. An economic activity qualifies as environmentally sustainable only if it contributes substantially to at least one of these objectives while doing no significant harm to any of the remaining five.

The Taxonomy Regulation marks a significant step toward embedding environmental conditionality into capital markets, shifting sustainability from a voluntary aspiration to a legally binding threshold. This principle sits at the heart of both the EU's Sustainable Finance Disclosure Regulation (SFDR) and the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) guidelines, serving as a cornerstone of genuinely integrated sustainability governance.

Yet the promise of DNSH has not been matched by its implementation. In practice, current appraisal frameworks remain confined within a utilitarian and quantitative logic that reduces compliance to a box-ticking exercise — one that is procedurally legible but normatively thin. This reductiveness generates a cluster of well-documented weaknesses, acknowledged in both the scholarly literature and practitioner experience. Three difficulties stand out. First, there is no stable, operationally adequate definition of what constitutes "harm" in the relevant sense: the concept is broad enough to encompass physical, ecological, economic, cultural, and relational damage, yet assessments routinely attend only to what is measurable and proximate. Second, the qualifier "significant" — which is central to the legal threshold — remains poorly defined, creating inconsistency across sectors, jurisdictions, and assessors. Third, there is persistent ambiguity about what DNSH is ultimately expected to achieve: whether it functions as a minimum safeguard, a proportionality test, or a more demanding standard of substantive justification.

1. What is the Do No Significant Harm Principle (DNSH)?

1.1 Definition

The **Do No Significant Harm (DNSH)** principle forms a cornerstone of the European Union's Sustainable Finance Framework. It was formally established through the **EU Taxonomy Regulation (EU) 2020/852**, adopted in June 2020 and effective from **1 January 2022**. The regulation provides a unified classification system for environmentally sustainable economic activities, ensuring that investments contributing to one environmental goal do not inadvertently harm others (European Commission 2020).

Article 17 of the Regulation specifies that, **to qualify as environmentally sustainable, an economic activity must not cause significant harm to any of the EU's six environmental objectives**. It further outlines detailed criteria for assessing when an activity may be considered to significantly harm progress toward an environmental objective (European Commission 2020).

The six environmental objectives as defined in the Taxonomy Regulation (article 9) are as follows:

- **Climate Change Mitigation:** An activity is deemed to cause significant harm if it results in considerable greenhouse gas emissions, thereby undermining efforts to limit global warming. In other words, actions that directly or indirectly increase carbon or methane emissions at scale are not compatible with the objective of addressing climate change.
- **Climate Change Adaptation:** An activity is considered harmful if it exacerbates vulnerability to current or future climate conditions—whether by increasing exposure of people, infrastructure, ecosystems, or the activity itself to climate-related hazards like floods, droughts, or heatwaves.
- **Sustainable Use and Protection of Water and Marine Resources:** Significant harm occurs when an activity negatively affects the ecological or chemical status of water bodies—such as rivers, lakes, groundwater, or marine environments—thereby impeding efforts to maintain or restore healthy aquatic ecosystems.
- **Circular Economy (Including Waste Prevention and Recycling):** Activities are considered harmful if they cause material inefficiencies, excessive resource consumption, or result in substantial volumes of waste that are not reused or recycled. Projects that increase long-term landfilling or incineration of waste without energy recovery may fall under this category.
- **Pollution Prevention and Control:** Significant harm is attributed to any activity that substantially increases the release of harmful substances into air, soil, or water—whether through emissions, discharges, or the use of hazardous chemicals—thus contributing to environmental degradation and human health risks.
- **Protection and Restoration of Biodiversity and Ecosystems:** An activity is classified as significantly harmful if it leads to ecosystem degradation, reduces biodiversity, or negatively impacts habitats or species of conservation concern. This includes actions that cause habitat fragmentation, introduce invasive species, or disturb protected areas.

To operationalize this principle, the Taxonomy Regulation provides for technical screening criteria, which specify how compliance with each environmental objective is to be assessed. The European Commission is empowered to adopt these criteria through **delegated acts**. In addition, Article 8 of the Taxonomy Regulation requires certain financial and non-financial undertakings to disclose the extent to which their activities are aligned with environmentally sustainable economic activities. The Disclosures Delegated Act further specifies the content and methodology of those disclosures.

1.2 Operationalization through Technical Guidance and national checklists

The DNSH principle was **later incorporated into the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF)**, established under Regulation (EU) 2021/241 as part of the EU's post-COVID recovery framework. Under Article 18 of the RRF Regulation, Member States must provide a case-by-case DNSH assessment for each reform and investment included in their Recovery and Resilience Plans (RRPs). In this context, measures in national plans are mapped against the RRF's six policy pillars: green transition; digital transformation; smart, sustainable and inclusive growth; social and territorial cohesion; health and resilience; and policies for the next generation.

The practical application of DNSH in the RRF is guided by the **Commission's Technical Guidance**, first published in February 2021 and amended in October 2023. This guidance provides specific criteria for assessing whether an activity be considered to significantly harm progress towards an environmental objective. These definitions help ensure that funded activities contribute to sustainability without undermining progress in other environmental areas.

Before any project is implemented, companies or other implementing entities must consult the **DNSH checklists** provided by their respective Member State. These checklists serve as an **initial screening tool** to determine which of the six environmental objectives could potentially be significantly harmed by a proposed measure. Based on this screening, the entity must then provide supporting evidence and carry out a DNSH assessment for the relevant objective or objectives, demonstrating that the measure does not cause significant harm.

This first screening step is also important because it determines the depth of the assessment required. Where the potential for environmental harm is minimal, a simplified DNSH assessment may be sufficient. Where the risks are more substantial, the measure must undergo a comprehensive DNSH assessment, involving a more detailed and evidence-heavy analysis demonstrating compliance with Member State-specific DNSH criteria. This two-tier structure is designed to ensure proportionality while preserving consistency with DNSH requirements across the Union.

More broadly, the Commission's RRF DNSH Technical Guidance groups measures into three broad categories, which determine the level of scrutiny and documentation required.

- The **first group** includes **measures in sectors like education, labor market reforms, public administration, and culture, which are generally considered to have minimal environmental impact**. For these, a simplified DNSH assessment applies, requiring only a brief justification from the Member State.
- The **second group** covers **measures that fully or substantially support one of the environmental objectives** outlined in Article 17 of the Taxonomy Regulation. These are considered automatically compliant with DNSH if they meet the criteria set out in the climate tracking methodology (Annex VI of the RRF Regulation), and only a fast-track explanation is required to show that the measure does not significantly harm other objectives.
- The **third group** involves **high-impact sectors** such as transport, industry, energy, and waste management. Given their potential environmental risks, these measures require a more detailed and robust DNSH assessment. Member States must provide comprehensive documentation demonstrating compliance with the principle.

The guidance also makes clear that compliance with existing environmental legislation, or the completion of an environmental impact assessment (EIA), does not automatically satisfy DNSH requirements. This reflects the Commission's intention to treat DNSH as an additional and independent safeguard rather than as a mere restatement of existing environmental obligations.

The governance framework of DNSH within the RRF is strict. Only projects that are found compliant with the principle may be approved by the European Commission. Where a proposed reform or investment is considered incompatible with DNSH, the Commission may require revisions before approval. DNSH therefore acts not merely as a reporting device, but as a substantive condition for access to EU funding. As Fasone and Simoncini note, DNSH operates as a "stringent limit" on the eligibility of RRF-funded projects, ensuring that only those aligned with the environmental objectives of the Taxonomy Regulation receive EU support (Fasone and Simoncini 2024). In this respect, the principle has had a significant influence on the design and content of National Recovery and Resilience Plans, including in controversial cases such as energy infrastructure investments (Famà 2025).

While the DNSH principle is intended to operate as a strict environmental safeguard, its implementation in many National Recovery and Resilience Plans (RRPs) has been uneven. The DNSH principle was inconsistently or inadequately applied in many RRP.

1.3 Legislative development of the DNSH framework

The DNSH framework has evolved through a series of legislative and delegated acts. These measures have gradually expanded, clarified, and in some cases adjusted the technical criteria used to assess sustainable activities and significant harm.

Date & Act	Description	Key Points / Applicability
June 4, 2021 – Climate Delegated Act (EU 2021/2139)	Established technical screening criteria to determine whether an economic activity substantially contributes to climate change mitigation or adaptation and causes no significant harm to other environmental objectives.	Applicable since January 1, 2022 .
July 6, 2021 – Disclosures Delegated Act (EU 2021/2178)	Supplementing Article 8 of the Taxonomy Regulation defines content and methodology for sustainability-related disclosures by undertakings under the Accounting Directive.	Applicable since January 1, 2022 .
March 9, 2022 – Complementary Climate Delegated Act (EU 2022/1214)	Added nuclear and natural gas activities to the taxonomy under strict conditions to align them with EU climate objectives and support the transition away from high-emission fossil fuels.	Published in Official Journal: July 15, 2022 . Applicable since January 1, 2023 .
June 27, 2023 – Environmental Delegated Act (EU 2023/2486) and Amendments to Climate Delegated Act (EU 2023/2485)	Introduced technical screening criteria for non-climate environmental objectives (water and marine resources, circular economy, pollution prevention and control, biodiversity, and ecosystems) and amended the Climate Delegated Act.	Published in Official Journal: November 21, 2023 . Applicable since January 2024 .
June 28, 2024 – Correction Act (EU 2024/3215)	Corrected certain language versions of the original Climate Delegated Act (EU 2021/2139) to ensure consistency across EU official languages.	Published in Official Journal: December 19, 2024 .
July 4, 2025 – EU Taxonomy Red Tape Simplification Measures (Omnibus I Delegated Act)	The European Commission adopted a Delegated Act simplifying the EU Taxonomy framework (Disclosure, Climate, and Environmental Delegated Acts) to reduce administrative burden while maintaining sustainability goals. DNSH criteria were simplified, particularly regarding: (a) exemptions for certain hazardous substances (e.g., ozone-depleting chemicals and Restriction of Hazardous Substances Directive (RoHS) exemptions); (b) removal of requirements to track self-classified substances under EU's Classification, Labelling and Packaging (CLP) Regulation.	Adopted as part of Omnibus I Package . Applies from January 1, 2026 for the 2025 financial year (with the option to apply earlier for the 2026 financial year).

Table 1 – Summary of legislation related to the DNSH

The legislative development shows that DNSH has been elaborated through delegated acts that seek both to specify technical criteria and to respond to practical concerns about implementation, proportionality, and administrative burden.

1.4 Extension of DNSH beyond the RRF

In addition to its application in the RRFs, the DNSH principle was incorporated into the **Common Provisions Regulation of 30 June 2021** to help mainstream climate action across EU funding. This regulation serves as a unified rulebook for eight major EU funds—collectively representing one-third of the EU budget—including the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), the European Social Fund Plus (ESF+), the Cohesion Fund, the Just Transition Fund (JTF), the European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF), the Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund (AMIF) and the International Security Fund (ISF) (Miller et al. 2022).

More recently, the European Commission has clarified that **DNSH does not function identically across all EU frameworks**. In November 2024, the EU Commission published a set of [frequently asked questions \(FAQs\)](#) to support stakeholders in the implementation of the EU taxonomy. The second question in the FAQ covers the relationship between the DNSH criteria in the EU Taxonomy and the way the DNSH principle is applied in the context of public funds, such as the Recovery and Resilience Facility and InvestEU. Here the Commission states that the DNSH principle serves distinct purposes across EU frameworks: in the EU Taxonomy it acts as a transparency tool for private finance, defining environmentally sustainable economic activities based on their substantial contribution to environmental goals and adherence to specific safeguards and screening criteria. In contrast, when applied to public funding instruments like the Recovery and Resilience Facility or the Innovation Fund, DNSH ensures that investments do not significantly harm environmental objectives, though its implementation is governed by each fund's specific legal framework rather than the Taxonomy Regulation itself.

In question number 5 it was clarified that the DNSH criteria outlined in the Taxonomy Delegated Acts are distinct from the European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS) requirements. While ESRS aims to ensure transparency regarding a company's sustainability impacts and risks, it does not impose specific performance thresholds. In contrast, the DNSH criteria are part of the EU Taxonomy's classification system and require compliance with defined quantitative or qualitative thresholds to confirm that an activity is environmentally sustainable. Under the Taxonomy Regulation, the environmentally sustainable activities must 'substantially contribute' to one of the six environmental objectives while 'doing no significant harm' to any of the other environmental objectives. As a result, ESRS disclosures alone are not sufficient to prove DNSH compliance, though the data provided through ESRS reporting can often support the necessary assessments. Questions regarding the specific classification of some activities along the DNSH (such as in transport, electricity, water supply, information and communication) are also answered.

Yet the principle's reach has not been uniformly strengthened. A significant and contested development was the partial waiver of DNSH introduced by Regulation (EU) 2023/435 — the REPowerEU amendment — which created a targeted exemption for measures improving energy infrastructure to meet immediate security of supply needs for oil and gas. Civil society organizations, including CAN Europe (CAN (Climate Action Network Europe) 2022), strongly

criticized this derogation, arguing that it opened the door to financing fossil fuel projects with no serious environmental safeguards and set a damaging precedent contrary to the RRF's core sustainability pillars. This episode, alongside earlier controversies around gas investments in the Czech Republic, Poland, Romania and the Pisão dam in Portugal, illustrates the persistent tension between DNSH as a formal requirement and its application in practice (Miller et al. 2022).

1.5 Sector-specific criteria

A recurring challenge identified in both academic and practitioner literature is that DNSH, by design, must be applied in highly varied sectoral and geographic contexts, yet requires sufficient consistency to function as a meaningful safeguard. Financial institutions and implementing entities have consistently reported that the absence of clear quantifiable thresholds and the technical complexity of sector-specific assessments are the main barriers to effective DNSH implementation. The technical screening criteria developed through delegated acts represent the Commission's primary attempt to address this problem — translating the principle into sector-specific, scientifically grounded requirements.

The content of DNSH is further shaped by **sector-specific technical screening criteria** and interpretive guidance. In relation to climate change adaptation, DNSH requires that physical climate risks—whether acute, such as floods and storms, or chronic, such as sea-level rise—be identified through a detailed **Climate Risk and Vulnerability Assessment (CRVA)**, covering all phases of a project. These assessments must be site-specific, using up-to-date data and methodologies, and result in adaptation solutions—either physical or non-physical—tailored to mitigate material risks over the activity's expected lifetime. The implementation period for such solutions begins once the CRVA and identification of solutions are completed, with effectiveness defined by the reduction of risks to a level that avoids major climate-related disruptions. Importantly, both physical and non-physical adaptation measures are valid, depending on the risk context. In terms of pollution prevention and control, recent amendments to Appendix C of the DNSH criteria (as of 27 June 2023) refined the rules around hazardous chemical substances. The concept of “essential use for society” was replaced by a requirement for operators to prove that no suitable alternatives exist and that any use is under strict controlled conditions.

The DNSH criteria for **pollution prevention and control**, revised in June 2023, focus on managing hazardous chemicals, particularly substances of very high concern under the Regulation on the registration, evaluation, authorisation and restriction of chemicals (REACH). The amendments removed the earlier concept of “essential use for society” and instead require operators to demonstrate that no safer alternatives are available and that any use is conducted under strictly controlled conditions. A 0.1% concentration limit for such substances in mixtures and articles has also been introduced. These changes reinforce the precautionary principle and strengthen safeguards in sectors handling hazardous materials.

For **biodiversity and ecosystem protection**, DNSH criteria prohibit construction on greenfield sites of high ecological value or in habitats supporting endangered species unless specific

conservation conditions are met. The economic activity must comply with recognized conservation management plans, and the area affected must show a net gain in biodiversity relative to its prior condition. This gain must not be used merely for offsetting negative impacts elsewhere, underscoring the non-compensatory nature of the DNSH principle in this domain.

In sector-specific applications, such as **construction and real estate**, the DNSH principle translates into technical requirements like ensuring that at least 70% of construction waste is reused or recycled, and that materials used emit limited levels of formaldehyde. For renovation projects, similar waste and pollutant controls apply. Demonstration of compliance may involve submission of permits or assessments conducted under EU environmental directives.

Therefore, **DNSH is not a one-size-fits-all standard but a principle requiring contextualized, scientifically grounded assessment procedures** that are embedded within the broader EU sustainable finance framework.

1.6 Recent developments

Recent developments suggest growing awareness within the EU of the need to balance environmental integrity with practical feasibility. The **REPowerEU strategy**, adopted in response to the energy crisis following Russia's invasion of Ukraine, temporarily exempts certain investments in energy infrastructure from the DNSH requirement, prioritizing energy security and diversification. While this shortcut provides immediate relief, it highlights the unresolved tensions between environmental integrity and practical feasibility. Meanwhile, the **Taxo4 report** by the Platform on Sustainable Finance tentatively suggests reviewing DNSH criteria to improve consistency and usability, though its recommendations remain modest in scope (Famà 2025).

The European Commission has adopted delegated acts to amend ESRS—including measures that postpone certain ESRS disclosure requirements—and it has proposed legislative amendments (including the 'stop-the-clock' Directive and an Omnibus 'content' proposal) to delay application timelines and narrow the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive's (CSRD) scope (European Commission 2025a). In April 2025 the European Parliament agreed to approve the European Commission's 'stop-the-clock' directive, delaying the implementation of key sustainability reporting and due diligence regulations, including the CSRD and the Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (CSDDD). This move, adopted with an overwhelming majority (531 votes for, 69 against, 17 abstentions), is part of the broader Omnibus I simplification package. Under the revised timetable, a large share of companies will begin CSRD reporting later than originally planned—large companies will first report for financial year 2027 (published in 2028), while listed SMEs (small and medium-sized enterprises, i.e., firms with fewer than 250 employees and either annual turnover \leq €50 million or a balance sheet total \leq €43 million) follow one year later, reporting for financial year 2028 (published in 2029).

In parallel, the first wave of companies covered by the CSDDD is expected to apply due diligence obligations from 2028, following an extended transposition period for Member States

(until 26 July 2027, per the European Parliament's postponement decision)(European Parliament 2025). These delays and scope reductions are being presented as efforts to give companies more time to adjust while still maintaining sustainability goals. Furthermore, in July 2025 the Commission adopted a Delegated Act amending the Taxonomy Disclosures, Climate and Environmental Delegated Acts, aimed at cutting red tape for companies under the EU taxonomy framework (Directorate-General for Financial Stability, Financial Services and Capital Markets Union 2025). These simplification measures are intended to reduce the administrative burden while preserving the taxonomy's core climate and environmental goals. They are applied from 1 January 2026, covering the 2025 financial year (with the option for companies to apply them already for the 2026 financial year if preferred (European Commission 2025b).

These changes do not amount to a fundamental transformation of DNSH, but they do show that the principle is evolving in response to practical challenges, political controversy, and competing policy objectives.

1.7 DNSH and the Green Oath

The European Commission's European Green Deal introduces the idea of a **"Green Oath: do no harm"** (European Commission 2019), which echoes the ethos of the Hippocratic Oath, an ancient pledge attributed to the Greek physician Hippocrates (5th century BCE) that sets out ethical principles for doctors. It signals a broad commitment to ensuring that environmental, climate, and sustainability goals are integrated into all legislative proposals and funding decisions of the EU. The European Green Deal aims to cut emissions by at least 50% by 2030, rising towards 55%, while legally binding the 2050 neutrality goal through the European Climate Law.

However, it remains **unclear whether this Green Oath aligns with the DNSH principle**: While the DNSH under the Taxonomy has a clear legal framework and technical screening criteria, the Green Oath appears more symbolic— evoking a broad moral commitment rather than a binding legal standard. The language of the Green Deal—using "should" instead of "shall"— implies a strong expectation rather than a legal obligation. This reflects an intention to align all EU actions with the green transition, even though some policies (e.g. in transport or agriculture) may inherently conflict with environmental goals (European Commission 2022).

The Commission has attempted to operationalize the Green Oath by incorporating it into its *Better Regulation Guidelines*, which aim to ensure high-quality, sustainability-aware legislation (Famà 2025). However, in said Guidelines the DNSH principle is neither clearly defined nor directly linked to the Taxonomy Regulation, raising concerns about coherence. The regulatory impact assessment (RIA) process now includes a DNSH check, requiring legislative proposals to demonstrate how they avoid significant environmental harm. Still, the **vagueness** of the Better Regulation's DNSH application risks reducing it to a procedural formality, rather than a substantive environmental safeguard. While the Green Oath and DNSH principle are intended to mainstream environmental considerations across EU policymaking, they originate from different contexts and may operate under different logics—one ethical and aspirational, the other legal and technical. This asymmetry creates a structural tension: where DNSH

demands demonstrable, evidence-based justification that no significant harm has occurred, the Green Oath relies on normative intent and institutional culture. In practice, the two instruments may reinforce each other — the Oath cultivating the political will necessary to apply DNSH rigorously — but they may equally diverge, particularly when the procedural demands of DNSH assessment are met formally without the substantive ethical engagement the Oath envisions. The lack of coordination between them could undermine the consistency and clarity of the EU's sustainability governance (Famà 2025).

1.8 DNSH principle and the precautionary principle

The precautionary principle is a foundational approach to risk management that emphasizes caution in the face of scientific uncertainty. It asserts that when there is a plausible risk that a policy, action, or innovation could cause harm to human health or the environment—and when scientific consensus on the matter is lacking—decision-makers should refrain from proceeding with the proposed measure. This principle encourages erring on the side of safety, even in the absence of conclusive evidence, to prevent potential irreversible damage.

The precautionary principle originated in German law, where it is known as the *Vorsorgeprinzip*. It was first implemented in air pollution legislation during the 1970s and was officially established in the German federal government's first environmental program in 1971 as a core environmental policy principle. Since then, the principle has been adopted by other administrative levels and extended beyond environmental protection into other fields. International references to the precautionary principle appeared in environmental agreements in the 1980s, beginning with the 1985 Vienna Convention for the Protection of the Ozone Layer, which mentions 'precautionary measures' in its preamble. In the 1992 Rio Declaration on Environment and Development, the precautionary approach was elevated to a guiding principle in forest management. Some international agreements reference the principle without defining it, while others follow the Rio Declaration's formulation—stating that a lack of complete scientific certainty should not be used as an excuse to delay action to prevent environmental degradation. Since the early 1990s, the precautionary principle has been explicitly or implicitly included in nearly all major international environmental treaties. It was incorporated into the 1992 Maastricht Treaty and later into the environmental legislation of many European countries.

Within the European Union, the precautionary principle is enshrined in **Article 191 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU)**, where it underpins environmental policy and regulation and reinforces the EU's commitment to sustainable development and public health protection. It was formally articulated in a **European Commission Communication of February 2000** (COM/2000/0001 final), which provided a clear definition and outlined the conditions under which it should be applied. This document emphasized transparency, proportionality, and consistency in implementation, ensuring that precautionary measures are scientifically justified, subject to review, and balanced against potential benefits and costs (European Commission 2000).

The EU has applied the precautionary principle across several major regulatory frameworks, including chemical policy (Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 — REACH) and food safety (Regulation (EC) No 178/2002). Crucially, this principle also offers a normative backdrop for the DNSH requirement in the EU Taxonomy and other sustainable finance frameworks. Both the precautionary principle and DNSH share an emphasis on avoiding irreversible or disproportionate environmental damage under conditions of uncertainty. Scholars have argued that linking DNSH more explicitly to the precautionary principle could strengthen its credibility and legal defensibility by clarifying the basis for action in the face of incomplete knowledge (von Schomberg 2014). This linkage also reinforces the proportionality element in DNSH—mirroring the doctrine of double effect and proportionality logic already embedded in EU law—and would help shift DNSH away from a purely technocratic exercise toward a broader framework aligned with sustainable development and public health protection.

The precautionary principle justifies public policy and other actions in situations characterized by scientific complexity, uncertainty, and lack of knowledge, where action may be necessary to avoid or reduce potentially serious or irreversible threats to human health and/or the environment. This should be based on appropriate scientific evidence and a balanced consideration of the advantages and disadvantages of both action and inaction, including their distribution. In other words, the precautionary principle allows for a lower standard of proof of harm in policymaking when the cost of waiting for more conclusive evidence could be high and/or the harm irreversible.

The precautionary principle may only be invoked when:

- The potential negative consequences have been identified;
- An assessment of available scientific data has been conducted;
- The level of scientific uncertainty has been evaluated.

If, after these steps, a high risk is determined, the responsible authority must decide which measures to take—whether to regulate via legal instruments or whether informational and educational actions are sufficient.

Following ClientEarth's interpretation, **the precautionary principle should be firmly embedded as a foundational tenet in the unified DNSH guidance**. This principle dictates that projects or measures which are insufficiently defined, lack essential technical detail, or are devoid of robust scientific evidence required for a proper DNSH assessment, should be ineligible for public funding or regulatory approval (ClientEarth 2024). In practice, **this means shifting the burden of proof**: the proponent of a project must demonstrate—with clarity and scientific substantiation—that the intervention will not cause significant harm to any environmental objective. Ambiguity, data gaps, or speculative benefits are insufficient to justify funding under the DNSH framework.

Furthermore, the precautionary principle requires that **assessments extend beyond immediate and isolated impacts to include long-term, cumulative, and systemic consequences**. Projects must be evaluated not only for their present-day effects but also for their potential to entrench harmful practices through lock-in effects—where infrastructure,

behavioural patterns, or supply chains make future harm more likely or harder to reverse. In this light, the absence of absolute scientific certainty about the potential environmental harm cannot be used as a justification to proceed with an activity that carries plausible risks of significant degradation.

This approach implies **a temporal inversion of the DNSH logic: rather than applying DNSH only after evidence of significant harm emerges, the precautionary principle activates DNSH scrutiny earlier in the decision-making process.** If **credible reasons exist to suspect that a project or measure might significantly harm the environment**—even if definitive scientific consensus is not yet established—**then the initiative should be halted or re-evaluated prior to formal DNSH assessment.** In such cases, **the application of precaution acts as a filter:** interventions with uncertain yet potentially serious impacts are excluded not because harm has been proven, but because it cannot be reasonably ruled out.

Embedding this interpretation of the precautionary principle into DNSH guidance ensures that the framework operates **as a protective mechanism in line with the EU Treaties and environmental law, rather than as a procedural box-ticking exercise.** It aligns with broader sustainability goals by prioritizing ecological integrity in situations of scientific uncertainty, and it enhances the legitimacy and credibility of public funding decisions in the context of the green transition.

1.9 DNSH in international law

Although the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) has been identifying environmental harm since its first Global Environment Outlook in 1995, the 2019 GEO-6: Healthy Planet, Healthy People (UN Environment 2019) represents a major conceptual and scientific advance. It not only documents extensive deterioration of air quality and climate-related pressures but also provides a rigorous scientific assessment linking this ecological decline directly to human health and well-being in the Anthropocene era. This language conveys the magnitude (wide-ranging, global in scope), the intensity (profound impacts), and the consequences (directly linked to human health and well-being) of this degradation. The report concludes that current governance systems are largely inadequate to respond to this escalating crisis. While international legal frameworks aimed at preventing serious harm to other states and ecosystems are evolving, they are doing so at a pace far too slow to match the rapidly intensifying scale of environmental damage (Gupta and Schmeier 2020). By framing environmental degradation as measurable and consequential harm, GEO-6 reinforces the normative foundation of the DNSH principle in international environmental law—underscoring that states and other actors have a duty to prevent activities that cause substantial or transboundary damage to ecosystems and people.

The 'no-harm rule', also known as the principle of prevention, is a well-established norm of customary international law, which obliges states to prevent, reduce, and control the risk of environmental harm to other states and areas beyond national jurisdiction (Brownlie 2019). Rooted in the general duty of good neighbourliness and the sovereign equality of states, the rule reflects the idea that the exercise of sovereignty must not result in damage to the

environment of other states or to the global commons. In international environmental law, the principle has primarily functioned as a basis for state responsibility and liability in relation to acts that, while not expressly prohibited, nonetheless cause transboundary environmental harm. The scope of the 'no-harm' duty has progressively evolved through international jurisprudence. Initially confined to preventing harm caused by private actors within a state's own territory, it has since expanded to encompass a broader obligation: not only to protect foreign nationals from wrongful acts committed by private individuals, but also to investigate, prosecute, and punish those responsible for causing injury to aliens or their property. The no-harm rule therefore functions as a cornerstone of **due-diligence-based** environmental governance: it establishes an **ex-ante obligation** to take reasonable measures to prevent significant transboundary harm, while also providing a normative basis for responsibility where harm nonetheless occurs (University of Turin and Kentache 2024). The no-harm rule operates between sovereign states, targeting transboundary damage to the environment or to the rights of other states, and it functions primarily as a basis for state responsibility under international law. The DNSH principle, by contrast, applies at the level of individual economic activities and investments within the EU regulatory framework. The no-harm principle, by placing emphasis on transboundary harm rather than environmental protection per se, stops short of embracing a genuine preventive dimension in relation to domestic or intra-jurisdictional ecological damage. The DNSH principle, in this sense, reaches further: it is not merely a rule of interstate relations but a structuring norm for sustainable economic governance.

Unlike the UN Environment Report, which is more descriptive, DNSH is a legal principle that obliges states to prevent environmental harm beyond their borders, a responsibility codified in Principle 21 of the 1972 Stockholm Declaration (Sands et al. 2018). The International Court of Justice has affirmed DNSH as customary international law, notably in its 1996 *Nuclear Weapons Advisory Opinion*, framing it as a duty of due diligence rather than a guarantee of outcomes (Mayer and Zahar 2021). In its 1996 *Advisory Opinion on the Legality of the Threat or Use of Nuclear Weapons*, the International Court of Justice affirmed that the *Do No Significant Harm* (DNSH) principle forms part of customary international law. DNSH entails a *positive obligation*, requiring states to exercise due diligence in preventing environmental harm (Mayer and Zahar 2021). A recent example is Article 2 of the UNESCO (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization) Declaration of Ethical Principles in Relation to Climate Change, published in 2017.

Importantly, DNSH is framed as a *duty of conduct rather than of result*, meaning that states are expected to take all appropriate measures to prevent activities within their jurisdiction from causing transboundary environmental damage (Dupuy and Viñuales 2018). Accordingly, **states are required to adopt preventive measures** to avoid transboundary environmental harm and has been recognized as a corollary to the principle of permanent sovereignty over natural resources. It emphasizes not only restraint but **proactive risk management** (Famà 2025).

While the EU's use of DNSH shares its preventive ethos, it diverges significantly in scope and application. Within the EU, DNSH does not primarily govern inter-state environmental responsibilities. Instead, it operates as a **regulatory tool for assessing and excluding**

activities with significant negative environmental impacts **in both public and private finance**—serving as a benchmark for sustainability rather than as a framework for cross-border environmental accountability (Famà 2025).

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1.10 DNSH in EU Research Funding Programs

The European Research Area (ERA) operates as a unified research and innovation (R&I) space that aims to foster scientific excellence while supporting strategic objectives such as the green and digital transitions. Within this context, the DNSH principle has become an increasingly visible cross-cutting reference in EU policymaking and public spending, including instruments that fund R&I. In practice, 'DNSH' operates in **different ways depending on the policy domain**: it can function **as a legally defined compliance concept** (notably in sustainable finance and certain public investment instruments) or **as a broader programme principle** guiding how projects anticipate, minimise, and manage environmental harm (European Commission 2021b).

In Horizon Europe, this creates a recurring source of confusion: programme documents have often used the label 'DNSH' even where the operational intent resembles a broader 'do no harm' ethos (Green Deal / 'Green Oath') rather than a strict taxonomy-style compliance test. The comparison table below clarifies these two logics before turning to how Horizon Europe has implemented (and progressively narrowed) the visibility of DNSH in proposal practice.

	Do no Significant Harm (DNSH)	Do No Harm (DNH)
Item	EU Taxonomy / sustainable finance law: DNSH is defined with reference to Article 17 of Regulation (EU) 2020/852, and is further specified via delegated acts/criteria.	European Green Deal 'do no harm' ambition. In Horizon Europe, the principle is typically operationalised via programme guidance and, where applicable, call/topic templates (often framed using the term "DNSH principle").
Origin / primary home	To assess whether an economic activity can be treated as environmentally sustainable (classification/disclosure contexts), including by ensuring it does not	To steer programmes/projects (including R&I funding) to avoid causing relevant environmental harm, typically via proposal-level explanation of methodology, risks and mitigation, and via project governance during implementation.

	significantly harm any of the six environmental objectives.	
Legal status / enforceability Purpose (what it is for)	Legal definition in EU Regulation; can be linked to disclosure/compliance obligations and (depending on instrument) eligibility or classification decisions.	Policy/programme principle. At project level in Horizon Europe, Commission responses indicate it may be voluntary and not necessarily affect proposal scoring; specific calls may nevertheless require applicants to address it and it can be followed up during implementation.
Assessment unit (what is assessed)	Economic activity (and associated boundaries used for taxonomy alignment/disclosures).	Project/action (design choices, work packages, pilots/demonstrators, procurement, fieldwork), assessed contextually and 'where relevant'.
Criteria indicators (how assessed)	Structured concept in Article 17; for certain activities, technical screening criteria (TSC) and/or generic DNSH criteria provide more specific conditions/thresholds and evidence mapping.	Often narrative and context-dependent; depth and criteria can vary across calls; relies on judgement plus risk management, monitoring and accountability arrangements rather than a single uniform checklist.
Operationalisation (how applied)	Documentation mapped to objectives/criteria; tends toward structured compliance/disclosure when TSC apply.	Implemented through guidance and templates (e.g., 'where relevant, describe DNSH/DNH'), plus risk registers, mitigation/monitoring plans, and governance mechanisms; operationalisation differs by programme/call.

Note: Horizon Europe documents often use the term "Do No Significant Harm (DNSH)" when explaining the programme-level 'do no harm' ambition; here, DNH denotes that broader policy/programme principle and its Horizon implementation practice.

Table 2 –Do No Significant Harm (DNSH) vs DO No Harm (DNH) in early comparison

Obligations for Member States to provide evidence of DNSH compliance are most clearly established in the RRF context, where DNSH is treated as a substantive condition for measures in national plans. Similarly, DNSH language also appears in other EU policy domains (including certain state aid frameworks), where it can be used as a factor in Commission assessment. These contexts should be distinguished from **Horizon Europe**, where DNSH has mainly functioned as a **programme steering principle** rather than a uniform compliance test (European Commission 2021b). In the Communication of the Commission C 528/10 of 2021 it is stated that member states must provide evidence as to whether the project complies with the

DNSH principle and that the Commission will consider compliance with this principle as an important factor in its assessment (European Commission 2021a).

In Horizon Europe WP 2021–2022, references to the DNSH principle (linked to Article 17 of the EU Taxonomy Regulation) were included at programming level and in several Pillar II work programme parts, notably Cluster 4 (Digital, Industry and Space), Cluster 5 (Climate, Energy and Mobility), and Cluster 6 (Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment). At the project level, applicants could describe—where relevant—how their methodology takes DNSH considerations into account. At project level, DNSH was also reflected in the proposal Part B template, giving applicants the possibility—where relevant—to explain how their methodology and expected impacts relate to DNSH considerations (including potential impacts on environmental objectives). Importantly, Horizon Europe practice has been that **proposals are generally not scored for DNSH compliance** unless the **call/topic text explicitly makes it an assessment requirement** (with limited, clearly identified exceptions in specific instruments or topics). In other words, DNSH functioned mostly as an opportunity (or prompt) for applicants to demonstrate awareness of environmental risks and mitigation, rather than a standardised pass/fail test.

Between 2021 and 2024, stakeholders argued that DNSH is ill-suited to knowledge-based activities and can discourage honest appraisal of environmental risks in research funding and performance across Europe. Science Europe (2023) has highlighted that DNSH implementation should not add administrative burden for researchers or increase the complexity of project proposals and evaluations, and that any broader application of DNSH should be preceded by a thorough assessment of how it is currently implemented in Horizon Europe (Science Europe 2023). Therefore, for them the assessment should consider the feasibility, appropriateness, and proportionality of the DNSH principle to all framework programme projects, including those with lower technology readiness levels in Pillar II (Science Europe 2023).

Over time, Horizon Europe practice has moved toward more selective, topic-dependent visibility of DNSH alongside a broader 'do no harm' framing aligned with the Green Deal / 'Green Oath.' The practical implication for applicants is that—even when DNSH language appeared in guidance or background sections—it did not automatically become a scored evaluation criterion unless explicitly required by the topic conditions. Applicants were nevertheless encouraged to reflect on minimising the project's environmental footprint (e.g., methodological choices, procurement, travel, fieldwork practices) and to consider longer-term impacts of research outputs. Procedurally, DNSH references were removed from the standard Part B proposal template from the template update of 16 December 2024 onwards (Horizon Europe Work Programme 2023-2025), and DNSH references were also removed from the standard evaluation form. Applicants therefore address DNSH-related aspects only when the call text or topic conditions explicitly require it. A key point for applicants is that, even when DNSH was mentioned in guidance and background sections, proposals were generally not scored for DNSH compliance unless the work programme/topic explicitly made it an assessment requirement (with limited, clearly specified exceptions). Applicants were then expected to reflect on minimizing their projects' environmental footprint, including choices around methodology, travel, and the long-term effects of research outcomes. This narrows

DNSH's default visibility in proposal writing: DNSH is no longer a 'standard section to fill in,' but a conditional requirement triggered by specific topics. This change prevents treating DNSH as a universal compliance test across all Horizon projects, while preserving the ability to require it where it is most relevant.

Although the DNSH principle is inspiring the R&I landscape in Europe, additional detailed guidance is needed on how applicants/beneficiaries are to consider whether their proposed research raises risks of environmental harm, and what might be done to minimize, mitigate, or eliminate those risks. Indeed, the Commission charged a panel of experts to elaborate a Guidance Note on assessing and managing risks of environmental harm in EU-funded research, which supports the identification and management of potential environmental risks in EU-funded research projects (European Commission, forthcoming). It offers practical guidance on recognizing and addressing ethics issues related to environmental harm, enabling researchers and beneficiaries to integrate the 'do no harm' principle throughout the research lifecycle. It also aids ethics evaluators in assessing environmentally relevant ethical concerns and will be periodically updated to reflect evolving technologies and risks (European Commission, forthcoming).

The **omission of the term "significance"** in the most recent guidance suggests a need to clarify how 'significant harm' should be interpreted when DNSH is applied to EU R&I activities. In this context, DNSH should be understood as a **technical and legal threshold**, not a cost-benefit balancing test: **any potential harms must be avoided or mitigated so that residual impacts remain below the applicable 'significant harm' criteria**, rather than being justified by the expected benefits. This includes **detailed, measurable thresholds** for six environmental objectives such as climate change mitigation, pollution prevention, and biodiversity conservation. In other words, the adjective 'significant' introduces a **quantitative and regulatory filter** into the analysis of harm. As stated in the Joint Research Centre's (JRC) technical screening criteria report, "Significant harm is defined on the basis of scientific thresholds and regulatory standards" (JRC 2021). The adjective '*significant*' therefore serves as a **quantitative and normative filter**, distinguishing between environmental effects that are acceptable within policy-defined limits and those that would materially undermine an environmental objective. This approach does not imply that the harms addressed by the DNSH principle are minor in moral or human terms. Rather, it reflects a **proportionality mechanism**: within environmental regulation, some measurable impacts may be considered permissible if they remain below established thresholds and are outweighed by substantial positive contributions. This contrasts with the broader ethical 'do no harm' principle, which interprets harm as a setback to basic human interests or rights and therefore tends to reject any form of harm, even if unintended or small in scale. The distinction thus lies not in the moral weight of harm, but in the method and domain of its assessment—technical in the case of DNSH, ethical in the classical 'do no harm' tradition.

The intended policy and research audiences are: a) the European Commission Directorates (e.g., DG RTD, DG ENV, DG CLIMA): responsible for setting the strategic and regulatory framework for DNSH integration in R&I; b) the National Research Ministries and funding bodies; c) research institutions and universities; d) scientific evaluation committees and Horizon Europe Review Panels as well as e) independent Ethics and Environmental Impact

Review Board. The intended stakeholders with a voice are academic researchers and research managers, (Environmental) NGOs and think tanks: consulted in shaping DNSH-relevant frameworks and in identifying sectors or practices with potential environmental risks, industry and private sector innovators, EU Agencies (e.g., European Chemical Agency (ECHA), European Food and Safety Authority (EFSA) and European Environment Agency (EEA)) as well as Research Councils and Advisory Groups.

Besides these stakeholders it is possible also to identify intended stakeholders without a voice or whose perspective is not sufficiently being recognized:

Non-Human Stakeholders: ecosystems, animals, plants, insects, other living beings as well as microbial and soil ecosystems which are affected by research outcomes but not represented in governance structures.

Future Generations: those who will bear the long-term environmental consequences of today's R&I investments yet are not part of decision-making processes.

Marginalized and Underrepresented communities: particularly those in regions outside of the EU or in lower-income EU regions who may be indirectly affected by the environmental externalities of EU-funded R&I activities.

1.11 DNSH and Innovation policy

Innovation goals such as enhancing competitiveness and reinforcing European industry, recognized as priorities by the European Commission, carry the potential to conflict with interventions aimed at protecting the environment. A case currently under discussion concerns the repercussions of the EU Biotech Act, proposed in December 2025 with the stated ambition of strengthening competitiveness of European health biotechnology (Directorate-General for Health and Food Safety 2025). The EU Biotech Act pursues primarily innovation and industrial policy objectives, aiming to accelerate the development and scaling of biotechnological applications in Europe, streamlining and simplifying multiple existing EU regulations to reduce time-to-market through accelerated clinical trial timelines, risk-proportionate requirements, and regulatory sandboxes for novel products.

The scientific literature is unambiguous on the core point: the bioeconomy has emerged as a route to sustainability, but it is not inherently sustainable. Various risks and potential pitfalls have to be considered and avoided (Amato et al. 2023). A comparative study of European bioeconomy strategies (29 policy documents from 14 European countries and the European Union) finds that SDG 2 (zero hunger), SDG 12 (responsible consumption and production), and SDG 14 (life below water) exhibit more than 50% negative impacts from bioeconomy transitions, highlighting challenges such as increased competition for land, food security risks, and potential harm to marine ecosystems — impacts that official strategies had largely been underestimated (Warchold et al. 2026). In particular some strategies often neglect the principles of “equitable” and “fair & inclusive” transition and fail to consider potential unintended consequences or trade-offs for sustainability (Warchold et al. 2026; Proestou et al. 2024).

Where biotechnological innovations target an intensified use of biological resources, competing objectives arise: the expansion of biomass production, new industrial bioprocesses, and the large-scale exploitation of biological raw materials can exert growing pressure on land use, biodiversity, and water resources. More specifically, marginal lands are often used for biomass production, and these lands are frequently valuable for natural functions such as biodiversity; in some cases, bioeconomic production does not reduce greenhouse gas emissions as expected, and greenhouse gas emissions may result from land use changes as well as from energy use in the processing of biomass.

These dynamics are compounded at the regulatory level by the specific design choices embedded in the Biotech Act. Strategic projects can benefit from fast-tracked permit-granting processes — a maximum of 10 months for regular strategic projects and eight months for high-impact ones — and streamlined environmental assessments. Legal scholarship has identified precisely this kind of acceleration as a source of regulatory risk: regulatory sandboxes, as programmes that allow enterprises to test innovations in a regulated real-world setting, often entail a temporary relaxation of applicable standards, while maintaining protections to sustain regulatory goals such as safety and consumer protection— a balance whose stability under competitive pressure remains uncertain (Ala-Lahti 2024). The political drive to accelerate innovation and approval procedures may in practice lead to a shortening or weakening of assessment processes, unless these are explicitly safeguarded.

Since the DNSH principle operates primarily through financing instruments and funding logics, it frequently remains decoupled from sectoral innovation policy frameworks. As a result, sustainability requirements are not systematically integrated into the structural governance of research and innovation, giving rise to a **governance gap**. The European Environment Agency has acknowledged that trade-offs must be carefully assessed and managed, since bio-based solutions may involve land use, biodiversity, or social equity trade-offs that require consideration and governance, and sound decisions need strong evidence, impact analyses, and stakeholder input (European Environmental Agency (EEA) 2025). According to Ala-Lahti (2024) occasional recourse to precautionary measures is therefore justified as a means of addressing these uncertainties and mitigating potential hazards, even within the authorised development procedures of novel industrial technologies. This argument gains added weight from the finding that the data indicate a greater prevalence of challenges than strategies initially recognized, reinforcing the need for more comprehensive risk assessments. The precautionary principle, in this reading, is not an obstacle to innovation but a precondition for its legitimacy: by requiring that uncertainty be taken seriously rather than administratively suspended, it helps ensure that the acceleration enabled by regulatory sandboxes and streamlined permits does not become a mechanism for externalizing unquantified ecological and health risks onto future generations.

As the preceding analysis has shown, the precautionary principle fundamentally reorients the application logic of the DNSH within the broader appraisal of innovation policy. Rather than functioning as a reactive corrective — triggered only once evidence of harm has already materialized — it shifts the scrutiny of potential adverse effects to the earliest stages of the decision-making process, embedding harm prevention as a constitutive element of regulatory design rather than an afterthought to it. This inversion carries significant implications: it means

that the burden of demonstrating safety cannot be deferred until after deployment, and that scientific uncertainty itself — rather than proven injury — provides sufficient grounds for precautionary intervention.

It follows that **innovation policy measures must be far more systematically aligned with the principle of harm prevention than current frameworks allow.** Biotechnological development should be governed in ways that render efficiency and competitiveness not ends in themselves, but outcomes that are achieved within, and constrained by, the requirements of ecological responsibility and long-term sustainability. In the context of the EU Biotech Act, this demands that the acceleration of regulatory pathways, the liberalization of environmental assessment requirements, and the use of time-bound derogations be counterbalanced by robust, enforceable safeguards.

2. Contested applications, weaknesses and challenges of DNSH

The DNSH principle was not born as a technical instrument. In its original spirit, it carried the weight of **a broad moral imperative** — comparable to a sustainability-oriented Hippocratic Oath. The European Green Deal explicitly introduced the idea of a "Green Oath: do no harm," echoing the Hippocratic commitment and signalling that EU action should not undermine environmental goals (European Commission 2019). Yet the relationship between this aspirational Green Oath and the legally defined DNSH principle has never been clearly established. The regulatory impact assessment (RIA) process now includes a DNSH check, requiring legislative proposals to demonstrate how they avoid significant environmental harm. Still, the **vagueness** of the Better Regulation's DNSH application risks reducing it to a procedural formality, rather than a substantive environmental safeguard. While the Green Oath and DNSH principle are intended to mainstream environmental considerations across EU policymaking, they originate from different contexts and may operate under different logics— one ethical and aspirational, the other legal and technical. The lack of coordination between them could undermine the consistency and clarity of the EU's sustainability governance (Famà 2025).

This tension is not merely administrative. It reflects a deeper problem: what was originally conceived as a moral imperative risks being narrowed into familiar modes of scientific and bureaucratic evaluation. These dominant frameworks, however, are precisely those that have historically struggled to prevent significant environmental harms and to adequately address questions of justice — including the distribution of risks and benefits, intergenerational responsibilities, and the recognition of diverse cultural relationships with nature. This raises a fundamental question about their suitability to define, measure, and adjudicate harm in the context of DNSH.

Therefore, this chapter shows that the contested applications and weaknesses of DNSH are not incidental failures of implementation. They point to a deeper structural tension: the drive to render the principle operationalizable has progressively stripped it of the normative complexity on which it fundamentally depends. Concepts such as 'harm,' 'significance,' and 'nature' are inherently value-laden — and any framework that treats them as technical will reproduce, rather than resolve, the very problems DNSH was designed to address.

2.1 Transitional activities and the limits of DNSH

One of the most contested dimensions of DNSH concerns its treatment of so-called **transitional activities, particularly natural gas and nuclear power**. The original RRF Technical Guidance adopted a strict approach, making clear that mere compliance with existing environmental law or the completion of an environmental impact assessment does not automatically satisfy DNSH requirements. The aim was to ensure that no green transition effort inadvertently undermines other sustainability goals.

In practice, however, this strict logic has produced paradoxical outcomes. Technologies positioned as stepping stones away from more harmful alternatives — such as natural gas infrastructure replacing coal, or waste-to-energy facilities replacing landfills — are often deemed non-compliant simply because their environmental footprint remains too significant in absolute terms. Critics argue that this approach disregards real-world transition dynamics, penalizing projects that could deliver short-term emissions reductions while enabling broader systemic change (De Vincenti 2022). In effect, DNSH functions here as an implicit trade-off rule: a presumption against allowing gains in one environmental objective where notable burdens arise elsewhere.

Gibson's work on sustainability assessment offers a useful framework for navigating this tension. Rather than endorsing unconstrained pragmatic balancing, Gibson argues for trade-off avoidance where core sustainability requirements are at stake, permitting exceptions only under clearly articulated "least-worst" rules, after alternatives have been exhausted and with explicit justification and safeguards (Gibson 2006, 2013). This is consistent with the Commission's own DNSH guidance, which already considers factors such as feasible low-impact alternatives, best available performance, lifecycle impacts, and lock-in risks. What is missing, Gibson's approach suggests, is a transparent and bounded protocol for handling transitional cases — rather than relying on unspoken absolutism or ad hoc discretion.

This **restrictive logic is especially visible in the treatment of fossil fuel-based energy**. The RRF guidance treats natural gas power and heat generation, as well as related infrastructure, as generally incompatible with DNSH. Waste-to-energy plants face similar exclusion, even where they reduce landfill use, on the grounds that they increase incineration and undermine circular economy objectives. The framework thus leaves little room for 'less bad' or transitional projects.

A **contrasting logic emerged with the Complementary Climate Delegated Act of 2022**, which **opened the possibility for certain natural gas and nuclear activities to qualify under the EU Taxonomy under strict conditions**. This created a notable tension between the stricter RRF guidance and the more flexible approach of the evolving Taxonomy framework — a tension that remains unresolved. **Framing fossil gas ('natural gas') as a transitional fuel is highly contested** on climate, health, and geopolitical grounds. Any near-term CO₂ advantage at the smokestack can be erased by upstream methane leakage, whose high short-term warming potency undermines climate targets when viewed on policy-relevant horizons (e.g., next 10–20 years). AR6 (the IPCC's Sixth Assessment Report) underscores why methane leakage is decisive for near-term warming: fossil CH₄ is assigned ~82–83 (GWP20) and ~29–30 (GWP100), making climate outcomes highly sensitive to losses along the gas supply chain (production, processing, transmission, Liquefied Natural Gas (LNG) liquefaction/boil-off, shipping, distribution) (IPCC 2023; IPCC 2022). While gas can emit less CO₂ per kWh than coal at the point of combustion, life-cycle assessments show that even modest leakage can erase this advantage—especially on a 20-year basis—calling into question narratives of gas as a 'clean' or 'transition' fuel. New gas infrastructure (pipelines, LNG terminals, Combined Cycle Gas Turbine plants) also creates carbon lock-in and stranded-asset risks that can crowd out investment in renewables, storage, and efficiency under tightening climate policy (Brauers 2022). These concerns intersect with governance criteria such as DNSH, and with security and

ethics issues? given continued EU purchases of Russian gas since 2022. Finally, gas combustion contributes to NO_x and indoor NO₂ exposure in homes, with documented respiratory health implications; whereas electrification (heat pumps/induction) and ventilation reduce these risks and add co-benefits.

2.2 Technocratic approach and weaknesses in the Technical Guidance

The implementation of the DNSH principle in the RRP reveals a technocratic and overly simplified approach that risks reducing the principle to a formalistic administrative requirement rather than a meaningful environmental safeguard. According to the Technical Guidance originally published in 2021 'significant harm' is explained as harm undermining the 6 environmental objectives (Climate Change Mitigation; Climate Change Adaptation; Sustainable Use and Protection of Water and Marine Resources; Transition to a Circular Economy; Pollution Prevention and Control and Protection; and Restoration of Biodiversity and Ecosystems) set out in the regulation.

The approach used is:

- a) **contextual** (what counts as 'significant' depends on the sector, scale, and mitigation measures);
- b) **threshold-based** (there are technical screening criteria that define acceptable levels of impact); and
- c) **risk-managed** (DNSH allows for trade-offs, provided that risks are minimized and managed transparently).

The DNSH principle puts great emphasis on 'significant.' The principle states that to avoid harm is generally impossible and thus the measures concentrate on the avoidance of what is perceived as a 'significant harm'. However, even from a quantitative point of view, the **Technical Guidance lacked the analytical depth necessary for rigorous environmental evaluation** (Miller et al. 2022). Life cycle assessments, for example, were deemed unnecessary, with broad 'considerations' deemed sufficient—thus avoiding the complexity of full impact analyses. Similarly, the use of the Technical Screening Criteria (TSC) from the EU taxonomy was made optional, leading to inconsistent application across Member States. Furthermore, the guidance permitted flexible interpretation, allowing countries to justify exceptions—even for fossil fuel-based projects—which ultimately diluted the transformative intent of the DNSH principle.

In addition to the technical weaknesses, this reliance on established technical tools fails to engage with the moral and contextual dimensions of environmental harm and risks transforming DNSH into a procedural box-ticking exercise. This undermines its precautionary and ethical ambitions.

2.3 Problems for accountability

These aspects underscore a structural weakness in EU environmental governance: **the Taxonomy operates as a classification system, not a prohibition mechanism**, which allows harmful activities to escape scrutiny so long as they are not claiming to be green (Famà 2025). The binary grading by the European Commission concerning RRP (either fully compliant with DNSH or not compliant), despite the acknowledgment of differing quality levels in national analyses, fails to differentiate between high- and low-quality applications. Moreover, it obscures learning opportunities and areas for improvement and **encourages minimal compliance rather than genuine transformation** (Miller et al. 2022). Furthermore, it can lead to perverse incentives, because a company might opt out of being classified as sustainable to avoid scrutiny under DNSH. Activities not seeking green finance or sustainability labels may still pose major environmental risks, yet fall outside the Taxonomy's remit, creating regulatory blind spots. Moreover, if DNSH applies only to the subset of “green” activities, the rest of the economy may continue to operate in unsustainable ways without comparable oversight. This would cause a problem for public accountability.

Moreover, the DNSH principle added complexity to public project approvals, creating political reluctance. The Trilogue negotiations further weakened DNSH standards in the Taxonomy (Miller et al. 2022). Without robust institutional support and inter-agency coordination, DNSH risks being seen as a bureaucratic hurdle rather than a strategic tool for promoting sustainability (Famà 2025). Thus, instead of serving as a transformative principle, DNSH risks becoming a symbolic gesture that reinforces existing power structures, imposes burdensome administrative procedures without meaningful oversight, and ultimately enables environmental harms to persist under the guise of technocratic rationality and bureaucratic efficiency.

The DNSH principle **operates primarily ex ante** (as described in the previous section), meaning it is applied before projects are implemented, without any substantive mechanisms for post-hoc evaluation. **This lack of ex post assessment significantly weakens accountability**, as it prevents actors from being held responsible for the full trajectory of their decisions and actions. In practice, this creates a regulatory gap in which potential harms that only become visible over time remain unaddressed, undermining both transparency and long-term responsibility.

Social Labs highlight

Findings from the RE4GREEN Social Labs (Deliverable 2.3) provide empirical support for concerns about accountability problems in the current enactment of the DNSH principle, while also highlighting conditions under which DNSH could function more effectively. Across R&I domains, participants largely experienced DNSH as an ex-ante compliance exercise rather than as a mechanism for ongoing responsibility, learning, or correction. It was also argued in the Social Labs that the binary framing of DNSH assessments encouraged minimal compliance: once projects are considered DNSH-compliant, there are few incentives or institutional pathways to revisit assessments, monitor downstream impacts, or strengthen mitigation measures over time.

At the same time, the Social Labs did not regard DNSH as inherently symbolic or futile. When applied in collective settings - such as committee-style assessments involving multiple forms of expertise - DNSH facilitated reflection on indirect, long-term, and otherwise overlooked harms, and helped establish a shared language for discussing environmental responsibility. Participants therefore emphasised that accountability failures are not only a matter of regulatory design, but also of institutional capacity. Limited expertise, time constraints, and a lack of supporting infrastructures constrained researchers' ability to engage meaningfully with DNSH, even where willingness to do so existed.

Social Labs consistently rejected individualised accountability. Participants argued that meaningful responsibility for environmental harm cannot rest with individual researchers or ethics committees alone, but must be distributed across institutions, funders, and research governance bodies. Without such institutional embedding and capacity-building, DNSH risks functioning as a procedural filter that satisfies formal requirements while leaving underlying environmental risks insufficiently addressed.

2.4 Ecomodernist logic of control

Rather than developing new evaluative methods that align with the ethical and precautionary aspirations initially associated with DNSH, the Commission has opted to operationalize it through established, technical frameworks for environmental risk assessment. This move reflects a deeper tension: what was originally conceived as a broad, almost moral imperative—

comparable to the Hippocratic Oath—is being reduced to familiar modes of scientific and bureaucratic evaluation. These dominant frameworks, however, are precisely those that have historically failed to prevent significant environmental harms, casting doubt on their suitability to define and adjudicate harm anew.

The interviews with government officials conducted by (Miller et al. 2022) and her group revealed several critical challenges that hindered the effective and coherent application of the DNSH principle across EU Member States. A recurrent theme was the **lack of sufficient data and analytical capacity to support robust assessments**, which left many administrations struggling to substantiate whether proposed measures would do no significant harm. Compounding this was the intense time pressure under which the RRP had to be developed, coupled with the absence of any prior models or institutional memory for how to implement DNSH effectively. The interviews also underscored the **diversity in national approaches**: some countries adopted centralized systems with coordinated oversight, while others relied on decentralized frameworks, leading to significant variation in expertise and procedural clarity. Furthermore, the bilateral pre-approval processes between member states and the European Commission lacked transparency, particularly regarding measures that were excluded from the plans—information that could have provided valuable precedents for other countries. Altogether, this operational fragmentation significantly weakened the overall coherence and consistency of DNSH implementation across the EU.

Furthermore, there are limitations of attempting to objectively and definitively quantify harm, especially when harm is inherently contextual, contested, and relational. The effort to apply an **ecomodernist logic of control**—where uncertainty is treated as a problem to be managed by technical means—fails to accommodate the complex social, political, and environmental entanglements that shape real-world impacts (Bernstein et al. 2023; Andersen and Massa 2000). **Assessing harm is not a purely technical matter; it involves deeply normative questions**: what types of harm matter, over which timescales, to whom, and who gets to decide what thresholds count as “significant”? These are not simply scientific questions but “trans-scientific” ones, as they resist precise answers and require interpretation, debate, and negotiation across diverse perspectives.

Social Labs highlight

Social lab participants also noted that socio-environmental harms, such as impacts on communities, social cohesion, cultural practices, or lived experiences of environmental change, were difficult to articulate within DNSH assessment while quantifiable measures seemed more favourable. In several labs, participants explicitly questioned whether these unquantifiable harms “counted” within DNSH assessments at all, illustrating how the framework implicitly privileges forms of knowledge aligned with scientific measurement and administrative comparability.

The reference to “significant” in the DNSH principle introduces a key dimension of **proportionality**—the idea that harms may be acceptable if outweighed by corresponding or greater benefits, provided those harms remain within an undefined but assumed acceptable threshold. This notion presupposes that harm is not entirely avoidable, especially in environmental matters, and instead must be minimized or justified relative to context. Such reasoning is historically rooted in moral and political philosophy, particularly in the *doctrine of double effect*, which holds that it can be morally permissible to cause harm as a foreseen side effect of pursuing a morally justified good end (McIntyre 2001; Anscombe 1958). Within this framework, what matters is not only the consequences of an action but also the intent and moral quality of the act itself. In the political realm, the same logic applies to state coercion—namely, the justification of restricting liberties or imposing regulations when actions are likely to cause harm to others or to shared goods like the environment. Here, too, the legitimacy of such collective interventions hinges on an account of harm that is neither purely subjective nor merely technical.

However, what is really understood as “significant harm” in comparison to “harm” is **conceived in an economic and narrow quantitative way**. This technocratic framing of DNSH is problematic because in sustainability science and environmental policy, discussions about environmental damage frequently overlook the **interrelationships between land and embedded cultural meanings, such as social ties, histories, and memories**. Anthropological critiques emphasize that environmental harm may not only entail degradation of ecosystems or property loss, but also the **erasure of cultural knowledge** deeply tied to specific environments (Kirsch 2001). As demonstrated, for example, in legal analyses of the Marshall Islands case following U.S. nuclear testing, Indigenous claims of harm—centred on cultural loss and situated experiences—struggle to gain traction within **property-based legal and economic frameworks** that narrowly define damage in terms of land or material assets (Kirsch 2001).

Moreover, this proportional understanding of harm raises at least two major concerns. First, the distribution of environmental costs and benefits is rarely symmetrical: those who gain from

environmentally beneficial policies are often not those who bear the harms. The case of **nuclear energy** illustrates this tension vividly, as the advantages of low-carbon power accrue mainly to present generations and wealthier regions, while the **long-term burdens of radioactive waste** fall on future generations and on communities in other countries. Second, in cases of **irreversible harms**—such as severe ecological degradation, the destruction of cultural heritage, or violations of fundamental human rights—**proportional compensation becomes morally and practically impossible**. Even when those harmed and those who benefit are the same individuals or communities, reparations cannot fully restore what was lost. Some forms of symbolic or non-economic compensation may mitigate such losses, but they remain **qualitatively inadequate** relative to the gravity of the harm.

These limitations reveal that the proportional logic embedded in the DNSH framework, while administratively useful, cannot resolve deeper **ethical and intergenerational justice dilemmas**. It therefore calls for a complementary normative reflection on the kinds of harm that are **never proportionate**—that is, harms which, by their irreversible or distributively unjust nature, should fall outside the permissible scope of the “significance” calculus altogether.

2.5 Emergence of structural harms

Modern antitrust and innovation scholarship increasingly argues that “significant harm” can take *structural* forms that are not visible through short-term price effects—especially in digital, multi-sided markets where services may be offered at a monetary price of zero. On this view, a narrow focus on consumer prices can miss how concentrated platform ecosystems entrench gatekeeper power and distort the competitive process, including incentives to innovate and to allow others to innovate (e.g., via control over distribution channels, interfaces, data access, and standards) (Khan 2017). These dynamics are tightly linked to well-established mechanisms in the economics of networks and standards: network effects can tip markets toward dominant “systems,” compatibility choices can generate “excess inertia” that delays superior standards, and switching costs can lock users—and even public institutions—into incumbents, creating durable ex post power. Building on this structural tradition, Showalter and Edelson (2024) have theorized “captured innovation,” where monopolists may still innovate but strategically constrain release or condition deployment to protect the monopoly core. In this way they produce harms through delayed diffusion of socially valuable innovations, restricted access via licensing/technical gating/contractual terms, suppression of competing or complementary alternatives, and lock-in dependencies that reallocate long-run power and risk onto downstream actors (including the public sector and communities) (Showalter and Edelson 2024). Rikap (2024) has theorized intellectual monopoly to explain the co-habitation of large incumbent firms with high entry and exit rates, emphasizing how self-reinforcing control over intangible assets can shape diffusion and who benefits from innovation, reinforcing the relevance of diffusion- and access-centred harm pathways (Rikap 2024).

In DNSH terms, insights from modern antitrust debates suggest that significant harm can arise not only through direct environmental or social impacts, but also through *structural innovation harms* linked to market concentration and gatekeeper power. Even where products appear “free” and immediate price effects are absent, dominant digital platforms can generate harms by delaying the diffusion of publicly valuable innovations, restricting access

through licensing, technical gating or contractual terms, suppressing alternatives by foreclosing competitors and complements, and creating lock-in dependencies that shift long-run power and risk onto public institutions and affected communities. The effects of these intellectual monopolies is not dissimilar from the social production of ignorance associated with knowledge production systems at the intersection of academia, regulation and industry (Kleinman and Suryanarayanan 2013).

2.6 What counts as harm? The normative blind spots of DNSH

The DNSH principle, as currently operationalized, rests on a narrow and predominantly quantitative conception of what constitutes "significant harm." While this technocratic framing offers administrative clarity, it obscures a fundamental question: what kinds of harm count, and for whom? Answering this question requires moving beyond checklists and thresholds toward a deeper engagement with the normative foundations of the principle itself.

Sustainability science and environmental policy have long recognized that environmental damage cannot be reduced to measurable losses of ecosystem function or material assets. Discussions about environmental damage frequently **overlook the interrelationships between land and embedded cultural meanings, such as social ties, histories, and memories**. Anthropological critiques emphasize that environmental harm may not only entail degradation of ecosystems or property loss, but also the **erasure of cultural knowledge** deeply tied to specific environments (Kirsch 2001). As demonstrated for example in legal analyses of the Marshall Islands case following U.S. nuclear testing, Indigenous claims of harm—centred on cultural loss and situated experiences—struggle to gain traction within **property-based legal and economic frameworks** that narrowly define damage in terms of land or material assets (Kirsch 2001).

Moreover, this proportional understanding of harm raises at least two major concerns. First, the distribution of environmental costs and benefits is rarely symmetrical: those who gain from environmentally beneficial policies are often not those who bear the harms. The case of **nuclear energy** illustrates this tension vividly, as the advantages of low-carbon power accrue mainly to present generations and wealthier regions, while the **long-term burdens of radioactive waste** fall on future generations and on communities in other countries. Second, in cases of **irreversible harms**—such as severe ecological degradation, the destruction of cultural heritage, or violations of fundamental human rights—**proportional compensation becomes morally and practically impossible**. Even when those harmed and those who benefit are the same individuals or communities, reparations cannot fully restore what was lost. Some forms of symbolic or non-economic compensation may mitigate such losses, but they remain **qualitatively inadequate** relative to the gravity of the harm.

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Social Labs highlight

In the Social Labs participants expressed discomfort with balancing unquantifiable or potentially irreversible harms against projected benefits, particularly where impacts would be borne by future generations, marginalized communities, or non-human entities. DNSH assessments often revealed the complex nature of harm: questions about significance, acceptability, and responsibility could not be settled by technical expertise alone, but required deliberation, interpretation, and normative judgement.

3. Expanding the reflection on harm - Western environmental humanities and DNSH

The previous section demonstrated that the DNSH principle, as currently operationalized, cannot adequately capture the full range of harms that environmentally consequential decisions may cause. Questions of irreversibility, cultural loss, and distributive injustice exceed the boundaries of technical assessment and demand a different kind of engagement — one that is explicitly normative rather than merely procedural. However, before such an engagement is possible, a prior question must be answered: **what ethical assumptions are already embedded, often silently, in the way DNSH defines harm in the first place?**

For this reason, the following chapter draws on Western environmental humanities and ethics to illuminate the moral architecture underlying DNSH decision-making. It integrates findings from the mapping of environmental and climate ethics conducted in WPI (D 1.1), situating the regulatory framework within broader intellectual traditions that have long grappled with questions of harm, moral considerability, and the limits of anthropocentric frameworks. The aim is not to replace technical assessment with philosophical reflection, but to show that the two are inseparable — and that a more defensible application of DNSH requires acknowledging the normative choices it already, if implicitly, makes.

3.1 Moral status and the intrinsic, instrumental and relational value of nature

The DNSH principle and related sustainability frameworks rely on assessments of what constitutes “harm,” to whom, and with what weight. Yet these assessments are never value-neutral: they implicitly presuppose answers to questions like **whose interests matter**, whether nature is valued only for human benefit or also **in its own right**, and how we treat harms that

are indirect, cumulative, or relational. This is why a brief environmental humanities and ethics perspective is needed here: it helps uncover the normative foundations that quietly structure risk assessment, policy design, and the interpretation of “significant harm.”

Expanding the conception of harm and significant harm raises philosophical questions concerning the moral interests that are capable of being harmed, and the seriousness of such harms.

A central debate in environmental ethics concerns the kind of value that nature and nonhuman entities possess: do they have **intrinsic value**—that is, value in and of themselves, independent of human use—or do they merely have **instrumental value**, being valuable only as means to human ends? This question is tightly connected to the concept of **moral status**, which refers to the inclusion of a being or entity within the “moral community”: those who are considered morally significant and therefore capable of being wronged or harmed. If a being has moral status, it must be morally considered in our actions and decisions.

Different traditions operationalize moral status through distinct criteria, often expressed as “isms” that, in practice, shape what counts as harm under DNSH, as it emerged in the mapping of environmental and climate ethics in WPI systematized the following categories according to the number of occurrences in the reviewed literature (see DI. 1.1).

Anthropocentrism restricts intrinsic value to humans; **sentientism** extends it to sentient animals; **biocentrism** to all living beings; **ecocentrism** to ecological collectives such as species and ecosystems; while **deep ecology** and related holistic views stress the value of the natural world as an interconnected whole. Other approaches shift attention from *who counts* to *how we ought to live with nature*: **ecofeminism** highlights how power, culture, and gendered inequalities structure human–environment relations, and **environmental virtue ethics** emphasizes the character traits and practices that sustain respectful ecological coexistence.

Alongside these worldviews, three categories of environmental value—**intrinsic, instrumental, and relational**—help clarify what is at stake when harms are assessed. Intrinsic and instrumental value are often presented as opposites, but many environmental ethics debates turn on how they interact and which takes priority in decision-making (e.g., O’Neill 1992; Taylor 1988; Norton 1994). Intrinsic value refers to things that are appreciated or pursued for their own sake—such as health, happiness, knowledge, or beauty—because they are considered inherently good or meaningful. In environmental ethics, debates about the intrinsic value, or alternative formulations such as inherent value or final value, have long been a central focus of debate (O’Neill 1992). Debates about which entities in ‘nature’ possessed intrinsic value connect directly with environmental worldviews, such as when it is claimed that all sentient beings or all ‘goal-directed’ living things possess intrinsic value (Taylor 1988).

Instrumental value, on the other hand, applies to things that are valued not for themselves, but because they serve as means to achieve something else that is intrinsically valuable. There are also positions in environmental ethics, such as environmental pragmatism (e.g. Norton 1994), which reject intrinsic values and are grounded solely upon instrumental values.

Building upon the ‘relational turn’ in contemporary sustainability (West et al. 2020), a third value category has been proposed alongside intrinsic and instrumental value, namely

“relational value” (K. M. A. Chan et al. 2016; K. M. Chan et al. 2018; Díaz et al. 2015). This emphasizes the significance of human-nature relationships and practices that shape cultural identities. In its assessment of environmental valuation, the International Panel of Experts on Sustainable Food Systems (IPBES) defines relational values as the importance of “desirable, meaningful, and often reciprocal human relationships – beyond means to an end – with nature and among people through nature” (Anderson et al. 2022: 63). Relational values are defined by the IPBES as generally “context-dependent, non-transferrable, non-tradable, and therefore largely non-substitutable” and concerning “relationships with nature that constitute people’s individual and collective identity” (Anderson et al. 2022: 63).

In contemporary conservation and wider environmental science literatures, relational values have been argued to be a third category of value alongside intrinsic and instrumental value (Chan et al. 2016). Crucially, relational value can be interpreted in non-centric terms: its ethical weight does not rest solely on benefits to humans, but on the commitments that arise within relationships that include non-human beings and places. Relational values and ecocentric worldviews are also part of emerging legal concepts such as the rights of nature (Villavicencio Calzadilla and Kotzé 2018; Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform On Biodiversity And Ecosystem Services et al. 2022). Ghijssels shows that relational values strengthen conservation not simply by adding another “reason” to protect nature, but by changing what motivates action and how governance is designed (Ghijssels 2023). In the Te Urewera case—declared a legal entity in 2014—relational values are encoded in law in ways that foreground *connection, meaning, and responsibility* (e.g., maintaining Tuhoe–Te Urewera relationships alongside safeguarding ecological integrity), which differs from intrinsic-value arguments that typically justify protection through nature’s worth “in itself” and often align with preservationist framings. In practice, this relational framing helps explain why committed actors are moved by experiences such as wonder, curiosity, learning, and living a worthwhile life—motivations that are empirically “real” and often dominant among conservation practitioners (Kachler et al. 2024)—while also supporting more inclusive, deliberative conservation processes that bring social sciences and humanities into valuation and enable participatory negotiation among stakeholders. At the same time, “relational” and “inclusive” valuation can still remain anthropocentrically oriented (focused on human wellbeing) unless relational values are explicitly linked to reciprocity, care, and respect that also provide **prescriptive guidance** for how humans ought to relate to nature (Ghijssels 2023).

This relational framing aligns with **new materialist** accounts of agency and **multispecies justice** (see paragraph 3.2), which treat beings as constituted through relations and material exchanges rather than as isolated units. On this view, “significant harm” is not only damage to discrete entities (a species, a habitat, an individual animal), but also the **disruption of the relational conditions of multispecies flourishing**—the webs of interdependence, practices, and ecological processes through which life is sustained.

However, within environmental ethics there is no agreement about whether relational values really are a new or distinct category of environmental value (Baard 2025; Luque-Lora 2023; Neuteleers 2020; Anderson et al. 2022; Stålhammar and Thorén 2019; Deplazes-Zemp 2024; Chapman and Deplazes-Zemp 2021). Nonetheless, even critics acknowledge that human-

nature relationships are ethically significant, and that harms to them can constitute serious moral wrongs (James 2019).

3.2 Different types of justice

In the climate justice debate, **harm avoidance justice** is an influential kind of justice, along with **distributive justice** (Caney 2014). The harm avoidance perspective focuses on the plight of the potential victims of climate change and climate policies and technologies, with the task of avoiding (serious) harm to them, typically in terms of threats to fundamental entitlements such as those based on human rights. In contrast, the distributive justice approach is concerned with ensuring fairness among the individual and collective actors responsible for shouldering the climatic burdens of mitigation, adaptation, and loss and damage. While the first approach is based on a version of the harm principle revised to track harm at the global and the intergenerational levels, the second approach is based on principles of distributive climate justice, such as the polluter-pays principle, the ability to pay principle, and the beneficiary-pays principle (Caney 2014).

This justice lens is included because “harm” is not only a descriptive notion but **also a normative one**: it depends on whose interests count, what thresholds matter, and how competing claims are balanced. Harm-avoidance justice helps define “significant harm” in terms of threats to fundamental entitlements (often rights-based), while distributive justice clarifies how the burdens of avoiding harm should be fairly allocated. This provides an ethical basis for strategy choices and for identifying who bears responsibility for enabling harm reduction.

To address the global challenge of climate change, beyond primary mitigation and adaptation obligations, Caney (2014) affirms that certain agents have *second-order responsibilities in the context of climate change*, building on the idea that those who can make a significant difference have a duty to act. This view is grounded in what the author terms the “Power/Responsibility Principle”, which states that those who possess the power to induce, compel, or enable others to act in climate-friendly ways have a responsibility to do so. Carley thinks that agents who are capable of shaping the behaviours and choices of others have a duty to act, especially in a climate emergency. The case for second-order responsibilities in climate action rests on four key assumptions. First, the **emergency condition**: climate change poses urgent and severe threats—such as extreme weather, health crises, and resource insecurity—with critical carbon thresholds potentially breached by 2040. Second, the **effectiveness condition**: actors like policymakers and communicators have the capacity to influence others and support compliance with emissions reductions. Third, they are **uniquely positioned**—holding knowledge or authority that makes their role in climate response indispensable. Finally, there is typically no **overriding duty** that outweighs the obligation to act; given the crisis, engaging in second-order efforts is a moral priority.

In contemporary debates on environmental and more-than-human ethics, a family of **non-anthropocentric theories of justice** has emerged to challenge the idea that *only humans* can be subjects (or beneficiaries) of justice. This move does not simply “add nature” to an otherwise

unchanged theory; it often **reworks what justice is about** (its subjects, objects, sites, and metrics). Different strands can be distinguished: **ecological justice**, which will be dealt with more in depth in 4.1, **animal justice** (Cochrane 2012, 2009; Garner 2013), **interspecific justice** (VanDeVeer 1979), and more recently **multispecies justice** (Celermajer et al. 2021).

- **Ecological justice** typically foregrounds ecosystems, ecological integrity, and the conditions of collective flourishing. Its unit of concern can be populations, habitats, ecological functions, or “ecological space,” and its core question becomes how to organize institutions so that humans do not wrongfully appropriate or degrade the biophysical preconditions of life (Wienhues 2025; Schlosberg 2013).
- **Animal justice** focuses more directly on **sentient animals**, often emphasizing welfare, rights, or comparable moral standing grounded in sentience and vulnerability. Here justice is frequently framed as protection against exploitation, suffering, confinement, and killing, with debates about what institutions (law, markets, food systems) owe to animals (Garner 2013; Cochrane 2009, 2012).
- **Interspecific justice** highlights **justice across species lines**: not only what humans owe to nonhumans, but how political communities should address conflicts among species interests and the governance of shared worlds (VanDeVeer 1979).
- **Multispecies justice** starts from the claim that the liberal “subject of justice” (the autonomous human individual) is a fiction that obscures ecological reality: humans are constituted through interdependence and embedded in webs of living and material relations. From this perspective, injustice is not only harm to humans distributed unequally; it is also the disruption, domination, erasure, and undermining of multispecies lifeways and ecological integrity (Celermajer et al. 2021; Fitz-Henry 2022).

3.3 Loss and damage- going beyond quantification

When it comes to topics that are related to DNSH in climate justice, the discussion on loss and damage applied to environment is also relevant. One of the key decisions made at the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) COP-18 meeting in Doha in 2012 was the establishment of a work programme on loss and damage, which included the development of a technical paper to enhance understanding of non-economic losses. Unlike economic losses, which involve the loss of goods and services traded in markets, **non-economic losses** refer to **those that fall outside of market systems—such as loss of life, cultural heritage, identity, biodiversity, and territory**. The technical paper released in 2013 adopted this market-based distinction, but the broader ethical and philosophical dimensions of non-economic loss remained underdeveloped. The Warsaw International Mechanism (WIM) was the institutional body tasked with addressing these issues, since its task was also to find ways to assess and, where possible, redress losses that had already occurred. This dual focus—on both prospective risk reduction and retrospective compensation—has raised complex ethical questions, especially when the losses in question defy easy quantification or commodification, which have been addressed in the literature (Shockley and Hourdequin 2017; Preston 2017). The UN technical paper has claimed that non-economic losses occur in three different areas: the private individual, society and the environment.

As with the case of emerging non-economic losses from climate change, anticipating and quantifying significant losses in advance often proves challenging. **Harms associated with new technologies frequently unfold in non-linear, incremental, and unexpected ways.** While some of the uncertainties involved may be reduced over time through further research and experience, others are deeply embedded in the complexity of social and ecological systems and thus resist straightforward resolution. These limitations reflect the inherent constraints of scientific knowledge when applied to complex, value-laden contexts (Stirling 2010). Much like climate change, where the most visible risks often concern human health and well-being, **technological harms frequently include social and cultural dimensions that are not easily reducible to conventional welfare metrics.** Impacts on traditional knowledge, community cohesion, or a sense of place may not manifest as direct threats to health, but they nevertheless represent serious forms of harm. Similarly, harms to the non-human environment are both real and morally relevant yet often elude identification and measurement. The growing recognition of socio-economic impacts and the cultural services provided by ecosystems signals a growing awareness of the inadequacy of assessments that focus solely on health and ecological risks. **A shift in ethical perspective is necessary**—one that moves beyond the calculation of risk to engage with the ways technologies shape and are shaped by human relationships, vulnerabilities, and worldviews. Preston and others think that the foundations of such an approach can already be seen in feminist care ethics, which emphasises responsiveness, interdependence, the moral importance of relationships as central to ethical reflection (relational ontology) and it is more sensitive to issues of power and vulnerability (Preston 2017; Preston and Wickson 2016).

McShane has introduced an important **distinction between harm and value in the consideration of loss and damage** (McShane 2017). One interpretation **ties loss to harm**, defining it as any impact that reduces the well-being of individuals. This is the more common understanding used in climate negotiations, where losses are often quantified in terms of economic costs or human welfare metrics. The other interpretation considers **loss as the destruction of something valuable**, regardless of whether it results in harm to humans. This perspective is more expansive, recognizing that entities like ecosystems, species, cultural practices, and sacred sites can be lost in ways that are deeply significant, even if they do not reduce human welfare in easily measurable ways. The harm-based framework, while intuitive and compatible with existing liability and compensation structures, is insufficient on its own. It tends to exclude nonhuman and non-economic values and reinforces a narrow anthropocentric and instrumental view of nature. McShane shares the criticism to the documents, such as those produced by the UNFCCC, which tend to reduce losses to market terms or frame non-economic values only through their utility to humans, such as biodiversity's value in terms of ecosystem services. Therefore, **focusing only on harms** (to people) **risks ignoring profound moral losses** such as extinction, loss of ecosystems, or erosion of Indigenous knowledge—values that **may not be easily quantifiable** or economically compensated. This approach risks overlooking what many people, especially in non-Western or Indigenous contexts, see as intrinsically valuable: **the land itself, cultural continuity, and the well-being of nonhuman beings.**

DNSH procedures often rely on measurable, mostly harm-based environmental indicators, but this leaves out significant losses that fall outside those frameworks. If the principle of DNSH is to fulfil its ethical and ecological mandate, it must reckon with the fact that **significant harm can occur even in the absence of measurable human suffering**. For example, the extinction of a species or the desecration of a sacred landscape may not directly harm any individual in a narrow sense but still constitutes a grave moral and ecological loss.

Furthermore, McShane (2017)'s emphasis on **inclusive, value-sensitive frameworks challenges** the reliance on purely economic or instrumental valuations that dominate current DNSH assessments. In doing so, she questions the sufficiency of using market proxies or ecosystem services to account for biodiversity, cultural heritage, or community cohesion. These insights suggest that **DNSH, in its current technical form, may be exclusionary and risk legitimizing policies that cause irreversible losses merely because those losses are not framed as direct harm to human welfare**.

Finally, McShane (2017) underscores the **importance of cultural and ethical pluralism in any robust harm assessment**. McShane calls for participatory methods that **recognize local perspectives, intrinsic values, and a wider conception of well-being**. This directly resonates with the ethical aspirations of DNSH, which aims to ensure environmental integrity and justice across generations and regions.

3.4 Harm in the debate on global and intergenerational justice

In the context of the DNSH principle, the ethical distinction between refraining from harm and actively contributing to good must be examined more critically. This links directly to longstanding debates in moral philosophy around **negative and positive duties** as well as to the debate on the **duties toward future generations**.

Traditionally, **negative duties**—to refrain from causing harm—are seen as more binding and universally accepted, forming the backbone of the DNSH principle. This aligns with the **harm principle** in liberal thought, where individual freedoms are bounded by the imperative not to harm others (as emphasized by John Stuart Mill). However, Lichtenberg challenged this dichotomy, arguing that in our globalized, interconnected world, **many of the harms we contribute to are diffuse, indirect, and systemic** (Lichtenberg 2010). These “new harms” arise not from violent acts but from everyday choices—consumption, energy use, or passive complicity in exploitative supply chains.

This challenges the notion that negative duties are easy to satisfy. In fact, **avoiding harm today may be just as demanding as aiding others**, and perhaps even more complex. The DNSH principle, if interpreted narrowly as “not doing harm,” could therefore miss the deeper moral challenge: that **harm can result from omissions, ignorance, and inaction** just as much as from active wrongdoing. The absolute moral threshold is defined in terms of equal minimal rights, so this is a rather minimalistic conception of well-being: we have to protect future people's well-being based on the rights they will have once they will be born. Their future human rights constrain our actions today.

From a **consequentialist view**, the distinction between harming and allowing harm collapses—the outcome is what matters. But Lichtenberg shows that even from a **deontological or virtue ethics perspective**, we must recognize the **moral weight of complicity, participation, and failure to act** in the face of harm (Lichtenberg 2010). These reflections invite us to understand that the DNSH principle cannot be seen merely as a passive, minimalist requirement, but rather as a call to **scrutinize the systemic consequences of our behaviour** and the systems we uphold. Ultimately, if the DNSH principle is to uphold genuine moral accountability, it must reflect the **blurred boundaries between doing harm, allowing harm, and failing to prevent it**—especially in the context of global sustainability and justice.

In their work on intergenerational justice Meyer and Roser have developed a **threshold conception of harm** in response to the non-identity problem in relation to the questions of future generations (Meyer and Roser 2009). This problem arises when decisions today (e.g. environmental or reproductive choices) shape who will exist in the future, making it difficult to claim someone was "harmed" if the alternative was nonexistence. Meyer and Roser argue that future people are harmed if our actions cause them to live **below a specified threshold of well-being**, regardless of whether they could have existed under better conditions. This avoids absurd conclusions about obligations to bring only the "best possible" people into existence. They then defend a **sufficientarian** rather than an egalitarian model for intergenerational justice. The authors argue that our moral and political obligations to future people—who are affected by today's actions but cannot yet interact or consent—are best guided by ensuring all future persons can attain a **threshold of sufficient well-being**, rather than focusing on equality between generations or maximizing total well-being (Meyer and Roser 2009). Intergenerational context differs then from typical justice relationships: future people cannot participate in current democratic processes, impose accountability, or interact as equals. These features, combined with epistemic uncertainty about future life conditions, make egalitarian or prioritarian models less practical or morally coherent in this domain.

Climate change is a central concern, as its irreversible effects impose harm across generations. Though action is hindered by economic concerns and political short-termism, youth movements and legal cases have started to assert a right to a safe environment. Skillington adopts a sociological lens rather than a philosophical one, contending that the priorities of contemporary capitalism have overshadowed all other considerations, particularly those related to environmental protection (Skillington 2018). She argues that the dominant focus on present-day interests results in an unjust distribution of responsibility and resources, to the detriment of future generations. This reflects a fundamental weakness in the current liberal-democratic political system (Skillington 2018).

The idea of harm as threshold and the sufficientarian approach developed by Meyer and Roser significantly deepens the normative foundation of the DNSH principle. DNSH, as used in EU policy and environmental governance, is often interpreted through a narrow procedural lens—ensuring that no action leads to clear, identifiable harm. But their work expands this understanding by grounding harm in **the moral duty to prevent future persons from falling below a defined threshold of well-being**, even when those persons cannot yet be identified.

This complements the idea of **negative duties** (to avoid causing harm) while introducing **positive obligations**—such as ensuring institutional structures and decisions today do not create futures in which people’s basic needs cannot be met. It supports a **proactive, justice-based reading of DNSH**, in which the absence of direct harm is not enough. We must ensure our policies, technologies, and environmental choices are sufficient to uphold a morally acceptable quality of life for future generations, recognizing that harm includes structural or systemic neglect.

Furthermore, by integrating this threshold view with Caney’s harm-avoidance justice (Caney 2014) and Lichtenberg’s discussion of systemic complicity (Lichtenberg 2010), the DNSH principle can be reframed as both a negative duty **not to cause foreseeable harm**, and a **positive duty to prevent foreseeable future deprivation**—especially when inaction, indifference, or unsustainable practices risk crossing that ethical threshold.

3.5 Importance of cultural and contextual considerations

This underscores a critical gap: assessments of harm under the DNSH principle must consider **cultural property rights and epistemological diversity**. The loss of culture is not merely symbolic; it can involve the disappearance of entire knowledge systems embedded in specific ecologies, practices, and landscapes (Kirsch 2001). Therefore, for DNSH to be ethically robust and socially meaningful, it must move beyond expert-led, risk-based calculations to include **holistic, qualitative evaluations** that reflect the lived realities, cultural narratives, and historical responsibilities of affected communities. Only by doing so can collective action against environmental harm be genuinely inclusive, just, and effective.

Insights from **medical anthropology** offer valuable critique and complementarity. The anthropology of risk highlights how laypeople often perceive and evaluate risks differently from experts, bringing attention to **cultural interpretations of vulnerability, agency, and moral responsibility**. Risk is not simply a calculable probability of harm, but also a socially constructed and politically contested phenomenon (Petryna 2013).

Expanding upon these concerns, insights from **moral philosophy, feminist bioethics, and science and technology studies (STS)** provide a rich conceptual basis for addressing the limitations of universalist, expert-driven assessments of environmental harm. Central to this critique is the notion of **situatedness**—the idea that moral knowledge is context-dependent and emerges from particular social, cultural, and historical positions (Haraway 1988b). This stands in contrast to abstract, decontextualized norms. The ideographic approach, as discussed by (Jonsen 2005), encapsulates this view by emphasizing that the task of ethics—especially bioethics—is not to impose theory onto practice, but to extract moral understanding from within **lived social practices and relations of interdependence**. Normativity, in this framework, arises through *inscription in social meaning and cultural embeddedness*, making moral evaluation a matter of **interpreting action within its specific context** rather than measuring it against universal metrics.

This **relational and interpretive orientation** has long been a hallmark of **feminist ethics** and **care theory**, where ethical responsibility is seen as fundamentally shaped by interdependent

relationships and contextual vulnerabilities (Gilligan 2003; Noddings 1984). Martha Nussbaum's capabilities approach similarly highlights the importance of individual embeddedness in social and material contexts, focusing on what people are actually able to do and be, rather than applying abstract standards of well-being (Nussbaum 2000). These perspectives challenge the dominant bioethical paradigm of principlism, which often abstracts moral questions from lived experience and cultural variability (Sherwin 1992). Moreover, scholars in disability studies and STS have underscored how dominant framings of risk and harm—especially those used in public health or environmental regulation—can marginalize alternative knowledge systems and forms of life that do not conform to dominant technocratic norms (Haraway 1988).

Thus, when assessing harm—particularly under instruments like DNSH—it becomes imperative to move beyond **generalized, population-level indicators** and instead consider the **ethical-political dimensions** of harm as they manifest in specific communities and relationships. A relational, ideographic approach does not reject the need for evidence or criteria, but it insists that **what counts as harm, who is affected, and what is owed in response must be determined through engagement with the situated realities of those affected**. This interpretive dimension adds critical moral depth and democratic accountability to environmental and bioethical governance.

In the field of **medical anthropology**, there is a distinctive emphasis on understanding the values, cultural frameworks, and intricate social-environmental interactions that shape how communities perceive and respond to ecological challenges. This discipline offers a valuable lens through which to explore environmental issues not merely as technical or scientific problems, but as deeply embedded within lived experiences, belief systems, and socio-political dynamics.

One of the critical contributions anthropologists can make to environmental problem-solving lies in their application of what Morgan (1991) terms “*systematic doubt*.” This methodological stance encourages a critical interrogation of the assumptions that underpin public debates, policy initiatives, and proposed solutions. Anthropologists recognize that such discourses often rely on taken-for-granted logics that may obscure the complexities of local ecologies and the realities of people's everyday lives. By revealing these hidden assumptions, anthropologists help reframe environmental problems in ways that are more context-sensitive and socially informed.

Furthermore, Milton advocates for engaging with environmental discourse through the lens of “*sensible cultural relativism*” (Milton 1997). This approach challenges the universality of concepts like “biodiversity,” which—although presented as globally beneficial—can function as ideological tools that justify state or corporate control over local resources, as critiqued by Shiva (Shiva 1993). In contrast to dominant Western narratives, local communities often develop their environmental knowledge through direct, embodied engagement with their surroundings. As Milton (1997, p.493) puts it, “local communities derive their knowledge of the environment by experiencing it from within.” This inside-out understanding invites a re-evaluation of external interventions and emphasizes the need to ground environmental action in the lived epistemologies of those most affected.

3.6 Learning from the One Health approach

The One Health (OH) concept recognises the close interconnection between human, animal, and environmental health. It is based on the understanding that the health of people is intrinsically linked to the health of animals and the ecosystems they inhabit. It promotes a collaborative, transdisciplinary approach to prevent and address health threats that cross species and environmental boundaries.

Originating from veterinary and ecological sciences, it has evolved into a global framework for tackling challenges like pandemics, antimicrobial resistance, and climate-related health risks. Throughout its history, the OH principle has achieved significant milestones, from the recognition in the mid-20th century by veterinary surgeon Calvin Schwabe of striking parallels between human and animal health to the formulation in 2004 of the [Manhattan Principles of Conservation](#), which formally advocated for a unified approach to preventing epidemic diseases and preserving ecosystem integrity. Since 2002, the [Quadripartite Alliance](#)—comprising the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH), World Health Organization (WHO), and United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP—with support from the [One Health High-Level Expert Advisory Panel \(OHHLEP\)](#)) has made significant strides in formally recognizing OH as a crucial framework for addressing health emergencies with cross-border implications.

The European Commission, too, in recent years, has progressively recognised the potential of the OH approach, especially after the experience of the COVID-19 pandemic. The OH approach has been increasingly integrated into R&I frameworks in the EU, yet critical knowledge and implementation gaps persist, limiting the ability of EU institutions to provide comprehensive scientific advice on issues like public health, environmental protection, and food safety. To address these challenges, the 2022 [ONE Conference](#), led by the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) and other EU agencies proposed a Cross-Agency One Health Task Force, aimed at improving strategic coordination, aligning research agendas, fostering stakeholder engagement, and facilitating joint initiatives among the five key EU agencies under the European Parliament's Committee on the Environment, Public Health and Food Safety (ENVI). The task force, guided by the principles of coordination, collaboration, communication, and capacity building, has established a joint framework and a 2024–2026 action plan to systematically embed OH principles into EU policymaking (Bronzwaer et al. 2022). In 2023, the EU agencies outlined four priorities in a Joint Statement by European Union Agencies strengthening the scientific evidence base, integrating OH into risk assessment, enhancing surveillance systems, and expanding education and training across sectors. Building on this foundation, the European Commission's Scientific Advisory Mechanism published a major 2024 opinion endorsing the OHHLEP definition of OH and recommending six policy areas—ranging from governance and coherence to education, research, and surveillance—to support a holistic, transdisciplinary and ethically grounded approach to EU health and sustainability challenges (European Commission's Group of Chief Scientific Advisors 2024). The European Commission has now firmly embraced the OH approach as a cornerstone of future health governance, demonstrated by President Ursula von der Leyen's mission letter mandating the expansion of the OH agenda (European Commission 2024) and the creation of a dedicated

Directorate for OH within DG SANTE, (European Commission and Directorate-General for Health and Food Safety 2025).

The OH approach provides a valuable conceptual framework for reflecting on and enriching the application of the DNSH principle. The integrated and holistic nature of the OH approach arises from the recognition that health outcomes—whether human, animal, or environmental—are deeply shaped by social determinants. This perspective broadens the analytical lens beyond biomedical or ecological parameters to include the cultural, economic, and societal conditions that influence exposure, vulnerability, and resilience. **One Health thus demands long-term strategies for systemic resilience** that address the interlinked effects of air, soil, water, and climate on the health of all living organisms. Crucially, it is grounded in governance principles that emphasize stewardship, sustainability, and ethical responsibility, underscoring the imperative for human actions to respect ecological integrity while safeguarding the well-being of both present and future generations.

This expansive vision offers critical lessons for the DNSH principle, which addresses six environmental objectives through technical metrics, but insufficiently accounts for the socio-cultural contexts that shape sustainability policy implementation and outcomes. Equally important is the recognition of the **interdependence of these ecological and climatic systems**—how climate, water, biodiversity, and pollution are mutually reinforcing rather than isolated domains—underscoring the need for integrated approaches rather than compartmentalized assessments.

One Health systemic methodology—which considers the cascading effects of human activities across ecological, social, and health domains—offers critical insights for the implementation of DNSH, especially in evaluating actions that may have indirect or long-term environmental repercussions (European Commission’s Group of Chief Scientific Advisors 2024). Beyond its emphasis on multidimensional and interdisciplinary thinking, OH highlights the essential **role of social and cultural factors in shaping environmental outcomes**, reminding us that values, practices, and governance structures are integral to both the causes of and responses to ecological harm. For instance, OH highlights the often-overlooked environmental consequences of human activity—such as, for example, the impact of illicit drug residues on soil and water ecosystems, or the links between pollution, diet, and mental health—demonstrating how environmental harm cannot be disaggregated from social behaviour or public health. In **recognizing the importance of socioeconomic and cultural factors** in shaping health outcomes, the OH framework advocates for policies that go beyond the medical context **to include environmental and social determinants of health**. This comprehensive perspective highlights the need for long-term resilience strategies that address the impacts of air, soil, water, and climate on the health of all living organisms. Furthermore, the OH approach is underpinned by governance principles that promote stewardship, sustainability, and ethical responsibility, reinforcing the need for human actions that respect the integrity of ecosystems and prioritize the well-being of both current and future generations (European Commission’s Group of Chief Scientific Advisors 2024).

The OH framework also calls attention to the **justice dimensions embedded in environmental governance**. In this way, OH foregrounds the importance of accessibility,

distributional fairness, and cultural context—insights that are critical for a more equitable implementation of DNSH. Its systemic approach also necessitates the evaluation of indirect, long-term, and cross-sectoral impacts, directly echoing DNSH's demand for multi-dimensional and anticipatory impact screening. By engaging with **feedback loops, cumulative risks, and trade-offs among sectors**—such as those between agriculture, water quality, and biodiversity—policies informed by OH support more nuanced and adaptive responses to complex environmental challenges.

Moreover, OH's ethical vision, rooted in interspecies stewardship and intergenerational fairness, offers a powerful moral orientation for DNSH. It recognizes the **reciprocal responsibilities between human and non-human life and frames health and environmental protection not merely as matters of risk mitigation, but as duties toward future generations and the broader web of life**. This socially embedded and justice-oriented paradigm can help anchor DNSH in a broader ethics of care and responsibility—one that is capable of responding to the ecological and moral complexity of the climate and biodiversity crises.

4. Ecology, transcultural and Eastern perspectives

The preceding analysis of Western environmental ethics has shown that concepts such as "nature," "value," "harm," and "do no harm" are far from self-evident. When placed under scrutiny, each reveals a layered history of philosophical assumptions, cultural contingencies, and contested meanings — and when translated into regulatory practice, these complexities do not disappear but instead resurface as interpretive ambiguities, assessment gaps, and normative blind spots. Yet Western environmental humanities represent only one of many frameworks through which these questions have been posed and answered. Building a robust normative foundation for DNSH therefore requires going beyond the familiar conceptual vocabulary of Western regulatory traditions and embracing insights from other parts of the world. This is not only a matter of intellectual breadth: as European societies become increasingly multicultural, sustainability frameworks that claim universal applicability must be able to speak to the diverse moral horizons, relational understandings of nature, and lived experiences of harm that different communities bring with them.

This section presents condensed findings from a broader and more expansive investigation conducted as part of this research project, covering three underexplored dimensions: ecological understandings of harm, transcultural frameworks and Indigenous knowledge traditions, and Eastern philosophical thought. Each of these bodies of knowledge offers resources that the current DNSH framework lacks — whether in the form of relational conceptions of nature, non-anthropocentric moral frameworks, long-term and intergenerational thinking, or fundamentally different understandings of what it means for a community, an ecosystem, or a living being to be harmed. The full original contributions are included in the Appendix to this deliverable.

4.1 Ecological harm and DNSH

Engaging with scientific and legal scholarship on ecological harm helps to clarify what it means, in practice, to “do no significant harm.” The analysis provided by Florent Noulèkoun and Asia Khamzina from Korea University—summarised here and presented in full in the Appendix—reveals why DNSH cannot be assessed through narrow, project-by-project checklists alone: environmental impacts often arise through cumulative pressures, cross-sector interactions, and delayed or spatially displaced effects. In this sense, ecological harm provides a useful conceptual bridge between the formal requirements of DNSH and the reality that ecosystems respond systemically to multiple, interacting drivers of change.

Ecological harm refers to **any adverse effect on the structure, function, or integrity of ecosystems induced by natural or anthropogenic** Ecological harm can be categorised in terms of its **source, scale of impact, and legal status**. With regard to the source, White (2021) distinguishes between harm caused by “taking from nature” (extraction-based), “adding to nature” (pollution-based), and “altering nature” (alteration-based). This **multidimensional understanding** highlights that harm is not limited to discrete events but **includes long-term**

processes—such as biodiversity loss, soil degradation, and climate disruption—that undermine ecosystem integrity and resilience.

Scientific and legal analyses show that traditional anthropocentric and causality-driven frameworks struggle to address such complexities. **Because these legal regimes focus on traceable, event-based damage and permissible thresholds of impact, they tend to overlook systemic, multi-actor, and transboundary harms.** As a result, many ecologically damaging practices remain legally permissible even when they contribute to long-term degradation of ecological systems. These limitations stem not merely from regulatory gaps but from a deeper conceptual bias that treats nature as an external resource rather than as a relational, interdependent system.

To address these shortcomings, **ecocentric approaches are gaining prominence.** Rights-of-nature frameworks—now recognised in several jurisdictions—treat ecosystems and species as right-bearing entities rather than as objects of human use. A broad analysis is offered in the paragraph 4.3. Complementary justice perspectives broaden the ethical and legal consideration of harm. Building on- and yet moving beyond – environmental justice, debates on ecological harm increasingly foreground **ecological justice**, a perspective that relocates moral concern from primarily human interests to the wellbeing of ecosystems and non-human entities. This framing is particularly relevant for addressing harms such as biodiversity loss or habitat destruction, which may not generate immediate or easily traceable human impacts but can undermine ecosystem integrity over time, with far-reaching consequences for ecological resilience and future generations. It also broadens the scope of responsibility by drawing attention to harms that occur upstream and downstream along supply chains, thereby expanding accountability beyond direct, localized damage. In doing so, ecological justice challenges anthropocentric tendencies in legal and ethical systems and supports governance approaches that protect ecosystems as wholes, including through the recognition of rights for nature within institutional frameworks. A related and more recent development is the concepts of **interspecies** and **multispecies justice**, which calls for explicit moral and legal consideration of non-human animals and plant species (cf. chapter 3.2).

Taken together, ecological and species justice broaden normative debates on responsibility and harm: they shift attention from distributive fairness among humans alone toward the legal and ethical protection of ecosystems, non-human beings, and species within governance and decision-making.

Against this backdrop, the DNSH principle appears both promising and limited. Designed as a safeguard against significant environmental harm, **DNSH offers a regulatory foothold for integrating ecological considerations into policy, finance, and research decisions. Yet its operationalisation remains hindered by ambiguous definitions, inconsistent metrics, and an emphasis on human-centred risk. DNSH is particularly ill-equipped to capture cumulative, transboundary, or irreversible ecological harms, or harms that affect non-human species without immediate human repercussions.** These tensions align with criticisms raised throughout this report: that DNSH, in its current technocratic form, struggles with uncertainty, relational harms, and the deeper ethical dimensions of environmental degradation.

Strengthening DNSH requires moving beyond compliance-oriented checklists toward a more ecologically grounded and justice-informed framework. Clarifying what constitutes “harm,” developing context-sensitive indicators, and incorporating ecocentric and relational principles would make DNSH more responsive to the realities of ecological change in the Anthropocene.

4.2 Indigenous perspectives

Indigenous and local communities hold vital knowledge for living within complex ecosystems, and the erosion or disappearance of these lifeways constitutes a profound loss—with ecological, social, and cultural consequences. The transcultural analysis – reported in full in the Appendix – offers key insights into how deeply the concept of harm is normatively and culturally embedded, underscoring the need to make these assumptions explicit if the DNSH principle is to be applied in a meaningful and context-sensitive way.

From a transcultural perspective, “harm” is not a universal, value-neutral category: it is shaped by culturally specific worldviews, historical experiences, and socio-political power relations. For this reason, **epistemic justice** is central—because defining harm depends on whose knowledge counts and whose voices are recognized as authoritative. For Indigenous Peoples and other marginalized communities, harm may include not only environmental degradation but also the erosion of cultural identity, spiritual disconnection from ancestral territories, and the silencing of traditional knowledge systems. Without participatory processes that centre these perspectives, operationalizing DNSH risks reproducing the very dynamics of domination it seeks to prevent, rather than enabling a genuinely inclusive sustainability approach aligned with decolonial calls for a “pluriverse” of knowledges.

In the research performed, a corpus search was carried out in the e-HRAF database (<https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu>) using the query (*subjects: (“human effects on environment” OR “social problems”) AND text:(harm OR damag* OR injur* OR pollut* OR contamin* OR degrad* OR impair* OR loss)*). After manual cleaning, the resulting dataset comprised 3,152 paragraphs from 306 cultures spanning eight world regions and nine subsistence modes. The paragraphs were then analyzed through deductive semantic mapping using pretrained FastText embeddings (Common Crawl; 300 dimensions) and Concept Mover’s Distance (CMDist): cultural dimensions were operationalized as semantic axes defined by opposing anchor lists (e.g., harm–help; norm–deviation), directions were derived from averaged antonym offsets, and each document was scored via cosine projection and CMDist transport cost to estimate alignment with each pole. Complementary purity/impurity and gender axes were added as controls to separate material harm from ritual-order language and to check robustness across distinct cultural logics, with axis coherence assessed using PairDir and document-level scores summarized at the cultural level.

Indigenous worldviews frequently understand harm in territorial, spiritual, and intergenerational terms, grounded in relational ontologies where humans are part of a living web of reciprocal responsibilities.

Cultural approaches to managing harm are far from uniform. Depending on historical experience and social organisation, societies rely on punishment, prevention, improvisation, or

collaboration. The cultural profiles derived from the HRAF corpus reveal that orientations toward harm and repair—or toward norms and deviation—are not arbitrary but represent historically grounded strategies developed in response to particular environmental and social pressures. Recognising these culturally shaped repertoires allows us to better anticipate how different societies might respond to ecological or social crises and the need to design mechanisms of control and repair that are both effective and culturally meaningful. In this sense, the transcultural analysis also makes it possible to identify basic types of Indigenous harm management approaches and to anticipate how different cultural groups may react to emerging technological developments.

4.3 Nature as a subject of rights and the DNSH principle

Nature as a subject of rights provides a powerful lens for expanding the DNSH principle beyond a purely technical exercise of risk screening. While DNSH is usually operationalized through compliance-oriented procedures that aim to prevent “significant harm” (often via indicators, thresholds, and impact categories), rights-of-nature approaches begin from a deeper normative shift: **nature is not merely an object to be managed or protected for human benefit, but a rights-bearing subject with intrinsic value.**

To ground the analysis empirically, the research performed by the University of Barcelona, which constitutes the second part of the study on transcultural perspectives contained in the Appendix, draws on the *Eco Jurisprudence Monitor*, an interactive global repository of ecological jurisprudence initiatives and resources that track efforts to advance the Rights of Nature and related Earth-centred legal frameworks. The repository documents a broad movement—spanning constitutional reforms, legislation, court rulings, and local ordinances—which challenges anthropocentric assumptions and aims to strengthen protections for animals, plants, and ecosystems, while also benefiting human societies through healthier living systems. Using this evidence base, the section maps how “nature as a subject of rights” is being institutionalized across jurisdictions and identifies points of convergence with DNSH.

A central argument is that DNSH and rights-of-nature frameworks converge on environmental protection, but they do so from different foundations and with different emphases. DNSH emerges from sustainability governance and environmental regulation as a preventive and evaluative tool—often technocratic in design—intended to ensure that activities aligned with sustainability objectives do not generate unacceptable ecological impacts. **Rights-of-nature frameworks, by contrast, represent a more radical legal-philosophical reorientation: ecosystems are understood as possessing intrinsic value and, in many cases, a form of legal personhood, independent of their utility to humans.** This difference matters because it changes the “default setting” of assessment: instead of asking whether harms are sufficiently mitigated to proceed, rights-of-nature approaches more readily ask whether an activity violates the integrity, regeneration, or vital cycles of a living system—and what restoration and guardianship obligations follow.

Rights of Nature are being institutionalized through five main routes:

1. **Constitutional recognition:** Ecuador's 2008 constitution is the flagship case, granting Nature (Pacha Mama) enforceable rights (existence, regeneration, restoration) and linking ecological integrity to human well-being through *buen vivir*.
2. **Specific legislation:** Bolivia's 2010 "Mother Earth" law recognizes Nature as a living system with rights and emphasizes duties of state and society, acknowledging the fact that the majority of the population identify as "Indigenous". Similar legislative moves include Oaxaca (Mexico, 2021), New Zealand's legal personhood for specific ecosystems (e.g., Te Urewera, Te Awa Tupua), and Uganda's 2019 law recognizing Nature's rights and enabling legal representation.
3. **Judicial decisions:** Courts have recognized ecosystems as rights-bearing entities, notably Colombia's Atrato River ruling (2016). India has pursued similar recognition for rivers (with legal complications), and Bangladesh (2019) recognized all rivers as legal entities with a designated guardian body.
4. **Constitutional proposals:** Some countries have sought recognition through reform processes—Chile's 2022 draft constitution included strong rights-of-nature provisions but was rejected. Related initiatives include Finland's constitutional animal rights proposal and Ireland's recommendation to consider a referendum on rights of nature/healthy environment.
5. **Local ordinances:** Especially in the United States, municipalities and Indigenous nations have adopted rights-of-nature laws (e.g., Lake Erie Bill of Rights, later struck down), showing strong grassroots momentum but also high legal contestation.

Overall, the global picture is one of rapid diffusion alongside uneven implementation and frequent legal challenges.

DNSH tends to be grounded in European sustainability governance and technical environmental law; rights-of-nature is grounded in constitutionalism, jurisprudence, and Indigenous/ecocentric worldviews. DNSH aims to avoid significant harm; rights-of-nature aims to recognize inherent rights of ecosystems. DNSH is preventive and evaluative; rights-of-nature is relational and often restorative. **Yet these differences create a potential synergy: DNSH tools can strengthen impact assessment and due diligence within rights-of-nature regimes, while rights-of-nature can expand DNSH's normative foundation by bringing intrinsic value, guardianship, restoration, and relational justice into what otherwise risks becoming a compliance checklist.**

The ILO Convention 169, formally *the Indigenous and Tribal Peoples Convention, 1989*, is the **most important legally binding international instrument** protecting the rights of Indigenous and tribal peoples. It can constitute a bridge between environmental governance and Indigenous rights. While DNSH comes from environmental regulation and ILO 169 from international human rights law, **both emphasize prevention and participation**. DNSH requires early identification and mitigation of environmental risks; ILO 169 requires consultation and meaningful involvement of Indigenous and tribal peoples before projects affecting their lands and resources proceed, including safeguards around resource governance, benefit sharing where possible, and compensation for damage. **The key**

conceptual overlap is that environmental harm is inseparable from cultural harm for communities whose identities, spirituality, and livelihoods are rooted in living territories.

Together, DNSH and ILO 169 can form a stronger accountability architecture: due diligence, participatory justice, and access to redress.

However, there are also challenges associated with this convergence. First, there is a persistent ambiguity around what counts as “significant harm,” which enables flexible—and sometimes self-serving—interpretations that can clash with Indigenous conceptions of harm (spiritual, symbolic, intergenerational, relational). A second challenge is the uneven implementation of ILO 169: the political will may be weak, institutional capacity limited, and consultation reduced to procedural formality rather than genuine free, prior, and informed consent. Structural power imbalances represent a third challenge: communities often lack the legal, technical, and financial resources to engage on equal footing, especially in centralized and technocratic decision environments. Finally, enforcement and oversight are limited: violations may not trigger concrete consequences, and mechanisms for redress can be slow or inaccessible.

These tensions are illustrated through the case study of the Bassari in Senegal, selected precisely because Senegal lacks ILO 169 ratification and does not recognize nature as a subject of rights—creating a useful contrast case for thinking about DNSH in settings where formal safeguards are weak. The case examines how development interventions promoting market-oriented crops can generate unintended harms that standard “benefit-focused” narratives overlook. Among the Bassari, subsistence agriculture is embedded in matrilineal kinship, age-based social structure, customary land access, cooperative labour, and a deep corpus of traditional ecological knowledge. Market crops introduced through NGOs and state programs (maize, rice, peanuts, cotton), often reliant on water, chemical fertilizers, and pesticides, interact with changing rainfall patterns to reshape land tenure (from customary to individualized/registered holdings), weaken communal reciprocity, and destabilize traditional governance of land and sacred areas. Gender impacts are central: monetization and cotton cultivation tend to be controlled by men, diverting land and labour away from traditional food crops historically managed by women, undermining women’s control over food production and income and altering symbolic and practical gender balance. Inequalities can deepen as only households with capital, inputs, or equipment fully benefit, while others face higher costs and risks (including seed quality and health concerns). The main lesson is that “harm” is not limited to measurable environmental impacts; it includes transformations of social organization, gender relations, cultural reproduction, and resilience—precisely the kinds of harms emphasized in the transcultural paragraph and too often rendered invisible in conventional assessments.

4.4 Eastern perspectives and implications for the DNSH

Western paradigms provide much of the current conceptual scaffolding for DNSH, but they are often grounded in individualistic or utilitarian assumptions: harm is framed as discrete, measurable, and primarily relevant to human interests. This can obscure relational harms (to communities, cultures, or more-than-human worlds) and underestimate long-term ecological interdependencies. Many East Asian perspectives begin elsewhere: the boundaries between

self and community, and between humanity and nature, are more permeable. **Harm is therefore frequently understood as a rupture of relationships, balance, and collective well-being rather than merely a quantifiable negative impact.** This shift is directly relevant to DNSH because it challenges narrow interpretations of “significant harm” and supports broader, justice-oriented, and context-sensitive assessments. In the work conducted by Akiyama and his group at the University of Tokyo, which is reported in full in the appendix to this deliverable, the concept of “harm” (and its corollaries) was explored in East Asian philosophical, religious, and cultural traditions, with an emphasis on Confucianism, Buddhism, Daoism, and Shinto, following historical evolutions in China, Japan, Korea, and Taiwan.

Confucianism frames harm primarily as damage to social and moral harmony. Ethical life revolves around cultivating virtues such as *ren* (benevolence), *yi* (righteousness), and *li* (proper conduct). Harm is not just rights violation or physical injury; it is the deterioration of relationships and the erosion of moral character. The well-known maxim—“What you do not wish for yourself, do not inflict on others”—captures a relational ethic that emphasizes empathy and responsibility. In practical terms, this implies that preventing harm involves restoring balance through appropriate conduct and institutions, not simply compensating losses (Wang 2022; Dollinger 1988).

Buddhism expands the moral community and centers non-harm (*ahimsā*) and compassion (*karuṇā*). Because suffering (*dukkha*) is understood as pervasive and interconnected, the scope of harm extends beyond human-to-human interactions to include all sentient beings and, in many interpretations, the wider ecological web. Mahāyāna traditions prevalent in East Asia emphasize interdependence: a single harmful act can reverberate through the network of life. This leads to a cautious stance toward actions with uncertain side effects—an ethical posture closely aligned with precautionary approaches in sustainability governance (Harvey 2000; Kang 2025).

Daoism emphasizes harmony with the Dao and warns against excessive intervention. Dao, which in Chinese means “the way”, refers to the ineffable, self-so ground of all reality — the natural order from which all things arise and unfold. Harm is often produced by forcing rigid structures onto complex living systems or by acting with hubris and overcontrol. The ideal of *wuwei* (non-coercive action) encourages minimal, adaptive, and context-sensitive governance—precisely the kind of mindset needed when DNSH assessments confront uncertainty, indirect effects, and systemic complexity. A “good intention” is not enough; what matters is whether intervention destabilizes an existing equilibrium and generates unintended harm.

Shinto, rooted in Japanese traditions, sees the natural world as infused with *kami* (sacred presences). Harm is often understood as defilement (*kegare*)—a disruption of purity and sacred order—addressed through communal purification rituals (*harai*) and collective practices that restore balance between humans, nature, and the divine. This highlights dimensions of harm that modern regulatory tools frequently miss: spiritual, symbolic, and place-based harms, and the collective responsibility to repair them.

Together, these traditions converge on a key point: **harm is frequently relational, holistic, and morally charged**. This reframes DNSH as more than a compliance filter; it becomes a practice of safeguarding harmony across social, ecological, and (in some traditions) spiritual domains.

Modernization and globalization reshaped concepts of harm across East Asia from the nineteenth century onward through colonial encounters, industrialization, and integration into global markets. These changes introduced more legalistic, individualistic, and economized understandings of harm, often reorienting policy toward development priorities. China, for example, saw Confucian norms interact—and sometimes clash—with Marxist-Leninist frames of class struggle and industrial progress (Kuhn 2016; Wang 2022). Japan’s Meiji-era modernization brought Western legal codifications that reshaped communal norms. Korea’s colonial and post-war development trajectories similarly transformed how harm was identified and remedied.

Globalization then intensified awareness of environmental harm as transnational: air and water pollution, deforestation, and climate change forced alignment with international regimes (e.g., Kyoto and Paris). Rather than replacing tradition outright, this often produced **hybrid paradigms**—mixing modern regulatory instruments with inherited ethical orientations such as Confucian relational responsibility, Buddhist compassion, Daoist ecological sensitivity, and Shinto reverence for place. For DNSH, the lesson is that “significant harm” is socially constructed and culturally interpreted; universal standards can benefit from local ethical resources rather than assuming a single evaluative lens.

Internal diversity across East Asia shows these traditions are not monolithic; conceptions of harm vary within and across societies. **In China, classical Confucianism links harm to broken moral relationships and disrupted harmony:** Mencius emphasizes innate moral tendencies: harming others suppresses human moral potential and corrupts both rulers and citizens. Xunzi, by contrast, treats harm as a predictable product of unrestrained desires, implying the need for strong institutions and ritual norms to prevent selfish competition from producing social and ecological damage (Wang 2022). Neo-Confucianism (e.g., Zhu Xi) adds a cosmological layer: harm becomes a fracture in the moral-natural order, highlighting interdependence and systemic balance—an intuitive parallel to DNSH’s concern with cumulative and systemic impacts (Deuchler 1995; Grayson 2013).

In Japan, Shinto frames **harm as pollution and disruption of sacred balance**, while **Buddhism adds compassion and responsibility for alleviating suffering**; historical movements broaden harm beyond direct injury toward neglect and injustice (Kang 2025), and modern voices like Kenji Miyazawa reinforce the idea that individual flourishing depends on collective flourishing. In **Korea**, ideas like Hongik Ingan (“broadly benefit humankind”) **frame harm as negating collective benefit and imply duties of proactive welfare**; **Neo-Confucian state ideology links legitimacy to preventing harm to the people**, while the Donghak movement adds strong dignity-and-equality themes that map well onto DNSH concerns about distributional effects and vulnerable groups (Deuchler 1995; Grayson 2013). In **Taiwan**, Indigenous cosmologies **often treat harm as disturbance to sacred ecological relations requiring collective restoration**; **syncretic community practices link harm reduction to mutual aid, and democratization has since institutionalized** these ethical expectations

through participatory environmental governance and procedural safeguards in impact assessments (Tang and Tang 1997). (Tang and Tang 1997).

From ethics to governance, harm mitigation across the region often blends moral frameworks with formal institutions. Confucian ideals of benevolent government shape expectations of proactive welfare; Japan's regulatory tradition echoes collective responsibility for nature; Korea's "green growth" agenda frames climate action as a national duty; Taiwan's democratization has strengthened procedural and participatory safeguards. These examples show multiple routes for embedding harm prevention into institutions—through regulation, consultation, and a culture of collective responsibility. The discussion also foregrounds technology and innovation: rapid technological change can generate indirect and unforeseen harms. Daoist and Buddhist warnings against hubris and overcontrol support a precautionary, adaptive stance—highly relevant to DNSH when evaluating complex interventions. The Fukushima disaster illustrates what happens when risk, local knowledge, and worst-case thinking are insufficiently integrated: even “clean” solutions can generate catastrophic harm without robust precaution, oversight, and community-centered governance (Buessler et al. 2011; Funabashi and Kitazawa 2012).

Civil society and community mechanisms—historically through lay associations, temple networks, and mutual-aid structures, and today through NGOs and grassroots movements—**reinforce that avoiding harm requires more than formal compliance.** It requires legitimacy, participation, and culturally rooted accountability, which can improve early detection of risks and broaden what is recognized as “significant.” (Ho 2005; Tang and Tang 1997; Kuhn 2016; Grano 2015)

East Asia's track record in managing harm reveals several policy-level takeaways that could refine or expand DNSH applications:

- **Holistic Definition of “Harm”:** By interpreting harm as disruptions to social, moral, and ecological harmony, policymakers may need to adapt environmental assessments to capture intangible or long-term effects.
- **Strong Ethical Underpinnings:** Integrating Buddhist or Confucian ethics can foster a deep sense of responsibility among government officials, businesses, and citizens, reinforcing DNSH compliance as a moral, not merely legal, obligation.
- **Community-Centric Approaches:** Lessons from communal networks (e.g., *kō* in Japan, temple associations in Taiwan) and civil society movements show how grassroots engagement can substantively enhance early detection of potential harm.
- **Adaptive Regulations:** Drawing on Daoist notions of flexibility, regulators might benefit from adopting adaptive management strategies—adjusting rules as conditions change, thereby pre-empting unintended harm.
- **Long-Term Vision:** Echoing Kenji Miyazawa's insistence that no one can be truly happy unless the entire world is happy, East Asian ethics remind policymakers to adopt long-range perspectives that transcend immediate fiscal or political cycles.

Furthermore, the Eastern perspectives can offer insights about the need for a **deeper reflection on the concept of “significant” in the DNSH and its implications.** Confucianism highlights **moral and communal rupture** (loss of trust, breakdown of harmony) as a serious

harm even if it is hard to measure; Shinto emphasizes **spiritual/cultural disruption** (e.g., *kegare* and damage to sacred places); and Buddhism/Daoism stress **interdependence and delayed effects**, where small impacts can become significant through ecological feedbacks and cumulative cascades.

Because conceptions of harm vary across societies, there is a need for **context-sensitive processes**: community dialogue and consensus-building, **adaptive** (non-static) standards informed by Daoist flexibility, and inclusion of spiritual/cultural custodians (e.g., shrine or temple networks) in impact assessments. It then contrasts the EU Taxonomy's environmental "pillars" approach with East Asian legal and policy traditions that often foreground **systemic balance and collective welfare** (e.g., China's "ecological civilization," Japan's comprehensive environmental measures, Korea's welfare-oriented constitutional framing, Taiwan's participatory EIA).

A further expansion is temporal: East Asian traditions emphasize **future generations**, encouraging intergenerational assessments, long-horizon scenario planning, and attention to irreversible tipping points. Finally, the text proposes ways to "measure the unmeasurable" via **composite frameworks** combining quantitative and qualitative indicators (social cohesion indices, cultural heritage inventories, adaptive capacity measures, and long-term ecological monitoring). Overall, it concludes that DNSH should treat significance not as a simple binary threshold but as a **multi-dimensional, relational, and evolving judgment** grounded in both scientific evidence and local ethical realities.

All in all, bringing East Asian perspectives into DNSH reflection underscores two closely linked shifts.

First, it highlights the need for a relational understanding of harm. Confucian, Buddhist, Shinto (and Daoist) traditions treat social and ecological well-being as fundamentally interdependent. From this view, "significant harm" is not limited to biophysical damage captured by technical indicators; it also includes erosion of community trust, disruption of cultural integrity, loss of spiritual or place-based meaning, and failures of moral accountability. For DNSH practice, this implies more holistic assessments and forms of stakeholder engagement that are continuous and community-embedded—closer to deliberative, consultative traditions than to one-off consultations treated as procedural requirements.

Second, it foregrounds intergenerational ethics and a precautionary approach to uncertainty. East Asian traditions emphasize responsibilities to descendants—through ancestor veneration, karmic consequences, and lineage continuity—encouraging DNSH to institutionalize long-horizon scenario planning and to treat "small" harms as potentially significant when they accumulate and push systems toward tipping points. This long-term orientation also strengthens how DNSH deals with technological complexity: Daoist caution supports incremental deployment, monitoring, and adaptive course-correction; Buddhist compassion reinforces climate justice by prioritizing vulnerable groups and fair burden-sharing; and Shinto reverence for nature heightens sensitivity to irreversible landscape changes and impacts on sacred sites.

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5. From compliance to design: DNSH as a deliberative framework for R&I practice

The preceding sections of this report have pursued two interrelated goals. The first was analytical: to explain the DNSH principle as it is currently defined, trace its legal and regulatory foundations, and document the significant gaps between its formal requirements and its implementation in practice. The second was normative: to argue that these gaps are not merely technical failures but reflect deeper conceptual limitations — a narrow, quantitative conception of harm that systematically excludes cultural loss, irreversibility, distributive injustice, and the claims of non-human and Indigenous stakeholders. DNSH, the report has argued, is already a normative framework, whether or not it acknowledges itself as one. Making that normativity explicit is not a weakening of the principle but a precondition for its more honest and effective application.

This chapter turns to the practical question that follows: what would a more adequate operationalisation of DNSH actually look like when applied at the level of research programs and governance?

The question is not straightforward, because research contexts present **particular challenges that standard regulatory DNSH assessments are not designed to address**. The harms associated with research are often emergent, indirect, and difficult to anticipate *ex ante*; they unfold across extended timeframes and diverse social and ecological settings; and they implicate communities, knowledge systems, and living entities whose moral standing is not captured by existing assessment frameworks. A compliance-oriented application of DNSH — one that treats the principle as a checklist to be satisfied at the funding application stage — is structurally ill-suited to these realities.

But there is a further dimension to this inadequacy that points beyond diagnosis toward a different kind of solution. DNSH, as currently conceived, is a governance instrument: it provides indicators for sustainable investment and functions as a mechanism of institutional accountability. It was not designed as a design orientation — that is, as a framework for making choices within R&I processes themselves, for deliberating between options, for integrating environmental and climate ethical perspectives into the ongoing work of researchers and innovators.

What this chapter argues, **therefore, is that the application potential of DNSH extends well beyond its current regulatory function**. In line with the broader claim advanced throughout the RE4GREEN project — that effective integration of environmental and climate ethics into R&I requires deliberative and discursive approaches — we propose understanding **DNSH-by-design as a deliberative and facilitative framework**: one employed not merely to screen projects before they begin, but **to orient choices, surface trade-offs, and structure ethical reflection throughout R&I activities**. This is not a departure from the principle's logic but a development of it — one that takes seriously both the normative commitments already

implicit in DNSH and the particular demands of the research contexts in which it is increasingly expected to apply.

5.1 Plural conceptions of harm and the need for contextual, in-depth assessment

From empirical and theoretical work—ranging from ethnographic studies of diverse cultural understandings of harm to ecological research, and from comparative analysis across Western and Eastern humanities—it has become clear that **harm**, as a core concept in ethics, cannot be reduced to a checklist of (quantitative) indicators. Assessing harm in research projects therefore requires **thick, context-sensitive analysis**, developed with and tested against the perspectives of the stakeholders and communities—human and more-than-human—who may be affected by a project’s aims, methods, and outcomes.

In practice, this also means recognizing that many salient impacts are not easily captured ex ante: harms can be cumulative, delayed, spatially displaced, and mediated through complex socio-ecological feedbacks. As the climate “loss and damage” debate illustrates, the most ethically significant losses may be non-economic (e.g., loss of life, cultural heritage, identity, biodiversity, territory), and therefore resistant to commodification or straightforward quantification (Shockley and Hourdequin 2017; Preston 2017). Stirling (2010) further underlines that uncertainty is not merely a knowledge gap to be closed, but often an inherent feature of complex systems—suggesting that robust harm assessment must remain open to surprise, contestation, and adaptive revision rather than treating risk as fully resolvable through calculation alone.

A justice lens is indispensable here because it clarifies *what “significant harm” means and who bears responsibility for preventing it*. In climate justice, Caney (2014) distinguishes harm-avoidance justice—centered on preventing serious threats to fundamental entitlements (often articulated in human-rights terms)—from distributive justice, which focuses on allocating the burdens of mitigation, adaptation, and loss-and-damage fairly (e.g., polluter-pays, ability-to-pay, beneficiary-pays). These perspectives are complementary: harm-avoidance helps define morally relevant thresholds (what must not be allowed to happen to vulnerable people and communities), while distributive justice specifies how the costs of preventing such harms should be shared. At the same time, the ethical vocabulary of harm must be widened beyond welfare-reduction accounts. McShane (2017), for example, draws a crucial distinction between interpreting “loss” as harm to human well-being versus understanding loss as the destruction of something valuable, whether or not it diminishes human welfare in measurable terms. Parallel arguments in feminist care ethics and related relational approaches emphasize that harms are often best understood as failures of responsiveness within relationships of interdependence, and that ethical assessment must attend to power, vulnerability, and lived social-ecological contexts rather than only abstract metrics (Preston and Wickson 2016; Preston 2017). This further supports **deliberative, participatory approaches** to DNSH that can register relational and culturally embedded harm – such as erosion of community cohesion,

loss of place-based identity, or undermining of traditional ecological knowledge—alongside biophysical impacts.

Across different concepts of justice, however, **important tensions remain**—especially once the “community of justice” expands beyond humans. A family of non-anthropocentric theories challenges the assumption that only humans can be subjects (or beneficiaries) of justice, reworking justice’s subjects, objects, and metrics. Multispecies justice, for example, extends environmental justice and debates on ecological harm by arguing that the community of justice includes nonhuman beings, ecological collectives, and the relationships through which multispecies lifeways are sustained. While it draws crucial impetus from animal-rights theory, which foregrounds the moral standing of individual animals, this individualist orientation can sit uneasily with conservation biology and ecological integrity perspectives that prioritize species, populations, and ecosystem functioning. At the same time, scholars caution that institutional strategies grounded in rights and legal personhood—central to many rights-of-nature movements—may both challenge the treatment of ecosystems as property and risk reproducing settler-colonial and anthropocentric legal categories unless paired with substantive commitments to Indigenous sovereignty and racial justice (Fitz-Henry 2022).

Engaging seriously with Indigenous perspectives — not as repositories of ecological wisdom but as sovereign political frameworks with their own jurisprudence over land, water, and living systems — reveals a dimension of harm that the current DNSH framework does not adequately address. Across many Indigenous traditions, responsible land stewardship is not passive non-interference but active, skilled, and culturally grounded practice. The land, in these frameworks, is not simply an object of protection but a subject of care — one that can be neglected, wounded, or revived depending on the quality of human engagement with it. Harm, therefore, is not only what is done to land, but what is withheld from it. Cultural burning offers a particularly instructive example. Practiced across Australia, Canada, California, and many other regions, it represents a form of land management that requires deliberate human intervention to sustain ecological health, prevent catastrophic wildfire, and restore degraded landscapes (McCormack et al. 2024). Historically suppressed by colonial legal frameworks that equated intervention with destruction, such practices have in many jurisdictions been progressively — if incompletely — rehabilitated through extrajudicial agreements and collaborative governance arrangements. Land needs to be supported in order to be revived. Inaction is not neutrality; it is itself a form of harm (McCormack et al. 2024).

This reframes what “do no harm” can mean at a fundamental level. Rather than a principle of restraint alone, **DNSH can also be understood as encompassing an affirmative obligation** — to support, rehabilitate, and sustain the conditions under which both human communities and living systems can flourish. In this way “Do No Harm” also moves towards an idea of rehabilitation and care through forms of intervention.

Finally, scholars caution that institutional strategies grounded in rights and legal personhood—central within many rights-of-nature movements—can both challenge the treatment of ecosystems as property and still risk reproducing settler-colonial and anthropocentric legal categories unless paired with substantive commitments to Indigenous sovereignty and racial justice (Fitz-Henry 2022). Decolonial perspectives sharpen this critique

by showing how colonial histories, racialised political economy, and extractivism shape what is recognised as “harm,” whose knowledge is treated as authoritative, and who holds decision-making power over land, waters, and more-than-human worlds (Fitz-Henry 2022; Celermajer et al. 2021). Together, multispecies and decolonial approaches add a justice-oriented layer that centres recognition and representation, strengthens accountability across supply chains, and prioritises the repair of damaged relationships—alongside distributional impacts.

For harm assessment in research projects, the practical upshot is clear: DNSH cannot be a one-off technical filter. It must be an **iterative, participatory, and pluralistic practice that can track cumulative and systemic effects, accommodate non-economic and nonhuman losses, and make explicit the normative judgments**—about thresholds, trade-offs, and responsibility—that any claim of “no significant harm” inevitably contains.

5.2 Continuous harm assessment in R&I

Current recommendations for implementing the DNSH principle in R&I processes concern the very early phase of projects, namely project design, proposal writing, and funding applications. Yet, as previous sections have demonstrated, the potential of the principle to adequately address normative dimensions of harms and their systemic character can only be harvested when **it serves as an orientation not only at the beginning but throughout the development and design process over the course of an R&I project**. Many (potentially significant) harms cannot be predicted at the beginning of a R&I project but are elicited, assessed, and processed at a later stage. Rather than being just another tick box exercise, a helpful operationalisation of the DNSH principle would foster deliberative and participatory research practices in order to keep track of harm potentials and their mitigation.

A central question for assessing a project with respect to its potential of not doing significant harm concerns the possibility of designing a project for no significant harm. If we ask this question, then we have to recognize that R&I agents (researchers, engineers, technology and system developers/designers, and innovators) have to be offered instruments in order to assess whether their work output (knowledge, devices, systems, processes, etc.) has the potential to cause significant harm — whether material or physical, economic, ethical, or societal in nature, whether direct or indirect, immediate or long-term, and whether resulting from intended use or foreseeable misuse. R&I agents are, usually, trained in assessing scientific-technical risks, for example life-cycle assessments, toxicity of compounds, environmental and eco-system impacts, etc. Moreover, especially in corporate innovation contexts, economic impacts are studied as well and are addressed in Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) of the respective activities. In all these cases, it is possible to formulate indicators that provide information about the acceptability of risks (defined as the likelihood of a harm of a certain extent). Since such a quantification of harm is not possible for a wide range of non-material harms as described in previous sections, different approaches to risk discourses are necessary if ethical and societal risks are to be included in the assessment of significant harms. The International Risk Governance Council (IRGC) has proposed the useful concept of the risk escalator to set a methodological foundation for a wider range of risk assessment strategies capable of addressing normative risks (Renn and Graham 2005). By disentangling complexity-induced,

uncertainty-induced and ambiguity-induced risks and outlining the different discourses needed to adequately address and work on them, it becomes possible to identify not only those technical risks that can be tackled by more research or more expertise but also value clashes and stakes that the R&I context at hand touches and that—for both eliciting and addressing them—require normative discourses that include affected and third parties.

It becomes obvious that **only a deliberative approach to responsible R&I agency can meaningfully employ the DNSH principle in R&I activities.** The identification, definition and processing of significant harms and available options for mitigating or avoiding them are **most effective when R&I practices include participatory, interdisciplinary, and inclusive multi-stakeholder discourses.**

In practical terms, the role of the DNSH principle in ethical impact assessments and ethical risk assessments needs to be clarified (cf. D 3.3). An adequate assessment procedure may be guided by DNSH as the guiding principle shaping its form and content. For example, a range of significant environmental harms are identified, and the impacts of the assessed R&I context in terms of these harms are surveyed. Highlighted risks are then to be addressed in the R&I work to avoid doing significant harm. In this sense, an R&I team potentially learns from the assessment survey what possible significant harms have not yet been on their screen. The purpose of such a DNSH assessment is to transfer knowledge about the type and conditions of such harms, and to make sure that all R&I is empowered to identify and respond to them. A useful assessment must come along with indicators of what causes these harms and which alternative R&I trajectories may reduce either the significance or the likelihood of occurrence of the harm. The logic of the assessment would be: Significant harm type A, B, C, D,... --> among these, your R&I project obviously has the potential to cause harm type A, D, F, K... --> measures to tackle/reduce/mitigate these harms. The assessors may not need to learn what the DNSH principle is, because the creators of the assessment method have translated it into the content of the protocol.

Alternatively, the DNSH principle may be introduced as a strategic guideline for finding out how to respond to identified adverse impacts of an R&I activity. For example, when the R&I team plausibly identifies a harmful impact and wonders whether and how it must be addressed during the research or the design of the innovative technology or system, the DNSH principle may give guidance. However, the harm identification itself is not informed by the principle but roots in other work processes (common assessment methods, professional experience, multi-stakeholder discourses, etc.). Then, R&I agents employ the DNSH principle to solve an issue they come across during their work, perhaps via another impact assessment, or through stakeholder consultations, for example. The identified harm is assessed through the lens of the DNSH principle in order to elaborate solutions and strategies for dealing with the risk. This requires a clear and workable definition of the DNSH principle and, again, indicators of how to express significant harms or their reduction, especially when it is intended as the overarching orientational principle to be applied in all R&I. R&I agents would need to learn what the DNSH principle actually is and how it applies to the context of the own work.

It is important to point out that the DNSH principle is **not intended as one among many assessment principles that responsible R&I agents** (i.e., those concerned about impacts and

implications of their work, including ethical, societal, and cultural ones) learn about and apply, such as the precautionary principle, the polluter-pays-principle, the proactionary principle, or the substitution principle that are usually applied in specific situations where their guidance is deemed helpful. The DNSH principle is not communicated and enacted as a tool that can be selected and applied depending on the contextual conditions of an identified harm.

Furthermore, the DNSH principle does not serve as a tool by itself. Rather, **the thorough reflection of harm potentials along the lines of its taxonomy encourages the application of existing (partly tool-like) assessment strategies** for technical, material, economic, legal, societal, cultural, and ethical implications.

In recent years, a range of normative risk assessment concepts and their translation into design and decision-making aids have been developed that are well-suited to be integrated with the rationale and the objectives of the DNSH principle. Ethical vision assessment (Grin and Grunwald 2000; Frey et al. 2022), ethical impact assessment (Brey 2025), and tools such as the Societal Readiness Thinking Tool (Braun et al. 2025) help R&I agents to gain validated and processible insights into the normative dimensions of their work. Innovation and design approaches such as value-sensitive design/engineering (van den Hoven and Manders-Huits 2012; Friedman and Hendry 2019; Spiekermann 2023), STIR (Fisher and Maricle 2015; Smolka et al. 2022), designing for value (Veluwenkamp and van den Hoven 2023), or ethics-by-design (Mönig et al. 2025), give practical guidance in co-creating research output that would proactively mitigate significant harm potentials. Since many of these approaches require inclusive, participatory, inter- and transdisciplinary, and multi-stakeholder R&I processes, the reflection of significant harms becomes the systemic endeavour it is intended to be.

What these approaches share — and what makes them relevant to a reoriented understanding of DNSH — is a **commitment to embedding normative reflection into the process of R&I rather than appending it as an external audit**. They treat harm not as a residual risk to be screened out at the point of funding approval, but as a category that must be actively interrogated, contested, and responded to as knowledge and design choices evolve. In this respect, they already embody the logic that a deliberative operationalisation of DNSH requires: that "do no significant harm" is less a threshold to be cleared than **an ongoing orientation to be sustained**.

6. Recommendations for operationalizing DNSH in research governance

The preceding sections pursued two interrelated goals. Analytically, they traced the DNSH principle's legal foundations and documented the gaps between its formal requirements and implementation in practice. Normatively, they argued that treating "do no significant harm" as a mere compliance exercise fails to acknowledge the deeper ethical commitments already embedded within it. Drawing on Western environmental ethics, transcultural frameworks, Indigenous knowledge traditions, and Eastern philosophical thought, the report has shown that harm is irreducibly specific — shaped by context, relationship, and value, and resistant to capture by standardized indicators. What counts as harm, to whom it can be done, and who holds authority to judge its significance are questions demanding interpretation and normative honesty, not only technical compliance.

The recommendations developed here therefore advocate for a model of harm assessment that is **contextual** — sensitive to the specific social, ecological, and cultural conditions of each research project; continuous — **structured** as an iterative practice rather than a one-off compliance exercise; and **pluralistic** — open to diverse epistemologies, including Indigenous and non-Western frameworks, and attentive to forms of harm that resist quantification.

Crucially, this chapter also makes the case that realizing such a model requires institutional commitment beyond good intentions. Dedicated funding and structural support for broadening normative research into harm — its meanings, its distributions, and its limits — must be recognized as a legitimate and necessary component of responsible research governance, not an optional supplement to it.

The following recommendations emerge directly from the analysis developed throughout this report. They are addressed primarily to research funding bodies, program managers, and governance actors responsible for designing and implementing DNSH frameworks at the level of research programs — with the broader aim of making harm assessment more rigorous, more just, and more responsive to the full complexity of what harm, in practice, means.

6.1 Recommendation: Align innovation governance with sustainability obligations

Contemporary EU innovation policy has progressively institutionalized instruments — accelerated regulatory pathways, environmental assessment exemptions, regulatory sandboxes, and time-bound derogations that structurally privilege speed and competitiveness over harm prevention. The DNSH principle, which requires that no economic activity supported by public funds cause significant damage to environmental objectives, remains largely confined to financing logics and ex ante approval conditions. It has not been systematically integrated into the structural frameworks that govern the design, authorization, and deployment of innovation policy more broadly. This decoupling constitutes a governance gap that must be closed.

Closing it requires two complementary moves. First, the DNSH principle must be extended beyond its current role as a funding eligibility criterion and embedded throughout the full lifecycle of publicly supported innovation — from early-stage research through to market deployment and beyond. Second, this extension must be animated by the precautionary principle, which reorients the application logic of harm prevention in a crucial respect: rather than waiting for evidence of injury to materialize before corrective action is taken, it activates scrutiny of potential adverse effects at the earliest stages of decision-making and treats scientific uncertainty itself as sufficient grounds for intervention. Together, these two principles establish that the burden of demonstrating safety cannot be deferred until after deployment, and that any mechanism that relaxes or accelerates assessment obligations must be counterbalanced by enforceable safeguards with genuine corrective authority. Efficiency and competitiveness remain legitimate policy objectives, but they are valid only insofar as they are pursued within — and constrained by — the requirements of ecological responsibility and long-term sustainability.

Implementation details

<i>Field</i>	<i>Details</i>
<i>Owner</i>	EC/DG RTD and DG ENV jointly define the governance requirement and ensure its coherence across innovation and sustainability policy frameworks; relevant scientific agencies provide methodological input to DNSH threshold-setting and precautionary screening; implementing agencies and funding bodies operationalize requirements through authorization conditions and grant clauses; project officers and ethics reviewers verify compliance and enforce consequences.
<i>Action</i>	(i) Establish a DNSH Lifecycle Governance Protocol specifying compliance obligations across all phases of the innovation cycle, with a tiered framework linking the degree of scientific uncertainty to the stringency of required precautionary safeguards; (ii) a publicly accessible registry of active derogations with associated uncertainty and DNSH compliance profiles, subject to periodic review
<i>Deliverable</i>	Programme-level: (i) a DNSH Lifecycle Governance Protocol specifying compliance obligations across all phases of the innovation cycle, with a tiered framework linking the

	<p>degree of scientific uncertainty to the stringency of required precautionary safeguards; (ii) model derogation templates incorporating mandatory sunset clauses, renewal conditions, and DNSH-linked corrective action triggers; (iii) guidance on uncertainty profiling methodology for novel technological applications; (iv) a publicly accessible registry of active derogations with associated uncertainty and DNSH compliance profiles, subject to periodic review.</p> <p>Project-level: (i) a DNSH and Precautionary Impact Statement prepared prior to authorization, documenting the uncertainty profile, identified risks, and proposed safeguards; (ii) a Derogation Conditions Record specifying terms, duration, and renewal criteria; (iii) a Safety and DNSH Compliance Report submitted at each renewal threshold, evidencing affirmative compliance with precautionary conditions.</p>
<p><i>Timeline</i></p>	<p>Short-term: integrate DNSH lifecycle compliance and precautionary screening requirements into relevant legislative and programmatic instruments as binding obligations rather than aspirational provisions. <i>Medium term</i>: develop the DNSH Lifecycle Governance Protocol and associated guidance in parallel with the entry into force of applicable frameworks, ensuring implementing instruments are operational from the first authorization cycle. <i>During authorization and deployment</i>: precautionary screening completed before any accelerated or sandbox procedure is initiated; DNSH compliance and uncertainty profiles updated at each reporting cycle; corrective action initiated immediately upon breach of DNSH or precautionary thresholds.</p>

6.2 Recommendation: Resource and require context-specific harm and significant harm analyses

Horizon Europe work programmes should earmark funding for context-specific harm-analysis, and projects with plausible harm pathways should be required **to devote a defined share of their budgets** to it. The analysis should include:

- documenting local meanings of “harm”
- inquiring on “significant harm”
- mapping affected groups, power relations, and competing interests;
- anticipating how trade-offs are likely to be perceived and contested.

This resourcing turns DNSH from an abstract compliance step into a culturally grounded assessment (Kotsila & Anguelovski 2023; Van Daalen et al. 2023).

In addition, the Commission’s Societal Readiness pilot offers a useful institutional design: it is accompanied by a dedicated Coordination and Support Action (CSA) that monitors, coordinates, and lightly supports implementation (e.g., interviews, workshops, cross-project exchange). A similar CSA-style “helpdesk” could be created for projects navigating harms and their significance—providing methodological guidance, facilitating learning across projects, and supporting adaptive updates rather than static compliance (European Commission 2025c).

Implementation details

<i>Field</i>	<i>Details</i>
<i>Owner</i>	EC/DG (DG RTD as lead, with the relevant thematic DG + implementing executive agency) sets requirement; funded university/PI executes it.
<i>Action</i>	Embed a mandatory “context-specific harm analysis” requirement in call text, proposal template evaluation/ethics checks, and the grant agreement (triggered when credible harm pathways exist). Require a defined budget share, stakeholder engagement, and periodic updates so the analysis is not a one-off.
<i>Deliverable</i>	Programme-level: guidance + checklist/template for applicants and reviewers. Project-level: a Harm Pathways and Mitigation Plan covering local meanings of harm/significant harm; affected groups/power relations/competing interests; contested trade-offs; and linked mitigation actions + monitoring indicators (with updates over time).
<i>Timeline</i>	Short-term: next Work Programme/call cycle (requirement + reviewer guidance). During the project: initial analysis early (e.g., months 3–6), update at mid-term review, final update before close-out.

6.3 Recommendation: Institutionalize social-cultural indicators in DNSH decisions

DNSH evaluations should systematically integrate indicators such as community cohesion, relational values/human–nature relationships, cultural heritage assets, and place-based meanings. These indicators should be co-designed with affected communities and explicitly documented as inputs shaping the DNSH judgement, making the assessment transparent, context-sensitive, and auditable.

Implementation details

<i>Field</i>	<i>Details</i>
<i>Owner</i>	EC/DG (DG RTD + relevant thematic DGs) sets policy requirements; implementing executive agencies / funding bodies operationalize them in templates and reviewer guidance; funded university/PI and partners implement indicator co-design and reporting; evaluators/ethics reviewers apply the evidence in DNSH judgements.
<i>Action</i>	(1) Define a minimum set of social-cultural indicator domains that must be considered relevant and integrate them into DNSH guidance and appraisal forms. (2) Require that projects co-design indicators with affected communities (or justify why not feasible) and trace how indicator evidence affected the DNSH judgement (decision-trace). (3) Provide evaluators with rubrics for assessing the quality of co-design and evidence use (not just the presence of indicators).
<i>Deliverable</i>	Programme-level: (i) DNSH guidance annex listing recommended social-cultural indicator domains and selection criteria; (ii) co-design research protocol; (iii) reviewer scoring guide (rubric) and short training module. Project-level: (i) Social-Cultural Indicator Evidence Note (methods, participants, indicators, results); (ii) DNSH decision-trace showing how indicators shaped the judgement and mitigations; (iii) updates when context changes.
<i>Timeline</i>	Short-term: next call/work programme revision (add indicator domains + templates + reviewer rubric). During the project: co-design and baseline evidence early (e.g., months 3–6), update when material changes occur and at mid-term, final evidence note + decision-trace at close-out.

6.4 Recommendation: Address structural innovation harms

DNSH should explicitly assess structural innovation harms that arise when dominant digital infrastructures can delay, constrain, or condition access to innovation (“captured innovation”), producing societal harms through restricted diffusion, foreclosed alternatives, and entrenched dependency. DNSH evaluations for digitally mediated projects should therefore include enforceable criteria for openness, interoperability, portability, and anti-lock-in safeguards, supported by contractual requirements and lifecycle monitoring (not only ex ante compliance).

- Assessment: risks of vendor/platform lock-in; dependence on proprietary standards/APIs; barriers to switching; limits on reuse/replication; restrictive licensing or data access terms; concentration of control over critical digital components.
- Minimum safeguard areas: open standards where feasible; documented interoperability interfaces; data and model portability; exit/switching plans; transparency on licensing/IP constraints; governance for long-term access and maintenance.

Implementation details

<i>Field</i>	<i>Details</i>
<i>Owner</i>	EC/DG (DG RTD + relevant thematic DGs; with support from DG CNECT where digital infrastructure is central) sets requirements; implementing executive agencies/funding bodies operationalize them in call texts, templates, and grant conditions; funded university/PI and consortium implement safeguards; evaluators/project officers verify compliance over the lifecycle.
<i>Action</i>	(1) Introduce a “structural innovation harms” DNSH screening for digitally mediated projects (triggered when projects rely on, build, or integrate platform-like infrastructures). (2) Make openness/interoperability/portability/anti-lock-in safeguards mandatory where risks are material, with clear <i>acceptability thresholds</i> (e.g., documented open interfaces, portability tests, exit plan). (3) Embed requirements in the Grant Agreement/contractual clauses (e.g., interoperability deliverables; data export formats; escrow or continuity plans where appropriate). (4) Require lifecycle monitoring with checkpoints (e.g., mid-term: interoperability/portability demonstration; final: verified exit plan + artifact availability).
<i>Deliverable</i>	Programme-level: (i) DNSH guidance annex defining “captured innovation” and structural harm pathways; (ii) criteria checklist for openness/interoperability/portability/anti-lock-in; (iii) model grant clauses (interoperability, portability, exit/switching, licensing transparency); (iv) reviewer briefing/training note.

	<p>Project-level: (i) Exit and handover plan: what standards you use, how other systems can connect (APIs/interfaces), how users can export their data in common formats, and how the project can move to another provider/system if needed.</p> <p>(ii) Proof that it works: at agreed milestones, show evidence (tests/demos) that the system can connect to other tools and that data can be exported and reused as promised.</p> <p>(iii) Ongoing DNSH compliance record: a short log updated during the project that records key risks, changes made, issues found, and the corrective actions taken.</p>
<p><i>Timeline</i></p>	<p>Short-term: integrate screening and criteria into the next call/work programme and evaluator guidance; add model clauses to grant templates.</p> <p>During the project: initial plan early (e.g., months 3–6), mid-term verification (interoperability/portability test evidence), final verification (exit plan + artifacts/exports validated) and post-project access/continuity arrangements where relevant.</p>

6.5 Recommendation: Move DNSH from ex ante approval to lifecycle accountability

DNSH should be embedded in adaptive, project-long governance with enforceable corrective capacity. This requires:

- multi-stakeholder panels combining technical, ethical, and cultural expertise (including Indigenous/cultural custodians where relevant);
- adaptive management protocols—phased deployment, continuous monitoring, trigger thresholds, periodic reassessment, and enforceable corrective actions (redesign, pause, termination), particularly under uncertainty and innovation-driven risk.

This directly addresses the well-noted weakness of predominantly ex ante enforcement with limited ex post correction (Famà 2025). In this way DNSH becomes a living risk-harm governance process rather than a one-time compliance statement.

Implementation details

<i>Field</i>	<i>Details</i>
<i>Owner</i>	EC/DG (DG RTD + relevant thematic DGs) defines the governance requirement; implementing executive agencies/funding bodies operationalize it via call conditions, grant clauses, and review processes; funded university/PI and consortium establish and run the governance system; project officers/evaluators/ethics reviewers verify functioning and enforce consequences.
<i>Action</i>	(1) Require each relevant project to establish an Independent DNSH Governance Panel with balanced expertise (technical, ethics, socio-cultural; include Indigenous/cultural custodians where relevant and legitimate). (2) Mandate an Adaptive DNSH Management Protocol covering phased deployment, continuous monitoring, periodic reassessment, and pre-defined trigger thresholds linked to enforceable corrective actions. (3) Build decision authority and escalation routes into contractual terms (e.g., panel recommendations must be addressed within fixed time). (4) Require transparent documentation and integrate governance outputs into periodic reporting and reviews.
<i>Deliverable</i>	Programme-level: (i) guidance on panel composition, independence, conflict-of-interest management, and fair participation/compensation; (ii) adaptive management template (monitoring indicators, triggers, escalation ladder, corrective action menu); (iii) model grant clauses enabling pause/redesign/termination tied to DNSH triggers; (iv) reviewer/project-officer checklist. Project-level: (i) DNSH Governance Charter (membership, roles, authority, decision process); (ii) Adaptive DNSH Management Plan (phases, monitoring, triggers, corrective actions); (iii) DNSH Decision and Corrective Action with evidence of actions taken.

Timeline

Short-term: include requirement in the next call/work programme cycle.

During the project: panel constituted and protocol approved early (e.g., months 1-3), monitoring active from first deployment phase, periodic reassessment aligned with reporting cycles (e.g., every 6-12 months), and immediate corrective action when triggers are met; final governance summary at close-out.

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6.6 Recommendation: Create a dedicated monitoring body within the European Commission

The European Commission should establish a **standing unit or task force** responsible for monitoring DNSH implementation across funded projects and programmes. Its mandate should include:

- tracking how harm—and especially “significant harm”—is defined, measured, and addressed during implementation;
- ensuring comparability and minimum standards across projects while allowing contextual flexibility;
- identifying recurring problems and best practices; and
- providing transparent feedback loops to improve future calls, guidance, and evaluation criteria.

This body would strengthen consistency and accountability, while aligning DNSH practice with the precautionary principle’s emphasis on **iterative learning and risk governance** (European Commission 2020a; PALTRIGUERA, et al. 2024). In this way the DNSH is moved from a fragmented project-by-project interpretation to a programme-wide learning and accountability function.

Implementation details

<i>Field</i>	<i>Details</i>
<i>Owner</i>	EC/DG (DG RTD as lead, with coordination across relevant DGs and executive agencies) establishes the body and mandate; executive agencies/funding bodies supply harmonized monitoring data; funded projects (universities/Pis/consortia) provide standardized reporting inputs; evaluators/project officers interface with findings in future assessments.
<i>Action</i>	(1) Create a DNSH Monitoring Unit/Taskforce with a clear mandate, governance, and resourcing (staffing, data access, coordination with agencies). (2) Define a minimum DNSH reporting standard and require projects to submit periodic DNSH implementation updates (not only at proposal stage). (3) Operate a cross-programme monitoring system that reviews project outputs, audits a sample in depth, and flags inconsistencies or recurring harm pathways. (4) Establish feedback loops: issue periodic guidance updates, propose changes to call texts/templates, and provide evaluator briefings.
<i>Deliverable</i>	Programme-level: (i) unit/taskforce terms of reference; (ii) DNSH implementation dashboard (internal) + protocol for sampling/audits; (iii) minimum reporting standard (definitions, indicators, required fields, comparability rules, confidentiality handling); (iv) periodic learning reports (recurring problems, best practices, recommended changes to calls/guidance/evaluation); (v) updated guidance and short training notes for evaluators/project officers.

Timeline

Project-level: (i) standardized DNSH implementation update submissions aligned to reporting cycles; (ii) documentation package for audits when selected.

Short-term: set up the unit/taskforce and reporting standard within the next programme cycle (or within 6–12 months administratively), and pilot monitoring on a subset of calls/projects.

Mid-term: expand to full coverage across relevant programmes; release the first annual learning report and integrate findings into the next Work Programme revisions.

Ongoing: annual/biannual updates to guidance, templates, and evaluator training based on monitoring evidence.

6.7 Recommendation: Provide targeted training and capacity-building programmes

DNSH assessments should be supported by **structured training for project teams, evaluators, and Commission staff**, focusing on the ethical, socio-cultural, and methodological dimensions of harm assessment. Training should include:

- participatory and deliberative methods (meaningful consultation, conflict-sensitive engagement);
- identifying indirect, cumulative, and long-term harms (including system feedbacks);
- integrating One Health approaches (linking human, animal, and ecosystem health) where appropriate; and navigating value pluralism and competing interests in ways that strengthen procedural fairness.

Such capacity-building would improve the quality of assessments, reduce the risk of superficial compliance, and better equip stakeholders to recognize harms that are uncertain, slow-moving, or unevenly distributed.

Implementation details

<i>Field</i>	<i>Details</i>
<i>Owner</i>	EC/DG (DG RTD as lead, with relevant thematic DGs + executive agencies) commissions and governs the programme; executive agencies/funding bodies integrate training into evaluator onboarding and project support; universities/research organisations and PIs ensure project teams complete relevant modules; evaluation panels/ethics reviewers adopt shared practices through training.
<i>Action</i>	(1) Develop a DNSH Training Curriculum with role-specific tracks (project teams; evaluators/ethics experts; Commission/executive agency staff). (2) Make training mandatory or strongly incentivized at key points. (3) Embed practical tools such as consultation scripts, harm pathway mapping, One Health integration checklists (4) Implement assessment of learning and a light certification system to ensure consistency and auditability.
<i>Deliverable</i>	Programme-level: (i) modular training; (ii) case-study library (typical harm pathways; indirect/cumulative harms; contested trade-offs; One Health examples); (iii) toolkits: participatory methods checklist, conflict-sensitive engagement guide, system feedback mapping template, One Health integration guide, procedural fairness guide; (iv) evaluator onboarding module and short refresher updates; (v) completion tracking protocol and reporting metrics. Project-level: (i) documented training completion record for relevant team roles; (ii) optional “community of practice” participation notes or learning log feeding into periodic DNSH updates.

Timeline

Short-term: design curriculum and pilot modules in the next call cycle (or within 6–12 months), prioritizing evaluator onboarding and high-risk digital/impact-heavy calls.

Mid-term: scale to programme-wide coverage, integrate into standard onboarding and project kick-off processes, and publish a stable toolkit.

Ongoing: annual refresh of modules and case library based on monitoring findings and emerging harm patterns.

Unapproved Draft

7. Conclusions

In this report, we examined the steps – and limitations – of the EC’s efforts to advance the “Do No Significant Harm” (DNSH) principle within European R&I. Translating the DNSH regulatory concept into an object of R&I governance proves challenging, we have argued, in large part because of the uncertain, cumulative, indirect, and socially contested nature of harm and its significance. We have presented ways in which the technical operationalization of the DNSH principle by the Commission could benefit from considering alternative ethical worldviews and cultural assumptions, as well as integration of long-term ecological feedbacks. Our arguments have invited a broader set of reflections on harm, the nature of “nature,” notions of justice, and health and damage beyond the quantifiable.

We have argued for an approach to DNSH that embraces, rather than shuns, the particulars of harm, its significance, and the adjudication thereof. Our position is that harm assessments need to be contextually sensitive; iterative rather than time bound; and open to diverse epistemologies. In designing our recommendations around these foundations, we have attempted to address the incompatibilities of the current approaches to DNSH in R&I and its greater ambitions (and potential). Specifically, an “early-and-done” approach to assessing harm – carried out by parties lacking the capacity or incentives for the work while facing a sea of competing governance priorities – is poorly suited to the opportunity of realizing the goals of the DNSH principle.

Instead, we have illuminated six concrete recommendations to operationalize DNSH governance as an ongoing, participatory, pluralistic practice. For each recommendation, we have detailed who might take up the recommendation, what actions and deliverables might be expected of them, and potential timelines for advancing the work. Adopting a lifecycle approach to considering DNSH, addressing structural innovation harms, and institutionalizing epistemologically broader social-cultural indicators are three recommendations for pluralizing DNSH governance in practice. Resourcing, requiring and building capacity to advance work on such broader notions of harm and its significance speak to the need for more participatory approaches. Finally, anchoring responsibility in a dedicated body to caretake the implementation of DNSH to reach its ambitions for the Commission offers a chance for the governance approach to thrive as an ongoing practice.

The work of rethinking DNSH is, ultimately, the work of rethinking responsible governance of R&I in an era of intersecting ecological, cultural, and social crises. As with any moment of crisis, one challenge is always to lift up from the grip of the present and look to the future. We hope this report serves as a beacon to brighten this future horizon and concretely benefit the Commission in its efforts to steward our precious human and planetary resources.

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List of abbreviations

AMIF: Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund

AR6: IPCC Sixth Assessment Report

CLP: Classification, Labelling and Packaging

CRVA: Climate Risk and Vulnerability Assessment

CSA: Coordination and Support Action

CSDDD: Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive

CSRD: Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive

CMD / CMDist: Concept Mover's Distance

DNH: Do No Harm

DNSH: Do No Significant Harm

ECHA: European Chemicals Agency

EEA: European Environment Agency

EFSA: European Food Safety Authority

EIA: Environmental Impact Assessment

EJIA: Environmental Justice Impact Assessment

EMFAF: European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund

ENVI: Committee on the Environment, Public Health and Food Safety

ERA: European Research Area

ERDF: European Regional Development Fund

ESF+: European Social Fund Plus

ESRS: European Sustainability Reporting Standards

EU: European Union

FAO: Food and Agriculture Organization

FPIC: Free, Prior and Informed Consent

HRAF: Human Relations Area Files

e-HRAF: Human Relations Area Files online

IPBES: Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services

IPCC: Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change

IRGC: International Risk Governance Council

ISF: Internal Security Fund

JRC: Joint Research Centre

JTF: Just Transition Fund

LEK: Local Ecological Knowledge

NCP: Nature's Contributions to People

NRCC: National River Conservation Commission

OCM: Outline of Cultural Materials

OH: One Health

OHHLEP: One Health High-Level Expert Panel

R&I: Research and Innovation

RE4GREEN: Research Ethics and Integrity for the GREEN Transition

REACH: Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals

RIA: Regulatory Impact Assessment

RRF: Recovery and Resilience Facility

RRP(s): Recovery and Resilience Plan(s)

SFDR: Sustainable Finance Disclosure Regulation

STIR: Socio-Technical Integration Research

STS: Science and Technology Studies

TEK: Traditional Ecological Knowledge

TFEU: Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union

TSC: Technical Screening Criteria

UNEP: United Nations Environment Programme

UNESCO: United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization

UNFCCC: United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change

WCED: World Commission on Environment and Development

WHO: World Health Organization

WIM: Warsaw International Mechanism

WOAH: World Organisation for Animal Health

Appendix

Unapproved Draft

Ecological harm and the “Do No Significant Harm” principle: Current debates and emerging challenges

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I. Definition and different types of ecological harm

Ecological harm refers to any adverse effect on the structure, function, or integrity of ecosystems induced by natural or anthropogenic activities (IPBES, 2019; MEA, 2005). It encompasses both direct impacts on species and habitats and indirect effects on ecosystem functioning and services. According to White (2021), ecological harm includes “the destruction, degradation or diminishment of ecosystems and non-human entities such as rivers, forests, animals, and plants, whether legally sanctioned or not”. Consequently, ecological harm often results in biodiversity loss, ecosystem degradation, disruption of ecological processes, and declines in ecosystem services (IPBES, 2019; MEA, 2005).

Ecological harm can be classified based on the source, scale of impact, and legal status (Table 1). Based on the source of the harm, we can distinguish harm that involves “taking from the nature” (extraction-based), “adding to the nature” (pollution-based) and “altering nature” (alteration-based) (White, 2021). For instance, habitat loss and fragmentation and overexploitation of natural resources beyond sustainable thresholds are examples of “extraction-based” harm as they result in declines in native species, loss of genetic diversity, alterations of species migration patterns, soil degradation and reduced forest regeneration (Table 1). By the scale of impact, ecological harm can be either local, regional or global (Table 1). At each of these scales, the effect of global harms can be cumulative (i.e., build up over time) or synergistic (i.e., amplified by interactions of multiple harms). Finally, ecological harms can be classified as illegal when they violate environmental laws or legal when they are lawful but ecologically damaging.

II. Scientific and legal perspectives of ecological harm: state-of-the-art

II.I Limitations of traditional legal frameworks addressing environmental harm

Traditional legal regimes addressing environmental harm have historically been shaped by anthropocentric, state-based, and causality-driven frameworks, wherein the environment is protected primarily to serve human interests (Sands et al., 2018; White, 2021). These frameworks rely on the principle of national sovereignty whereby environmental governance is exercised by individual states. They also require a clear causal link between a specific harmful action and identifiable ecological damage. As a result, legal action has generally been limited to cases of direct, localized harm where responsibility is traceable to a single actor. This approach struggles to account for complex, cumulative, and transboundary environmental issues such as biodiversity loss, climate change, and ocean acidification, which involve multiple actors and diffuse sources of harm (Peel & Osofsky, 2017; Westra, 2004).

Moreover, traditional environmental regulations often focus on permissible thresholds of exploitation or damage rather than on preventing harm. This has led to legal systems that may tolerate environmentally damaging practices if they meet technical standards or regulatory requirements, even when such practices contribute to long-term ecological degradation (Bogojević, 2013; White, 2021). As environmental crises become increasingly interconnected and planetary in scope, these legal regimes are being criticized as inadequate. Scholars now call for a shift from anthropocentric, state-centric, and event-based frameworks toward ecocentric legal paradigms that recognize the intrinsic rights of nature and promote broader responsibility frameworks capable of addressing systemic, multi-actor, and transboundary ecological harm (Higgins et al., 2012).

II.II Ecocentric legal frameworks

Given the shortfalls of traditional legal regimes in addressing ecological harm, recent discussions in green criminology and environmental law have urged a shift from anthropocentric environmental law toward more ecocentric legal frameworks that recognize the intrinsic rights of nature. This transition is grounded in the idea that ecosystems, species, and natural entities possess legal standing not only as resources for human use, but also as right-bearing entities that deserve protection (Cullinan, 2011; Higgins et al., 2013). The Rights of Nature movement has gained momentum globally, with countries such as Ecuador and Bolivia incorporating nature's rights into their constitutions. Similarly, legal cases in India, Colombia, and New Zealand have recognized rivers, forests, and mountains as legal persons (Boyd, 2017; Kotzé & French, 2018). These developments reflect growing recognition that traditional environmental laws are insufficient in addressing the scale and complexity of ecological harm in the Anthropocene.

Ecocentric legal approaches also promote broader frameworks that move beyond state-centric and single-actor models. Because ecological harm is increasingly recognized as systemic and multi-actor in nature, these approaches emphasize collective, multi-scalar governance that includes states, corporations, communities, and international institutions as co-responsible actors for ecological harm (Kotzé, 2016). They also aim to address cumulative and transboundary harm, such as deforestation, ocean plastic pollution, and climate change, by accounting for diffuse sources and long-term impacts. In doing so, they integrate principles of environmental justice, ecological justice, and species justice (refer to section 2.3 for additional details), thereby accounting for the intrinsic rights of non-human beings and ecosystems (Schlosberg, 2007; White, 2021).

Furthermore, ecocentric legal frameworks advocate preventative, precautionary, and restorative justice mechanisms. Emerging legal innovations, such as the recognition of "ecocide" as an international crime and the rise of earth-centered constitutionalism, are being explored as ways to hold powerful actors accountable for ecological damages (Higgins et al., 2013). These paradigms also challenge dominant economic and legal systems that externalize environmental costs and normalize harm, calling instead for systemic transformation in governance, ethics, and regulations. In sum, the ecocentric legal approach towards ecological harm represents a multidimensional effort to realign regulatory law with the biophysical realities of earth's systems and the moral imperative of protecting life in all its forms.

II.III. Justice perspective on ecological harm

In recent decades, the ecological harm debate has expanded to include diverse justice perspectives that seek to address the multifaceted nature of environmental degradation. Central to these debates is "**environmental justice**," which emphasizes the fair distribution of environmental benefits and burdens along with the recognition of marginalized communities and their participation in environmental decision-making (Schlosberg, 2007). Environmental justice critiques how disadvantaged groups, particularly rural communities and indigenous people, disproportionately bear the costs of ecological harms, such as pollution and climate change, while having limited access to resources or platforms to challenge these injustices (Agyeman et al., 2016).

Beyond environmental justice, ecological harm debates emphasize "**ecological justice**," which shifts the moral focus from human-centered concerns to the wellbeing of ecosystems and non-human entities. Ecological justice argues that nature should not only be valued for its utility to humans but also recognized for its intrinsic worth and right to flourish (White, 2021). This perspective is essential in addressing harms such as biodiversity loss and habitat destruction, which may not always directly impact humans in the short term but may have significant long-term consequences for ecosystems and future generations. Ecological justice

extends accountability beyond direct human harm by considering environmental injustices upstream and downstream in supply chains. Thus, ecological justice challenges the anthropocentric bias in legal and ethical frameworks by advocating for the protection of entire ecosystems and the recognition of their rights in governance systems (Kotzé, 2016).

A more recent addition is the notion of "**species justice**," which emphasizes the moral and legal consideration of non-human animals and plant species (White, 2021). It advocates respect for the distinctiveness of all species, not just endangered or keystone species, and calls for rethinking of the harm that human activities such as habitat encroachment and genetic modification cause to species (Donaldson, 2011). Species justice intersects with animal rights discourses and has implications for the design of conservation policies, agroecological systems, and land-use governance, particularly in biodiverse but socioeconomically vulnerable regions (e.g., Central Africa). Collectively, these justice perspectives contribute to a broader normative rethinking of responsibility and harm, where the focus is not only on distributive fairness but also on legal protection of non-human entities and species.

III. Ecological harm and the "DNSH" principle: current debates and emerging challenges

Within the discourse of promoting ecocentric legal approaches to mitigate ecological harm, the DNSH principle has emerged as a policy tool designed to integrate environmental safeguards into financial, developmental, and climate-related decision-making. The DNSH is a key criterion in regulatory frameworks such as the European Union (EU) Sustainable Finance Taxonomy ([EU Taxonomy Regulation](#)). It requires that economic activities avoid significantly harming the six core environmental objectives of DNSH including climate change mitigation, biodiversity, pollution, water and marine resources, circular economy, and ecosystem health. While DNSH holds promise as a risk-mitigation mechanism, concerns exist regarding its operational ambiguity, especially regarding what qualifies as "significant harm" and how it is measured across temporal and spatial scales (AFME, 2024). The lack of standardized metrics and context-sensitive thresholds challenges its practical enforcement and weakens its ability to address cumulative and systemic ecological damage.

Another central critique of DNSH is its tendency to rely on anthropocentric legal paradigms, which emphasize harm merely as risks to human interests, thereby neglecting the intrinsic value of nature. This limitation hinders the ability of DNSH framework to account for ecological harms that affect non-human species and ecosystems (Bosselmann, 2016). Furthermore, DNSH is often poorly suited to dealing with multi-actor, transboundary harms, such as deforestation driven by global commodity chains, where causal links are diffused and cut across jurisdictions (Bosselmann, 2016; White, 2021). In response, current debates have called for ecocentric interpretations of DNSH and cross-sectoral harmonization, grounded in principles of ecological justice, species justice and rights of nature, to broaden the notion of harm beyond anthropocentric cost-benefit analyses (Bosselmann, 2016; White, 2021).

Overall, the DNSH principle represents a significant step toward embedding environmental responsibility in decision-making. However, there is an urgent need to clarify definitions, develop robust methodologies (i.e., standardized metrics) for ecological harm assessment, and expand its normative scope to include various (i.e., justice, systemic, cumulative and transboundary) harm perspectives. This step will be crucial for ensuring that DNSH evolves from a technocratic compliance tool into a meaningful standard for safeguarding planetary health.

IV. Operationalizing DNSH for ecological harm reduction

Although the DNSH principle emerges as an important normative and operational framework to mitigate the adverse impacts of nature and anthropogenic activities on key environmental objectives, its operationalization for an effective reduction of ecological harm requires more than compliance checklists. Operationalizing the DNSH principle calls for integrated, precautionary, and ecologically grounded approaches capable of addressing complex, cumulative, and transboundary harms.

In practice, DNSH implementation must be grounded in context-specific environmental risk assessments, robust indicators, and transparent methodologies to identify and mitigate potential harms throughout project lifecycles (AFME, 2024; ESMA, 2023). In particular, efforts should be made to ensure compliance with the "Precautionary Principle", which advocates for preventive action in the face of uncertainty. This entails rigorous environmental impact assessments, adoption of safe ecological thresholds, and adaptive management approaches that continuously monitor and adjust actions based on ecosystem feedback. For example, if a project on land-use changes presents risks of habitat fragmentation beyond safe connectivity limits, that project should be halted or redesigned even if the full scope of harm is not yet scientifically quantified (Brunnée & Hey, 1996; Sands & Peel, 2012).

To be ecologically meaningful, DNSH implementation must also be aligned with principles of ecological and species justice and intergenerational equity to ensure that harm prevention extends beyond anthropocentric impacts and encompasses the intrinsic value of nature (White, 2021). Mainstreaming ecological justice into DNSH implementation may involve mapping environmental burdens along global supply chains, including Environmental Justice Impact Assessments (EJIAs) in planning processes, empowering affected communities through participatory governance, and appointing ecosystem or species representatives (Banwell et al., 2025). Operationalizing species justice requires conservation and restoration strategies that prioritize ecological integrity, avoid species biases, and uphold the ecological roles and needs of non-human life forms. For example, offsetting biodiversity loss through multispecies tree planting complies with the DNSH principle when viewed through a multispecies justice lens as it accounts for the complex habitat needs of diverse species assemblages (Banwell et al., 2025; Celermajer et al., 2021).

Because ecological harms emerge from various actors whose collective actions adversely impact (non-) human entities, DNSH assessments should also be designed to detect and respond to multi-actor, cumulative, and transboundary ecological risks. This necessitates new forms of shared and differentiated accountability, robust ecological indicators, and institutional mandates that operate across borders and sectors as suggested by French & Kotzé (2018).

Overall, a reformed DNSH paradigm can serve as a crucial tool in the transition toward sustainability that respects planetary boundaries and species equity.

Types of ecological harm		Manifestations/Examples	Impacts
Source of harm	Extraction-based	Harm that results from destructive activities (e.g., logging, mining, overfishing, groundwater depletion)	Declines in native species, loss of genetic diversity, altered migration patterns, etc.
	Pollution-based	Harm induced by air and water pollution, soil contamination, plastic waste, etc.	Eutrophication, death of marine organisms, microplastic propagation
	Alteration-based	Harm related to activities such as genetic modification, habitat fragmentation, regulation of water courses, invasive species introduction, etc.	Biodiversity loss, altered food webs, disease transmission
Scale of impact	Local*	Harm that affects specific ecosystems or communities (e.g., deforestation in a village)	Erosion, water table disruption, local conflicts etc.
	Regional*	Harm that spans multiple ecosystems or administrative zones (e.g., large dam construction)	Biodiversity loss, pest and diseases
	Global*	Harm that affects planetary systems (e.g., climate change, ocean acidification)	Rising air temperatures, sea-level rise, extreme weather
Legal status	Illegal	Harm that violates environmental laws (e.g., poaching, illegal dumping)	Species extinction, altered migration patterns
	Legal	Harm that are lawful but relate to ecologically damaging activities (e.g., industrial emissions)	Rising air temperatures, greenhouse gases

*At local, regional and global scales, harms can result from cumulative (i.e., small actions that build up over time such as microplastics) or synergistic (i.e., multiple actions that interact to amplify the magnitude of the damage) stressors

Table 1- Description of various ecological harms

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The Do not harm principle in a transcultural perspective

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Project acronym: RE4GREEN

Introduction

The RE4GREEN project aims to provide guidance and resources to help the development of research projects and technologies in accordance with the European Green Deal and the Do No Significant Harm principle (DNSH). The European Green Deal is the EU's strategic framework for achieving climate neutrality by 2050, promoting sustainable economic growth through investments in clean energy, circular economy, and biodiversity protection. The DNSH, embedded in EU funding mechanisms (Davila, 2022), requires that supported activities (including research and innovation) must not cause significant harm to any of the six environmental objectives defined in EU taxonomy regulation (see below). These two frameworks are closely linked: while the Green Deal defines the overarching sustainability goals, the DNSH principle serves as a safeguard to ensure that progress in one area does not come at the expense of others. RE4GREEN supports researchers in aligning their work with both, ensuring environmentally responsible innovation.

The EU taxonomy regulation establishes environmental objectives outlined in Article 17 of (EU) 2020/852. These environmental objectives are:

1. *Climate change mitigation*: activities that reduce or prevent greenhouse gas emissions.
2. *Climate change adaptation*: activities that reduce vulnerability to the impacts of climate change.
3. *Sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources*: activities that contribute to the preservation of water resources and marine ecosystems.
4. *Transition to a circular economy*: activities promoting recycling, reuse, and resource efficiency.
5. *Pollution prevention and control*: activities aimed at reducing environmental pollutants.
6. *Protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems*: activities that conserve biodiversity and restore ecosystems.

In our case, the importance of the DNSH principle lies in several aspects, such as ensuring that research and innovation activities, claiming to be environmentally sustainable, are evaluated *holistically*, considering their environmental benefits and harms in a particular socio-cultural context.

However, there are several limitations to fully apply successfully this principle. Firstly, as Gupta and Schmeier (2020) pointed out, there is limited research that explores how DNSH can be effectively operationalized to anticipate, reduce, or mitigate harm. This lack of conceptual clarity raises important questions about the principle's practical enforceability, its interpretative flexibility across different contexts, especially when they are culturally diverse, and the mechanisms through which it can be monitored and evaluated. Without a deeper theoretical and empirical understanding of DNSH, there is a risk that it may be applied inconsistently or superficially, undermining its intended role as a safeguard in sustainability-oriented initiatives.

Secondly, because of the poor elaboration of the concepts of social impacts driven by environmental crises in the current regulation, the DNSH principle, as currently enacted by the EU, fails to acknowledge the actual damages caused by technological developments like nuclear plants, mining, or cloud computing, to name a few. Consequently, scientific and technological practices developed under this framework may produce harm (Bernstein et al., 2022).

Last, but not least, the concept of "harm" is usually shaped by paradigms from the Global North, which often emphasize individual rights, measurable impacts, and anthropocentric notions of well-being. However, these framing risks overlooking rich and diverse understandings of harm rooted in non-Western epistemologies, particularly those articulated through southern epistemologies (Sousa Santos, 2014) and frameworks of environmental justice (Martínez-Alier, 2002; Escobar, 2008). These perspectives emphasize relational ontologies, collective rights, and the spiritual and territorial dimensions of harm, which are central to many Indigenous and Afro-descendant communities. By failing to incorporate these worldviews, DNSH may inadvertently perpetuate epistemic injustice and limit its transformative potential. A more pluralistic and intercultural approach to defining and assessing harm is therefore essential to ensure that DNSH serves as a truly inclusive and context-sensitive principle in global sustainability governance.

In this work we aim to expand the conceptualization of the DNSH principle by incorporating these epistemologies through a transcultural exercise about how "harm" is understood in these non-Western traditions, and by paying attention to the emergence of the nature as a subject of rights in its own, a movement closely connected with the protection of local communities ways of life and indigenous rights over their territories and traditions.

This document is organized as follows: first we will address the study of the concept of harm in a culturally diverse world drawing in the Human Relation Area Files (HRAF), a world-wide database that incorporates ethnographies collected during a century and available at <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/>. Next, we will focus on the topic of nature as a subject of rights and the ILO Convention. Finally, we will reflect how to apply the lessons learned to a case study.

The concept of harm in a culturally diverse world

Tribal and Indigenous peoples'... lifestyles can offer modern societies many lessons in the management of resources in complex forest, mountain and dryland ecosystems [WCED 1987, 12] ... These communities are the repositories of vast accumulations of traditional knowledge and experience that link humanity with its ancient origins. Their disappearance is a loss for the larger society, which could learn a great deal from their traditional skills in sustainably managing very complex ecological systems. (WCED 1987, 114-15)

The concept of “harm” from a transcultural perspective involves diverse cultural, legal, and ethical systems, particularly in global governance, environmental policy, and development. In this sense, the notion of *epistemic justice* plays a substantial role, because it means that it values different ways of knowing, including subaltern voices such as Indigenous Peoples and local communities. Harm often reflects power imbalances and systems of oppression. In this vein, incorporating a transcultural lens into the DNSH principle also requires acknowledging that what constitutes “harm” is not universally defined, but rather shaped by culturally specific worldviews, historical experiences, and socio-political contexts. For Indigenous Peoples and other marginalized communities, harm may include not only environmental degradation but also the erosion of cultural identity, spiritual disconnection from ancestral territories, and the silencing of traditional knowledge systems, among others. Therefore, operationalizing DNSH in a truly inclusive way demands participatory processes that centre these voices and recognize their authority in defining what is at stake. This aligns with calls from “decolonial” scholars for a “pluriverse” of knowledges (Escobar, 2018), where multiple ways of being and knowing coexist and inform policy and governance frameworks. Without such an approach, DNSH risks reproducing the very systems of domination it seeks to mitigate.

From a cultural perspective, we can distinguish at least three major frameworks: Western, Eastern, and Indigenous/local community cosmologies. In Western traditions, harm is often conceptualized through individualistic and utilitarian lenses and is typically framed in legal and economic terms. Eastern philosophies, such as Buddhism, Taoism, and Confucianism, tend to emphasize relational and holistic understandings of harm, where the focus is on balance, harmony, and the interconnectedness of all beings. Finally, indigenous worldviews often conceptualize harm in *territorial, spiritual, and intergenerational terms*; it may involve the desecration of sacred sites, the disruption of ancestral relationships with the land, or the disruption of traditional social organization. These perspectives are grounded in *relational ontologies*, where humans are not separate from nature but part of a living web of reciprocal responsibilities (Cajete, 2000; Kimmerer, 2013).

In this vein, integrating Local Ecological Knowledge (LEK, Berks 1999) into the global sustainability concepts, offered a pathway toward more culturally inclusive and ecologically grounded sustainability governance, like the expression “Nature's Contributions to People” (NCP) popularized by the IPBES platform as alternative to the more instrumental concept of “ecosystem services” (Piccolo et al. 2022). LEK “is both cumulative and dynamic, building on experience and adapting to changes. It is an attribute of societies with historical continuity in resource use on a particular land” (Berkes, 1999, p. 8). It provides nuanced insights into human–environment relationships that are often overlooked by Western-centric frameworks. Ethnoecological research has demonstrated the value of LEK in promoting agrobiodiversity (Balee, 1994), sustainable water management (Gunnell & Krishnamurthy, 2003; Pandey, 2001), and climate adaptation (Berkes & Jolly, 2002; Pandey et al., 2004). In this context, ethnoecology has shown interest in the study of the institutions that regulate the use of natural resources (Reyes-García & Martí Sanz, 2007). Therefore, embedding LEK and ethnoecological perspectives into DNSH assessments through participatory approaches can help ensure that sustainability efforts do not inadvertently harm the very communities they aim to support, while also enriching the principle with pluralistic understandings of harm.

The Human Relation Area Files (HRAF)

We aim to contribute to expand the understanding of DNSH principle by researching the concept of harm from a transcultural perspective, drawing on the Human Relations Area Files (HRAF). This repository contains ethnographic descriptions of cultures worldwide codified following the OCM (Outline of Cultural Materials). These labels allow us to retrieve and analyse text corpora using word embedding methodologies to identify significant patterns in how different cultures conceptualize harm.

We address the formidable task of comparing texts related to “harm” from disparate cultural contexts, defining two primary cultural dimensions:

a) harm-reparation, and

b) norm–deviation.

Classic anthropological works like *Patterns of Culture* by Ruth Benedith (1913), and *Purity and Danger* from Mary Douglas (1966), among many others, argue that cultural elements are not independent but patterned and that the notions of pollution and contamination are closely related to underlying conceptions of the world, i.e., that norms, order, and purity are opposed to pollution, damage and danger. **Across the diverse human experience, rituals restore periodically purity from pollution or contamination, either material or symbolic, renewing the sacred cosmological order in a context of continuous degradation. The famous expression “dirt is matter out of place” (Douglas, 1966) tells us that pollution never appears in isolation but is related to its opposite, purity, and the world's systematic ordering and classification.**

Finally, it is worth mentioning the concept of the "Buen Vivir" (in English, *living well*, in Quechua, *sumak kawsay*, in Aymara, *suma qamaña*, in Mapudungun, *küme mongen*). It is an Andean Indigenous cosmovision that also stresses the idea that well-being is not an individual state, or something related to affluence, but to the harmonious reproduction of the set of mutual obligations between humans, non-humans and the Pachamama (Mother Earth). This notion of "*Buen Vivir*" has been explicitly incorporated into the new constitutions of Ecuador (2008) and Bolivia (2009), pioneering the path to the rights of nature movement. We will discuss this topic in the next chapter.

Data and Methods

The search was conducted in the Human Relations Area Files online (e-HRAF). The query was as follows:

(subjects: ("human effects on environment" OR "social problems") AND text:(harm* OR damag* OR injur* OR pollut* OR contamin* OR degrad* OR impair* OR loss))

After cleaning the data manually, we obtained **3,152 paragraphs from 306 cultures** covering eight world regions and nine subsistence modes. The region with the highest number of documents was North America, while the Middle East had the fewest (Table 1).

Region	N
Africa	572
Asia	684
Europe	295
Middle America and the Caribbean	197
Middle East	89
North America	893
Oceania	268
South America	154

Table a- Documents by geographical region

As for subsistence modes, the results cover nine different types according to HRAF classification. Only 7 cases had no assigned mode, with an overall balanced distribution. The highest number of documents correspond to intensive agriculturalists, while the lowest correspond to primarily hunter-gatherers.

Subsistence mode	N
Agro-pastoralists	336
Commercial economy	355
Horticulturalists	526
Hunter-gatherers	464
Intensive agriculturalists	815
Not assigned	7
Other subsistence combinations	331
Pastoralists	185
Primarily hunter-gatherers	133

Table b- Subsistence mode and documents

The selected paragraphs were subjected to deductive text analysis based on word embeddings and the Concept Mover's Distance (CMDist) metric. In this approach, we define cultural dimensions as axes formed by opposing semantic poles — i.e., harm vs. help or rule vs. deviation — and use pretrained vectors to construct semantic directions by subtracting antonym pairs.

For each binary dimension (e.g., Norm vs Deviation), we defined two anchor lists (one per pole, see Table 3). From these anchors, we derived a semantic direction by averaging the pairwise vector differences between opposite terms of the list. This direction provides an orientation signal. We then were able (i) to obtain each document's position along the direction via a cosine projection, and (ii) to measure each document's engagement with a given pole using the method Concept Mover's Distance (CMD), which computes the minimum transport cost needed to move the document's word distribution onto the pole's anchor set in the embedding space (again using cosine distance). Lower cost means stronger engagement and higher values indicate more substantial alignment. We summarize these document-level scores by culture and report internal reliability for each axis.

This type of analysis requires the use of trained word vectors. These vectors can either be generated locally or obtained from pre-trained sources. We opted for the latter approach, as recommended by Stoltz and Taylor (2021). The vectors were trained with FastText, encompassing 2 million English-language vectors in 300 dimensions, derived from Common Crawl data. Once the vectors were ready, with the aid of CMDist we computed the minimum cost to move the vocabulary of each document toward the selected pole, yielding a positive value when the text leans toward the pole of interest, and a negative value when it trends toward the opposite.

To account for the variation in the data, we developed and integrated two *additional* cultural dimensions to complement the two *main dimensions* (harm-reparation and norm-deviation, see Table 3): *Purity*, and *Gender*. The first *main* dimension aims to capture a continuum that spans from one pole, associated with *harm*, *risk*, and similar concerns, to the

other pole, which pertains to *care, support, and protection*. The second **main** dimension, which is more closely related to social cohesion and order, features one pole connected to *sanctions, norms, and rules*, while the opposite pole addresses *deviation and irregularities*. The dimensions of Purity and Gender complemented the analysis. **In particular, the purity/impurity axis is meant to capture a grammar of order/taboo (clean/unclean, contamination/purification) that is not reducible to material harm. This prevents conflating “harm” with “ritual disorder” and lets us check robustness across distinct cultural logics.** Figure 1 shows the correlation matrix between the cultural dimensions.

Harm (main dimension)	Norm (main dimension)	Purity (control)	Gender (control)
harm — help	norm — deviation	pure — impure	man — woman
damage — reparation	norms — deviations	purity — impurity	men — women
contamination — purification	sanctions — clemency	cleanliness — uncleanliness	he — she
degradation — restoration	sanction — pardon	clean — dirty	him — her
risk — order	rule — anomaly	pureness — unpure	his — hers
contaminated — clean	rules — anomalies	stainless — stain	boy — girl
erosion — conservation	regular — irregular	untainted — tainted	boys — girls
—	stable — instable	immaculate — filthy	male — female
—	—	purity — dirt	masculine — feminine
—	—	fresh — stale	—
—	—	sanitation — stain	—
PairDir*: 0.21	0.19	0.21	0.49

* PairDir measures how consistently the difference vectors of anchor pairs point in the same direction—when PairDir is high, it means those offsets are well aligned and the terms reliably define a single, coherent semantic axis. As a rule of thumb, PairDir values < 0.08 are considered weak, 0.08–0.15 marginal, 0.15–0.20 fair, and ≥ 0.20 strong (Boutyline & Johnston, 2025).

Table c- Primary cultural dimensions (left columns) and complementary ones (right columns).

The second part of the research—focused on Nature as a Subject of Rights—was carried out using the Eco Jurisprudence Monitor. Is an interactive online platform that compiles ecological jurisprudence initiatives globally as well as related resources for researchers, lawyers, policymakers, and activists. It is designed for anyone interested in the movement to advance the Rights of Nature and other Earth-centred legal frameworks that challenge anthropocentric perspectives. The goal is to strengthen protections for animals, plants, and entire ecosystems, which in turn benefits human societies (available at <https://ecojurisprudence.org/>).

Results: the management of harm across cultures

Figure 1 shows that the purity pole is positively associated with the normative pole ($\rho = 0.26$) and negatively with the harm pole ($\rho = -0.31$). This fact indicates a tendency for the

normative to be more closely linked to purity and the harmful to impurity. The masculine pole (and its feminine counterpart) has no significant association with the other poles.

Figure 1 – Correlation matrix between cultural dimensions.

To produce the cultural quadrants or profiles (see Figure 2), we crossed the two basic dimensions (Harm - reparation and Norms- deviation) and computed the median of each one. Next, we grouped the documents by cultures or peoples and computed the average within each dimension, plotting them in the corresponding quadrants. We filtered out those cultures that had fewer than five documents leaving 178 cultures in the dataset.

Case 1: Ganda (intensive agriculturalists, Eastern Africa)

“If a person fired his grass, as was customary during the dry season, and if this by accident ignited and destroyed a neighbor’s house, the man was held guilty of arson and had to make good all the damages.” (harm pole = 0.97, norm pole = 0.38, purity pole = -2.15, male pole = 0.09)

Case 2: Tarahumara (agro-pastoralists, Northern Mexico)

“The offenses so far discussed, with the exception of thefts, occur almost exclusively in the context of the tesgüinada. Property damage, however, refers exclusively to damage done by animals to growing crops or to fences. If the owner can be proved guilty the penalty is equal repayment in kind. It is understood that authorities can be called upon in such cases, but no instances of such action were reported. In three remembered cases of animal damage to fields, an informal settlement was made of an amount of corn or beans equivalent to what was lost” (harm pole = 1.39, norm pole = 0.14, purity pole = -0.56, male pole = 0.73)

In the [blue colour High normative control and Low Harm quadrant](#) (e.g. Kpelle, Southern Coast Salish), the norm proceeds pre-emptively even when the harm is low, activating ritual tribunals or strict taboos to neutralize any potential risk. We can label this quadrant as “**Preventive** management of harm”.

Case 3: Kpelle (horticulturalists, Western Africa)

“[Gbokeple is accused of taking a Saki’s lantern without permission and condemned to pay a fine].

Chief: When he pays the court fees we will drink.

Yakpaulo: Lend us the \$.50 that Saki paid, then he (Gbokpele) will replace it.

Chief: No, it has been given to me, let’s just wait. Go bring the money for the lantern.

Gbokpele: I can’t just pay that money and be happy.

First elder: You want to keep the man’s lantern for nothing? (laughs)

Chief: Do you want respect? You say you’re not satisfied. Where do you want to talk this matter so you can be satisfied?

Saki’s wife: He did not ask me for that lantern; the lantern was on the table. He took it.
Gbokpele: I asked you for it.

Saki: Nyago-Nelee was there. He did not ask for it.

Gbokpele: I asked for this lantern, and you told me not to stay long.

Saki’s wife: Nyago-Nelee’s daughter told you: “Don’t you remember the palaver you and Saki had last year? Don’t touch his lantern!” So I told him, “No, don’t touch that lantern I don’t agree that you should take it.”

Chief: What do you say Gbokpele? You can't put words to the lantern?"
(harm pole = -1.91, norm pole = 1.37, pure pole = -0.34, male pole = 0.49)

Case 4: Southern Coast Salish (hunter-gatherers, Northwest Coast and California)

"No special authority enforced the taboos on polluting the river prior to the beginning of the run. There was also no special "fish watcher" or ceremonial lookout for the beginning of the run, although everyone in any Twana community was on the alert for this event. Individual human beings did not control salmon runs, by guardian-spirit power or other means. "There is no special tama'-namis (guardian-spirit power) for salmon runs, to bring salmon; that is up to the salmon people. Some wealth powers (s'iyalt) give power to attract fish of all kinds, make them come where you live, in multitudes, but this is not power to specially make them run up the river. They could stop the run if they dirtied the river or got the salmon angry." (Harm pole = -1.84, norm pole = 1.49, pure pole = 1.14, male pole = 0.15)

In the **green colour Low normative – High harm quadrant** (e.g. Ticuna, Turks), we find high-damage scenarios *without* a coercive apparatus—magic, religious resignation, or improvised agreements—reflecting the weakness of formal structures in emergency contexts. We can label this quadrant as "**Incidental** management of harm".

Case 5: Ticuna (primarily hunter-gatherers, Amazon and Orinoco)

"Cure of epidemics. — Epidemics come from the sun, where their presence is indicated by a greenish aureole. Without the sun's desire they are carried off by the wind, which spreads them among men. On the occasion of a serious epidemic of catarrh, a certain shaman called the people together, collected the invisible pathogenic substance from each, placed it in an urn, and rendered it harmless by smoking." (Harm pole = 0.81, norm pole = -1.82, pure pole = -1.35, male pole = -0.009)

Case 6: Turks (commercial economy, Middle East)

"So it was that we grown-ups emerged from the winter with very little harm done; but the children! Ah, how the wretched children suffered! From the new-born to those a year old, not one survived. Pitiless children's disease, profiting by the cold, swept the little creatures away. Ask any villager all the same, whether it was the cold that carried them off, or whether it was Allah's will!." (Harm pole = 1.90, norm pole = -0.61, pure pole = -2.02, male pole = -0.38)

Finally, in the **purple colour Low norm – Low harm quadrant** (e.g. Woleai, Crow) we find how, in the face of moderate damage, communities rely on networks of reciprocity and flexible political agreements, relegating formal sanctions to a secondary role. We can label this quadrant as "**Cooperative** Management of Harm".

Case 7: Woleai Region (other subsistence combinations, Micronesia)

“In times of natural disaster individual lineages, subclans, or clans can turn to co-members on other islands for assistance. The tatibw`ul discussed above showed how this occurs. If the disaster is severe, it is also possible, because of the inter-island political organization, to ask for assistance on an island level and not via kin groups. Yapoig, the paramount chief (Mongalifach) of Satawal, made such a request after the 1958 typhoon. He asked Lefaioup, the Lamotrek paramount chief, for several canoe loads of ripe coconuts. Although Lamotrek had also been severely damaged by the storm, Lefaioup readily agreed to furnish the nuts and she continued to do so at intervals through 1960. Lamotrek would also have had the right to ask for similar assistance from either Satawal or Elato, but one could easily have justified this on the basis of the former island’s superior status ranking. But in any case, it is apparent that the politico-economic organization of the H`u permits islands of lower status to make such a request and does not allow Lamotrek to refuse it. In part, the tribute payments maintain this system.” (Harm pole = -1.03, norm pole = -1.14, pure pole = 0.63, male pole = 0.3)

Case 8: Crow (hunter-gatherers, Plains and Plateau)

“The reply from Washington was both foreordained and unexpected. As it happened, on September 25, 1890, two days before the 289 chiefs and headmen had met at Crow Agency to draft their petition, Congress had authorized the Indian Office to negotiate with the Crow Indians for the purchase of all their land west of Pryor Creek. While the tribe awaited a response to their petition, a commission was being appointed to meet with them in council. On November 27, a time when tribal leaders had hoped they would already be enjoying their new rations, the three new commissioners arrived at Crow Agency, ready to exchange American cash for nearly 2 million acres of the upland country in the Clarks Fork and Stillwater River valleys. Hungry, and grieving the loss of dozens of their kinsmen to disease, hundreds of families began to converge on the Little Bighorn to take part in the council.” (Harm pole = -1.41, norm pole = -0.41, pure pole = 0.02, male pole = -0.16)

This ethnographic mosaic underscores the issue that the cultural management of harm is not univocal, but varies between punishment, prevention, improvisation, and collaboration depending on the traditions and needs of each society.

Cultural profiles highlight no single model for managing harm: some cultures reinforce preventive norms, others respond with punishment once harm has already occurred, and others rely on informal or spiritual arrangements. The distribution of these logics in the HRAF corpus suggests that proximity to one pole or the other (harm vs. repair; norm vs. deviation) is not artificial, but rather a historically and socially distinct strategic response to environmental pressures. Understanding these strained cultural repertoires helps us anticipate how different societies respond to environmental or social crises and poses the challenge of articulating control and repair mechanisms that are both effective and culturally relevant. In this vein, this transcultural exercise also helps us to classify the diverse indigenous cultures into four basic types related to the management of harm and foresee the consequences of technological developments depending on the particular cultural group.

Nature as a subject of rights and the DNSH principle

Ecological awareness will arise only when we combine our rational knowledge with an intuition for the nonlinear nature of our environment. Such intuitive wisdom is characteristic of traditional, nonliterate cultures, especially of American Indian cultures, in which life was organized around a highly refined awareness of the environment.

F. Capra, *The Turning Point*

This section presents how the DNSH principle relates (in several ways) to the concept of nature. Firstly, we analyse the concept of "Harm" from a cultural, ecological and epistemic approach, then we introduce the idea of Nature as a subject of rights, along with the countries that have constitutional recognition, specific laws, judicial decisions, local laws or ordinances and proposed in the constitutional process, reflecting this perspective. We then explore how these two approaches intersect and identify their points of convergence. Secondly, we focus on ILO Convention 169 and its commonalities with the DNSH principle, particularly from the perspectives of Indigenous peoples, tribal groups, and local communities.

This research was carried out using the Eco Jurisprudence Monitor. This repository is an interactive online platform that compiles ecological jurisprudence initiatives globally as well as related resources for researchers, lawyers, policymakers, and activists. It is designed for anyone interested in the movement to advance the Rights of Nature and other Earth-centred legal frameworks that challenge anthropocentric perspectives. The goal is to strengthen protections for animals, plants, and entire ecosystems, which in turn benefits human societies (available at <https://ecojurisprudence.org/>).

The relationship between the DNSH principle and the recognition of Nature as a subject of rights lies in the convergence of two complementary approaches to environmental protection. While DNSH emerges from international sustainability frameworks—such as the EU Taxonomy Regulation—as a precautionary and technocratic tool to prevent environmental degradation, the recognition of Nature's rights stems from a more radical legal and philosophical shift that redefines the human–nature relationship. Rooted in indigenous worldviews and ecocentric legal traditions, the rights of Nature framework posits that ecosystems possess intrinsic value and legal personhood, independent of their utility to humans (Boyd, 2017; Kauffman & Martin, 2018).

In this vein, integrating the rights of Nature into DNSH assessments could enrich its normative foundation by introducing relational and ethical dimensions that go beyond harm minimization. This convergence opens the door to a more holistic and justice-oriented environmental governance, where Nature is not merely protected as a resource, but respected as a rights-bearing entity. Such integration would also align with calls for epistemic and

ecological justice, recognizing diverse legal traditions and ontologies in global sustainability efforts (de Sousa Santos, 2014; Escobar, 2018).

The approach of Nature as a subject of rights has been adopted in several countries and at different levels, such as constitutional recognition, specific laws or judicial decisions. Some of these countries are Ecuador, Bolivia, Colombia, India, New Zealand, Bangladesh, Mexico, the United States, Uganda and Chile (Figure 3). This approach recognises nature not as an object of protection, but as a legal subject with its own rights, such as the right to exist, regenerate, and maintain its vital cycles, and, in most cases, it is based on indigenous worldviews already mentioned such as *sumak kawsay* ("good living"), which promotes a relationship of reciprocity and respect with the nature.

Figure 3 – The nature of subject of rights in the World.

Case 1 - Recognized in the Constitution

Ecuador is the first and only country in the world to recognise nature as a subject of rights in its constitution of 2008¹. In its 7th chapter, "Rights of Nature", articles 71-74 elaborate several

¹ <https://www.lexis.com.ec/biblioteca/constitucion-republica-ecuador> The translation is sourced from the official English version of the Ecuadorian Constitution.

approaches to this recognition, some of them are: nature, or Pacha Mama, has the right to integral respect for its existence and for the maintenance and regeneration of its life cycles, structure, functions, and evolutionary processes; all communities, peoples, and nations can call upon public authorities to enforce the rights of nature; the State shall give incentives to natural people and legal entities and to communities to protect nature and to promote respect for all the elements comprising an ecosystem; Nature has the right to be restored (this restoration shall be independent of the obligation of the State and natural people or legal entities to compensate individuals and communities that depend on affected natural systems); The State shall apply preventive and restrictive measures on activities that might lead to the extinction of species, the destruction of ecosystems, and the permanent alteration of natural cycles; Communities, peoples, and nations shall have the right to benefit from the environment and natural wealth, enabling them to enjoy a good way of living (*buen vivir*).

Case 2 - Recognized through specific laws

In **Bolivia** in 2010, the Law "Derechos de la Madre Tierra" (the Rights of Mother Earth) was passed, recognising Mother Earth as a collective subject of public interest with specific rights. This law also focuses on the obligations and duties of the Plurinational State and society to guarantee respect for these rights. In Chapter II, "Mother Earth, definition and character", Mother Earth is defined as a dynamic living system made up of an indivisible community of all interrelated, interdependent and complementary life systems and living beings, which share a common destiny. Mother Earth is considered sacred from the worldviews of communities and peasant Indigenous peoples.

In **Mexico**, in 2021, the Congress of Oaxaca approved a constitutional amendment that explicitly recognizes the rights of nature in its state constitution. It establishes that every person within the territory has the right to live in a healthy environment and in harmony with nature, for their development, health, and well-being. In the face of potential environmental harm, state and municipal authorities, within their administrative and judicial competencies, must act in accordance with the precautionary principle. Environmental damage and degradation will result in liability for those who cause it, in accordance with the provisions of applicable laws.

On the other hand, the amendment establishes that Nature, composed of its elements, ecosystems, and biodiversity, is a collective entity that holds rights and must be respected in its entirety. The Rights of Nature in this amendment include: the preservation and protection of its constituent elements; the right to carry out its natural and vital cycles and ecological functions; the right to the full restoration of its ecological balance; and the right to legal representation. These rights must be guaranteed by the authorities of the State of Oaxaca, within the scope of their competencies.

New Zealand is a global pioneer in recognizing nature as a subject of rights, particularly through the legal concept of legal personhood for natural entities. This approach stems from both indigenous Māori worldviews and innovative legal frameworks. There have been several developments under this recognition, mainly Acts and Treaties, where places such as national parks, rivers, and others are recognized as a legal entity in their own right (e.g. Te Urewera Act, Te awa Tupua Act, the Treaty of Waitangi). The Māori resurgence has influenced New Zealand's

model, which, in turn, has inspired similar movements worldwide, including in India, Colombia, and Ecuador, where rivers and forests have also been granted legal rights.

Uganda has made significant strides in recognizing nature as a subject of rights, particularly through its 2019 National Environment Act, which marks a major legal and philosophical shift in environmental governance. In this act, Uganda recognizes the Rights of Nature. According to Article 4(1) of the Act, nature has "the right to exist, persist, maintain and regenerate its vital cycles, structure, functions and its processes in evolution". This means that ecosystems and natural entities are no longer seen merely as property or resources, but as rights-bearing entities.

Some practical implications of this act are that Nature can now be represented in court. Local communities, environmental organizations, and legal advocates can sue on behalf of rivers, forests, and other ecosystems; Indigenous and local communities are recognized as custodians of nature, aligning with traditional ecological knowledge and practices.

Other examples: recognition of the Mar Menor Lagoon as a subject of rights and foreign legal entity (Switzerland and Spain); Serbia National Rights of Rivers Law; Paris Grants Honorary Citizenship to the Seine; Porteirinha (Brazil) municipal law on the rights of the Mosquito River; Loyalty Islands New Caledonia Environmental Code recognizing rights and legal personality of certain elements of Nature.

Case 3 - Recognized through judicial decisions

Colombia is a global leader in recognizing nature as a subject of rights, with a legal framework that blends constitutional law, indigenous worldviews, and environmental justice. In 2016, Colombia's Constitutional Court issued a groundbreaking ruling (T-622/16) that recognized the Atrato River as a legal subject with rights. This was in response to a lawsuit by Afro-Colombian and Indigenous communities who denounced the river's degradation due to illegal mining and pollution. The Court declared that: the river has the right to protection, conservation, maintenance, and restoration; and that the government must act as a guardian, alongside community-appointed representatives, to ensure the river's well-being.

Colombia's approach is rooted in Biocultural Rights (a concept that links the rights of ecosystems with the cultural and spiritual rights of Indigenous and local communities), Legal Personhood (ecosystems like rivers and forests are treated as legal entities, capable of holding rights and being represented in court), and Constitutional Environmentalism (the Colombian Constitution guarantees the right to a healthy environment, which courts have interpreted to include the rights of nature itself). Again, these nominal rights do not always translate directly into environmental or cultural protection of indigenous territories.

India has taken notable steps toward recognizing nature as a subject of rights, particularly through its judiciary, although a comprehensive legislative framework is still evolving. In 2017, the Uttarakhand High Court declared the Ganga and Yamuna rivers as legal persons with rights, duties, and liabilities, similar to a human being. The court stated: "The rivers are central to the existence of half of the Indian population and must be treated as living entities". However, this ruling was later stayed by the Supreme Court of India, citing concerns over legal and administrative complications. On another hand, Indian courts have extended the idea of legal

personhood to other natural entities, such as glaciers, forests, and lakes, especially in the context of environmental degradation and climate change.

India's approach is deeply influenced by indigenous and spiritual traditions that view rivers and forests as sacred beings, and Environmental jurisprudence that seeks to balance development with ecological integrity.

Bangladesh has taken a significant step in recognizing nature as a subject of rights, particularly through a 2019 Supreme Court ruling that all 700+ rivers in the country are legal entities with the right to be protected from pollution and encroachment and that the National River Conservation Commission (NRCC) was appointed as the legal guardian of these rivers, empowered to sue on their behalf. The court emphasized that rivers are living entities essential to the survival of the nation, especially given Bangladesh's identity as the "Land of Rivers".

Other examples: Puno, Peru Regional Ordinance Establishes Lake Titicaca as a Subject of Rights; Chaco (Argentina) Court Case Recognizing Laguna Francia as Subject of Rights; Panama Supreme Court Case on Sierra Llorona Nature Reserve; Erfurt (Germany) District Court Second Ruling Recognizing the Rights of Nature; Pakistan court case D. G. Khan Cement Company Ltd. v. Government of Punjab.

Case 4 - Proposed in constitutional process

Chile has been at the forefront of a bold attempt to recognize nature as a subject of rights through its recent constitutional reform process, although the effort has faced setbacks. In 2021–2022, Chile embarked on rewriting its Pinochet-era constitution, with strong public support for environmental protections. One of the most groundbreaking proposals was to enshrine the Rights of Nature in the new constitution. The key proposals were: a citizens' initiative titled "15,000 Hearts for the Earth", backed by the Earth Law Center and Defensa Ambiental, gathered enough signatures to be formally debated by the Constitutional Convention; and the proposal called for recognizing Nature as a legal subject, with rights including the right to exist and be preserved, the right to regenerate its life cycles and ecological functions and the right to integral restoration and representation

In the draft Constitution (2022), the Article 103 stated that nature has the right to respect and protection, including the regeneration, maintenance, and restoration of its functions and processes. Despite the ambitious environmental vision, the draft constitution was rejected by voters in a national referendum in September 2022. Reasons included concerns over the document's length, complexity, and perceived radicalism, not necessarily opposition to environmental protections. The Rights of Nature are not yet enshrined in Chilean law, but the debate has significantly influenced public discourse and future legal possibilities. Environmental advocates continue to push for legal reforms that reflect ecocentric values and indigenous worldviews.

In **Finland**, on December 14, 2023, a citizens' initiative was submitted to the Finnish Parliament proposing the inclusion of basic animal rights in the Finnish Constitution, alongside human rights. Currently, the Constitution does not contain any provisions regarding animals. Fundamental rights are exclusively granted to humans, and human rights take precedence over laws designed to protect animals. Since this is a constitutional amendment, it must follow a

complex legislative process. As a result, the proposal for enshrining basic animal rights could become a reality no earlier than 2027. The constitutional proposal also states that “Although animal rights and the rights of human beings are not the same, they are equivalent in principle when weighed against each other. The aim is a balanced assessment of the interests of humans and animals. The responsibility for animals includes caring for the common living environment and respecting all sentient individuals that live there, with due regard for their fundamental rights”.

On December 14, 2023, **Ireland’s** Joint Committee on Environment and Climate Action recommended that the government move forward with a national referendum to amend the Constitution (Bunreacht na hÉireann) to include the rights of nature. This recommendation was part of the Committee’s official review of the Citizens’ Assembly on Biodiversity Loss Report, published in March 2023 and referred to the Committee for consideration. The Committee had until December 31 to respond.

In its findings, the Committee endorsed the Citizens’ Assembly’s proposal to give the Irish people the opportunity—through one or more referenda—to enshrine the rights of nature in the Constitution. Among its key recommendations, the Committee urged the government to begin preparatory steps during the current Dáil term. These steps include establishing a well-resourced expert group tasked with designing and drafting the potential referendum question(s), aimed at protecting biodiversity by recognizing the rights of nature and/or the right to a healthy environment.

Other examples: Aruba Constitutional Amendment recognizing the Rights of Nature; El Salvador proposed constitutional amendment to recognize the rights of Nature.

Case 5 - Recognized through local laws or ordinances

In the **United States**, the recognition of nature as a subject of rights is an emerging and decentralized legal movement, driven largely by local governments, Indigenous nations, and grassroots activism, rather than federal law. The key developments are: Local Ordinances and Community Bills of Rights: over 50 communities in 11 states have passed local laws recognizing the rights of ecosystems to exist, flourish, and evolve. One of the most notable examples is the Lake Erie Bill of Rights (LEBOR), passed by voters in Toledo, Ohio, in 2019. It granted Lake Erie legal personhood and the right to be free from pollution. However, it was later struck down by a federal court.

Indigenous Legal Innovations: several Native American nations, including the Ho-Chunk Nation, Ponca Nation, and Ojibwe, have adopted rights of nature laws within their sovereign legal systems. These laws often reflect traditional ecological knowledge and spiritual relationships with the land, rivers, and wildlife.

State-Level Efforts: some states have introduced legislation to recognize nature's rights, though none have yet passed comprehensive laws at the state level. The Green Party and other political movements have incorporated rights of nature into their platforms.

Other examples: Marinduque Philippines Environmental Code Recognizing the Rights of Nature; Eijsden-Margraten (Netherlands) Motion for Rights of Nature.

According to the Eco Jurisprudence Monitor database (ecojurisprudence.org), there are 684 cases across 63 countries where Indigenous peoples, local communities, civil society organizations, NGOs, politicians, and other actors have launched initiatives to recognize Nature as a subject of rights. The country with the highest number of initiatives—both approved and rejected—is the United States (180) cases, followed by Ecuador (80), and Colombia (29), among others. The number of initiatives is just an indicator of activism that may not be reflected in new nature-centered legal frameworks to address environmental challenges.

As evidenced by the cases presented, there are notable similarities -as well as points of convergence and complementarity, between the DNSH principle and the recognition of nature as a subject of rights:

Aspect	DNSH	Nature as subject of rights
Basis foundation	European and technical environmental law	Constitutional law and Indigenous worldview
Goal	Avoid significant harm to the environment	Recognize the inherent rights of nature
Approach	Preventive and evaluative	Ethical, relational, and restorative
Application	Projects funded by public funds	Constitutional and jurisprudential framework
Complementarity	May integrate broader cultural and ecological criteria	May use DNSH tools to assess impact

Table 5 – Similarities between the DNSH principle and Nature as subject of rights

DNSH and the ILO Convention 169

The intersection of environmental protection and Indigenous rights is becoming increasingly central in global governance. Two key frameworks that illustrate this convergence are the DNSH principle and the International Labour Organisation’s Convention 169 (ILO 169). Although they stem from different legal traditions -environmental law and human rights law- they share common values and reinforce each other in practice.

The ILO Convention No. 169 for Indigenous and Tribal Peoples (1989) is an International Legal Instrument that aims to recognize the aspirations of Indigenous peoples to exercise control over their own institutions, ways of life and economic development and to maintain and develop their identities, languages and religions, within the framework of the States in which they live. It requires **Free, Prior, and Informed Consent (FPIC)**, safeguards cultural integrity, and ensures that Indigenous communities participate in decisions affecting their lands and resources.

The Article 15 of this convention points out the following:

“1. The rights of the people concerned to the natural resources pertaining to their lands shall be specially safeguarded. These rights include the right of these people to participate in the use, management and conservation of these resources.

2. In cases in which the State retains the ownership of mineral or sub-surface resources or rights to other resources pertaining to lands, governments shall establish or maintain procedures through which they shall consult these peoples, with a view to ascertaining whether and to what degree their interests would be prejudiced, before undertaking or permitting any programs for the exploration or exploitation of such resources pertaining to their lands. The people concerned shall, wherever possible, participate in the benefits of such activities and shall receive fair compensation for any damage which they may sustain as a result of such activities.”

According to this, both frameworks prioritize prevention and participation:

- DNSH calls for early identification and mitigation of environmental risks.
- ILO 169 mandates that Indigenous communities be consulted before any project that might affect them is initiated.

This shared emphasis on early engagement helps prevent harm before it occurs. They also recognize the interconnectedness of environmental and cultural integrity. While the DNSH principle focuses on ecological sustainability, the ILO convention acknowledges the deep cultural and spiritual ties Indigenous Peoples have to their lands. In this sense, environmental degradation is not only ecological harm, it's also cultural harm.

Both DNSH and ILO 169 convention impose legal obligation: the DNSH requires states and corporations to exercise due diligence in preventing harm; the ILO convention ensures legal safeguards for indigenous rights, including access to justice. Together, they form a robust foundation for accountability and redress.

In the Figure 4 we present a map of the ILO Convention distribution. In green the countries that have ratified the convention and, in red, the ones that have not.

Figure 4 -- ILO Convention distribution

Challenges

There are several challenges in the convergence of the DNSH principle and the ILO Convention. First, there is the ambiguity and lack of a universally accepted definition of what is “Significant Harm”. This ambiguity:

- Allows for flexible or even self-serving interpretations by states and corporations.
- Undermines the consistency of DNSH application across jurisdictions.
- Often clashes with Indigenous worldviews, where harm includes not only physical or ecological damage but also **spiritual, cultural, and symbolic impacts** that are not always recognized in conventional environmental assessments.

Second, the gaps in the implementation of the ILO Convention. Although the ILO Convention is legally binding, its implementation is uneven and often superficial: the political will is frequently lacking, especially in countries where extractive industries are economically dominant; the institutional capacity is limited, meaning that many government agencies lack the training, resources, or cultural competence to conduct meaningful consultations; and the consultations often fail to meet the standards of Free, Prior, and Informed Consent, and are reduce to procedural formalities rather than genuine dialogue.

Third, there is a structural imbalance of power between Indigenous People and state or corporate actors. In this sense, Indigenous People often have limited access to legal, technical, and financial resources, which restricts their ability to engage on equal footing. Generally, the decision-making processes are frequently centralized and technocratic, marginalizing Indigenous voices even when consultations are held.

Forth, both DNSH principle and the ILO Convention suffer from limited enforcement capacity, meaning that the violation of the DNSH principle rarely result in concrete legal consequences, especially in international contexts. The mechanisms for redress under ILO 169 are often slow, costly, and inaccessible to affected communities. Finally, there is a general lack of independent oversight to ensure compliance with both frameworks.

In sum, the convergence of the DNSH principle and the ILO Convention represent more than just a technical alignment of environmental and human rights norms, it signals a paradigm shift in how we understand and govern sustainable development. This convergence acknowledges that environmental protection and Indigenous rights are inseparable. Ecosystems are not just physical spaces to be preserved, they are living territories imbued with cultural, spiritual, and historical meaning for Indigenous Peoples. By integrating the DNSH's emphasis on ecological integrity with ILO 169's insistence on participatory justice and cultural respect, we move toward a holistic model of sustainability.

Case Study: Market crops and DNSH among the Bassari (Senegal)

In this case study, we aim to illustrate a practical application of the typology produced by the transcultural analysis of harm in a country like Senegal, where no ILO convention or mention of nature as a subject of rights is present. In particular this case study examines the impact of introducing market-oriented crops on the Bassari culture, gender balance, and social organization. It emphasizes the importance of considering the holistic consequences—often unintended—of technological advancements that are initially perceived as beneficial (Porcuna et al., 2023, 2024).

The Bassari are an ethnic group residing in south-eastern Senegal, primarily engaged in subsistence farming, mostly dependent on rainfall. Their agricultural practices are deeply intertwined with a matrilineal kinship system, and an age-based social structure. The Bassari cultivates both traditional crops such as sorghum, Bambara groundnut, and fonio — rich in symbolic and ritual significance— and more recently crops like maize, rice, cotton, and peanuts. Traditional crops are resistant to droughts and water scarcity, whereas crops obtained from the market or NGOs are water-intensive and need chemical fertilizers to maximize their productivity. During the last decades the rainfall season became shorter, more erratic, and less reliable.

Bassari relies on customary use and access rights to land and farming, along with cooperative work. Nonetheless, increasingly, households are seeking formal recognition of land to exploit their plots on their own because of the investment in market crops and fertilizers. Following Porcuna (2023), women traditionally attended the local markets to sell grain or other vegetables but during the last decades, “there have also been several NGO- or government-based development projects promoting maize, rice, and peanut cultivation, through the provision of seeds, chemical fertilizers, and pesticides.”

Based on the cited ethnographic records, we performed a semantic analysis of the Bassari, giving a High Risk – High Norm type, but with low values in both cases. This high norm feature may explain its resilience despite the dramatic consequences of climate change and the introduction of market-oriented economies. Interestingly, the male pole is negative, and the pure pole is positive, indicating a strong matrilineal background that gives women a prominent role in society, both practical and symbolical.

Culture	norm_avg	harm_avg	pure_avg	man_avg	quadrant
Bassari	0,5704968 8	-0,0287862	1,21459742	-0,4585201	High Norm / High Harm

Table 6 – Bassari scores of cultural dimensions

Moverover, during the last decades, development projects and market dynamics have reshaped traditional seed exchange systems, impacting crop diversity and the community's social-ecological resilience. Traditional seeds circulate among the Bassari following customary rules, often embedded in matrilineal ties and neighborhood networks. Of course, these seeds are embedded in a rich corpus of Traditional Ecological Knowledge (TEK) that tells how, when, and in what circumstances women can plant the seeds, collect the crops, and consume them, reflecting the gendered division of labor. Whereas women used to manage the

production cycle of crops, the growing monetization of farming, depending on market exchanges, is changing the situation. In particular, cotton cultivation is controlled by men and diverts land and labor from traditional food crops, undermining women's control over food production and household income.

In addition, there is a decline in communal work, reciprocity practices, and traditional land management systems, so far controlled by the matrilineage. Thus, the introduction of private landholding and the commodification of agriculture has weakened cultural taboos, such as those prohibiting farming near sacred areas. Farmers now depend more on chemical pesticides (previously distributed by NGOs) and external seed sources, raising costs and risks (e.g., spurious seeds, health concerns). In sum, market crops have exacerbated inequalities between wealthier and poorer households in a way that only those with access to resources (e.g., oxen-ploughs, irrigable land, cash for inputs) can fully benefit.

This example calls for a holistic approach able to have into account not just the direct consequences of technological advances (like productive seeds) but the unintended consequences on the way of life, the social organization, the gender balance and the culture as a whole of indigenous or ethnic peoples. On our opinion these goals just can be achieved with a direct participation of communities in the policies that affect their livelihood and cultural reproduction.

Conclusions

This document addresses the main question of how the European “Do No Significant Harm” (DNSH) principle can be expanded and refined through a transcultural perspective that incorporates non-Western epistemologies, particularly Indigenous and local knowledge systems. While the DNSH principle is a core component of EU environmental governance, its current application risks being limited by technocratic, anthropocentric, and Global North-centric frameworks. As such, the report proposes that in order to be truly inclusive and effective, DNSH must be redefined through ethical pluralism, integrating alternative worldviews on what constitutes “harm.” To explore this, the report first revisits the cultural variability in definitions and management of harm using data from the Human Relations Area Files (HRAF), analyzing over 3,000 ethnographic records through semantic mapping techniques.

The study identifies four major cultural profiles in the management of harm—punitive, preventive, improvisational, and cooperative—highlighting how social regulation and reparation differ widely across societies. This analysis challenges universalist assumptions and reveals that harm is not only physical or environmental, but also spiritual, relational, and deeply rooted in cosmological and territorial values. In addition, the study shows that harm never occurs in isolation but in a complex web of cultural dimensions.

Next, drawing on the notion of “El Buen Vivir”, the study then turns to the growing legal recognition of Nature as a subject of rights in different jurisdictions. Reviewing constitutional reforms, judicial rulings, and local ordinances from countries such as Ecuador, Colombia, Bolivia, India, and Uganda, it illustrates how Indigenous worldviews that treat ecosystems as living entities can reshape environmental law. This paradigm shift aligns with and complements the objectives of DNSH by proposing a framework where Nature’s intrinsic value is acknowledged beyond its utility to humans.

The report further analyses the intersection between DNSH and ILO Convention No. 169, which safeguards the rights of Indigenous and tribal peoples over their lands and resources. The convergence of these initiatives points toward the need for participatory, culturally sensitive, and justice-oriented environmental assessments.

Finally, the case study of the Bassari people in Senegal exemplifies how market-driven development interventions —though intended to be beneficial— can have unintended harmful consequences on social organization, gender dynamics, traditional knowledge, and ecological resilience. This underlines the necessity of including affected communities in the assessment of harm, not merely as stakeholders but as epistemic sources of right and politics.

In sum, this report argues for a rethinking of the DNSH principle as an intercultural and participatory tool, capable of recognizing diverse understandings of harm and embedding them into environmental governance. Only through such pluralistic integration can DNSH fulfill its promise as a truly global safeguard for sustainability.

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The Concept of ‘Harm’ in East Asia and Its Management: Implications for DNSH

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Project acronym: RE4GREEN

Abstract

The principle of “Do No Significant Harm” (DNSH) has gained prominence within international policy frameworks, particularly in the European Union’s (EU) sustainable finance taxonomy, Horizon Europe, and more recent projects such as RE4GREEN. At its core, DNSH stipulates that endeavors—even those aimed at advancing sustainability—must avoid significantly undermining other environmental or social objectives. Yet the notion of “harm” that underpins DNSH remains rooted in predominantly Western ethical and philosophical paradigms, potentially neglecting a valuable reservoir of non-Western insights. This paper explores the concept of “harm” (and its corollaries) in East Asian philosophical, religious, and cultural traditions, with an emphasis on Confucianism, Buddhism, Daoism, and Shinto. By delineating historical evolutions in China, Japan, Korea, and Taiwan, the paper examines how these traditions articulate, manage, and mitigate harm, with special attention to ethical frameworks prioritizing communal welfare, relational ethics, and the harmonization of humanity with nature. Through a comparative lens, this study highlights how East Asian insights can enrich and refine DNSH-driven policies. Key contributions include the potential for broader conceptions of “significant” harm; emphasis on holistic well-being that integrates both human society and natural ecosystems; and dynamic, context-sensitive approaches to conflict resolution. Specific examples of policy implementation—ranging from the EU Taxonomy’s Article 17, which delineates environmental objectives, to operational stipulations within Horizon Europe—serve as critical test cases for integrating diverse philosophical standpoints. Ultimately, this paper argues that merging East Asian ethical thought with DNSH can promote more equitable, resilient, and ecologically attuned decision-making processes in global sustainability initiatives. The paper concludes by outlining a blueprint for future research and policy-making that engages in dialogue across traditions, reinforcing the necessity of collaborative international efforts in addressing complex ecological and social challenges.

I. Introduction

I.I The Concept of “Harm” and the DNSH Principle

The principle of “Do No Significant Harm” (DNSH) has emerged as a cornerstone in the European Union’s (EU) approach to sustainability and regulatory measures, signaling a transition toward a more holistic paradigm of impact assessment. Originating in part from environmental governance and social responsibility frameworks, DNSH stipulates that new legislation, financing, or project development must ensure that no major deleterious consequences befall other ecological or societal objectives (European Commission, 2020). For instance, the EU Taxonomy for sustainable finance requires that economic activities aligned with certain green objectives (e.g., climate change mitigation) must not significantly undermine other critical areas (e.g., pollution prevention or the protection of water resources). This holistic approach to risk and benefit echoes important ethical debates within the Western

philosophical canon, ranging from deontological injunctions to utilitarian cost-benefit assessments (Rawls, 1971; Singer, 1972).

Despite DNSH's recent currency in policymaking, it draws upon a legacy of legal and ethical constructs that emphasize the avoidance of undue harm as a fundamental civic and moral obligation (Kant, 1785/1996; Mill, 1859/1989). Nevertheless, the conventional framing often gravitates toward Western conceptual distinctions between individual rights and collective welfare, potentially limiting its scope in addressing more holistic or relational forms of "harm." As global environmental challenges increasingly transcend national borders and cultural boundaries, exploring alternative paradigms of harm is not merely academic, but imperative for robust policy design.

I.II The Necessity of an East Asian Perspective

While DNSH is enshrined in various EU directives, its scope and efficacy could be augmented through the infusion of East Asian philosophical and religious traditions. Confucianism, Buddhism, Daoism, and Shinto have long engaged with questions of harm and well-being, albeit within frameworks that foreground harmony among self, community, and nature (Nakamura, 1964). These traditions often encourage moral obligations that extend beyond human relationships to encompass the environment, deities, and ancestral legacies, thereby offering a more inclusive horizon for understanding the ramifications of one's actions.

This is particularly relevant given contemporary shifts in global sustainability discussions, where programmes and projects such as Horizon Europe and RE4GREEN, alongside broader climate-governance agendas, recognize the complex interdependencies of ecological and social systems. The East Asian vantage point can illuminate nuanced dynamics often overshadowed in Western discourse: for example, the Confucian emphasis on relational ethics (ren, 仁) and ritual propriety (li, 礼), the Buddhist precept of non-harming (ahimsā), the Daoist principle of wuwei (无为) which encourages minimal interference with natural processes, and the Shinto view of living in respectful communion with *kami* (神). Engaging these perspectives can serve as an integral step in refining international policy frameworks that rely heavily on discrete regulatory or legalistic notions of harm.

I.III Research Background and Objectives

This paper emerges against the backdrop of intensifying climate challenges, calls for environmental justice, and ethical considerations in technology and innovation (IPCC, 2021; 2022). As the global community grapples with existential threats—ranging from resource depletion to biodiversity loss—DNSH frameworks have the potential to provide coherent guidelines for equitable development. However, the theoretical underpinnings of "harm" remain contested, particularly as "significance" can vary by cultural context, ethical frameworks, and socio-political conditions.

The central objectives of this study are:

- To elaborate how "harm" has been conceptualized historically within East Asian traditions.
- To compare these conceptualizations with influential Western philosophical frameworks, thereby highlighting convergences, divergences, and synergies.

- To propose ways in which East Asian insights can inform and deepen the DNSH principle in contemporary policy arenas, including practical ramifications for the EU Taxonomy, RE4GREEN, and other global sustainability initiatives.
- To outline the ethical and philosophical ramifications of incorporating East Asian perspectives into DNSH, especially regarding climate justice, environmental ethics, and the intersections of technology and innovation with sustainability goals.

These objectives position the paper as both a theoretical inquiry and a policy-oriented analysis, seeking to engage academic scholarship across multiple disciplines and contribute constructively to ongoing debates in international regulatory contexts.

II. Theoretical Foundations of "Harm"

II.I Western Philosophical Views (Liberalism, Utilitarianism, Modern Environmental Movements)

In Western thought, conceptions of "harm" have often been delineated in tandem with the articulation of individual rights and freedoms. John Stuart Mill's *On Liberty* (1859/1989) famously posits the "harm principle," stating that the sole justification for societal or governmental interference in individual conduct is to prevent harm to others. Liberal political theory, following Mill, frequently locates harm in violations of autonomy or personal liberty. The emphasis is on protecting individuals from physical, psychological, or economic injury, reflecting a broader cultural focus on rights-based frameworks (Mill, 1859/1989).

It should be noted, however, that Western philosophical conceptions of "harm" have developed not only through individualistic traditions such as utilitarianism and liberalism, but also through a variety of ethical schools that emphasize community and relationality. For example, communitarianism, contractualism, virtue ethics, feminist ethics, and the ethics of care all stress the importance of collective responsibility, moral development within social contexts, and attention to interpersonal and intergenerational relationships, in addition to individual rights and utility. Furthermore, in recent years, there has been a growing trend in Western thought to move beyond anthropocentrism, as seen in environmental ethics, posthumanism, and eco-philosophy, which seek to expand ethical responsibility to the entire ecosystem. By acknowledging this diversity, the potential for dialogue and complementarity between Western and East Asian perspectives can be further enriched.

Utilitarianism, another dominant strand in Western ethics, defines harm principally in terms of suffering or a reduction of aggregate well-being (Bentham, 1789/1988; Singer, 1972). Here, the moral imperative to minimize harm is measured by the net consequences of actions for overall utility. The significance of harm is thus evaluated through cost-benefit calculations, which can, at times, relegate minority or long-term interests to lesser priority if they do not figure prominently in immediate utility calculus.

In the context of the modern environmental movement, "harm" extends beyond anthropocentric concerns to incorporate ecological well-being and the moral standing of non-

human entities. This shift resonates with the precautionary principle in environmental policy, asserting that the lack of full scientific certainty does not justify postponing measures to prevent potential harm (Rio Declaration, 1992). Within the EU, such thinking informs policies that adopt a broad definition of environmental harm, encompassing pollution, habitat destruction, and the disruption of ecosystems.

While these Western paradigms contribute robust theoretical scaffolding to DNSH, they can be critiqued for their frequent reliance on individualistic or utilitarian premises. Defining harm as discrete, measurable, and immediately relevant to human interests may overlook subtler relational or communal dimensions, as well as long-term ecological interdependencies. In contrast, many East Asian perspectives start from a relational or holistic view, wherein the demarcation between self and community — or between humanity and nature — is more permeable.

II.II Eastern Philosophical Views (Confucianism, Buddhism, Daoism, Shinto)

Confucianism

Confucian ethics orients primarily around societal and familial harmony, highlighting the virtues of *ren* (仁, benevolence), *yi* (义, righteousness), and *li* (礼, proper conduct). Harm in this tradition is not merely the infringement of rights; rather, it is the rupture of social harmony and moral relationships (Tu, 1998). In Confucius's *Analects*, the principle 「己の欲せざる所は人に施すこと勿かれ」 (“What you do not wish for yourself, do not inflict on others”) underscores the imperative to avoid causing suffering or moral deterioration in others. The measure of “harm” thus transcends physical injury to encompass ethical and relational dimensions, emphasizing the restoration of interpersonal balance through ritual propriety.

Buddhism

Buddhism introduces the doctrine of non-harm (*ahimsā*) and compassion (*karuṇā*) as universal moral imperatives (Keown, 2020; Williams, 2009). The Four Noble Truths posit that suffering (*dukkha*) originates in attachment and ignorance, and ethical practice aims to alleviate suffering for all sentient beings (Harvey, 2000). This universalistic outlook broadens the scope of harm beyond human-to-human interactions, placing equal importance on the well-being of animals and ecosystems. Mahāyāna traditions prevalent in East Asia, especially those influenced by Yogācāra and Huayan schools, stress the interdependence of all phenomena (Kang, 2025; Williams, 2009). Hence, the potential harm resulting from a single act reverberates throughout the interconnected web of existence, compelling practitioners to adopt a highly cautious approach to potentially harmful actions (Suzuki, 2002).

Daoism

Daoist philosophy, as expressed in the *Daodejing* and the *Zhuangzi*, underscores non-interference (*wuwei*, 无为) and living in accord with the Dao (道). While not prescribing a formal doctrine of harm, Daoism identifies the destructive consequences of excessive intervention or ambition. “Harm” thus emerges as a breach of natural harmony and a disturbance of the spontaneous flow of life (Ames & Hall, 2003). The Daoist sage avoids imposing rigid structures

on the world, minimizing forced or artificial interventions that might yield unintended harmful consequences. Relevance to DNSH is evident: a policy that seeks to do “good” while inadvertently causing “harm” would be discouraged in Daoist thought, which prioritizes subtlety, adaptability, and ecological sensitivity.

Shinto

Unique to Japan, Shinto venerates *kami* (神)—spirits or deities believed to reside in natural phenomena, objects, and ancestral lineages. Harm in this context might be construed as defilement (*kegare*, 穢れ) that disrupts the purity (*kiyome*, 清め) of individuals, communities, or sacred spaces (Kuroda, 1981). Shinto does not traditionally codify harm in legalistic terms; rather, it relies on ritual purification (*harai*, 禊ぎ) and communal festivals to restore balance between humans, nature, and the divine (Kasulis, 2017). When considered in relation to DNSH, Shinto offers a culturally rich perspective on preserving environmental sanctity and communal coherence, demonstrating that “harm” extends to spiritual and symbolic domains.

II.III Modernization and Globalization: Shifts in “Harm”

Throughout the 19th and 20th centuries, East Asian societies underwent rapid modernization and Westernization, often driven by colonial encounters, global market integration, and state-led industrialization programs. These processes transformed traditional conceptions of harm and introduced more individualistic or legalistic frameworks (Fairbank & Goldman, 2006). In China, Confucian norms collided with Marxist-Leninist ideologies, where harm came to be framed through class struggle and economic development priorities. Japan’s modernization in the Meiji and Taishō eras dovetailed with industrial expansion, reconfiguring communal norms and introducing Western legal codifications. Korea faced similar upheavals through Japanese colonization and post-war development, reshaping communal perspectives on what constitutes harm and how it should be rectified.

With globalization, environmental crises such as air and water pollution, deforestation, and climate change emerged as transnational harms, forcing East Asian states to integrate into international frameworks like the Kyoto Protocol or the Paris Agreement. While adopting Western regulatory regimes, governments and communities also attempted to preserve indigenous ethical traditions, forging hybrid paradigms of harm that blend Confucian relational ethics, Buddhist compassion, Daoist harmony with nature, and modern policy instruments (Kuhn, 2016).

These evolving notions of harm underscore the dynamic interplay of Eastern traditions with modern legal, scientific, and economic frameworks. This interplay holds critical lessons for DNSH, particularly in clarifying how “significance” might be socially constructed or how local cultural norms might enhance or challenge the universal applicability of regulatory measures. As we transition to a more in-depth examination of East Asia’s internal diversity in Chapter 3, it becomes evident that these traditions—far from monolithic—offer a rich tapestry of perspectives on harm that can critically inform global policy discourse.

III. Diversity of “Harm” in East Asia

III.I Historical Evolution in China (Confucian Ethics)

III.I.I Classical Confucianism: Confucius vs. Mencius & Xunzi

Classical Confucian ethics finds its clearest exposition in the *Analects*, attributed to Confucius (551–479 BCE). Within this foundational text, the notion of “harm” is integrally tied to the preservation of social harmony and moral propriety. As highlighted by the adage 「己所不欲，勿施於人」，「己の欲せざる所は人に施すこと勿かれ」 (“What you do not wish for yourself, do not inflict on others”), Confucius underscored empathy and relational integrity rather than merely prohibiting the direct infliction of injury (Tang & Yu, 2023; Wang, 2022). In effect, harm is understood as the disruption of ethical relations among family members, community members, and officials. Such disruption can arise not only from overt violence or oppression but also from subtle moral lapses—an idea aligning with the notion of “significant harm” that extends beyond physical damage.

Mencius (372–289 BCE), often regarded as the “Second Sage” of Confucianism, expands on this ethic, positing that humans have an innate moral sense—exemplified by the “heart-mind” (xin, 心)—that naturally inclines them toward benevolence (ren, 仁). From Mencius’s viewpoint, causing harm signifies suppressing or betraying one’s intrinsic moral dispositions (Berkson, 2021; Lan, 2023; Sung, 2019). This framework implies that institutional or systemic harms—such as unjust governance—are egregious not only because they inflict suffering but also because they corrode the moral fabric of both rulers and the ruled. By extension, state policies that ignore environmental degradation or social inequities fail the Confucian imperative to nurture the moral potential of all citizens.

A contrasting strand emerges in Xunzi (310–235 BCE), who contends that human nature is initially inclined toward self-interest rather than benevolence (Sung, 2012; Van Norden, 2007). Harm, in Xunzi’s view, is rooted in indulgence of these raw impulses—unrestrained desires or aggressive competition—necessitating ritual (li, 礼) and social institutions to maintain order (Hutton, 2016). In contemporary policy contexts, this perspective underscores the value of robust legal and ethical structures to prevent “harmful” behaviors that might arise from unregulated human appetites or corporate interests. Applying these insights to DNSH might involve stringent regulations or codes of conduct that constrain potentially exploitative market forces.

III.I.II Neo-Confucianism: Zhu Xi and the Song Dynasty

During the Song Dynasty (960–1279 CE), Neo-Confucian thinkers such as Zhu Xi (1130–1200) synthesized Confucian, Daoist, and Buddhist ideas, further refining conceptions of moral and natural order. Zhu Xi’s emphasis on *li* (理, universal principle) and *qi* (氣, vital force) laid a metaphysical foundation for understanding the interconnectedness of all things, including humanity and the environment (Angle, 2009). From this vantage point, harm is not merely an ethical transgression but a fracturing of the cosmic order, implicating both moral and cosmological dimensions.

Neo-Confucian governance in the Song era was partly characterized by an effort to align official policies with ethical principles. In modern parlance, one might see parallels in how “Do No Significant Harm” guidelines seek to ensure that economic or technological ventures do not violate the underlying equilibrium of ecological and social systems. That said, Neo-Confucian statecraft also had to contend with realpolitik, balancing moral ideals against military or economic pressures. This tension resonates with today’s policy discussions on reconciling growth objectives with environmental sustainability (Bai, 2020).

III.I.III Relevance to the DNSH Principle

Drawing from classical Confucian to Neo-Confucian streams, Chinese thought posits a continuum of harm that extends from the moral-spiritual to the socio-political and ecological. This perspective invites greater nuance in policy tools designed to operationalize DNSH. For instance, Article 17 of the EU Taxonomy Regulation outlines conditions where an economic activity is deemed to cause “significant harm.” An East Asian reading might question whether this definition captures intangible but potentially profound disruptions to social or moral order. Policies informed by Confucian insights could require a more holistic assessment—beyond quantifiable environmental impacts—to gauge whether a project disrupts communal harmony, cultural heritage, or ethical norms.

III.II Historical Evolution in Japan

Japan’s historical experience presents a tapestry of Shinto beliefs, successive waves of Buddhist transmission, Confucian moral-political frameworks, and modern Western influences (Kasulis, 2017). These layers have interacted dynamically, generating rich discourses on the nature of harm and how it should be addressed.

III.II.I Ancient Shinto Foundations

In ancient Japan, Shinto provided a worldview wherein *kami* (神)—sacred presences—resided in natural features like mountains, rivers, and trees (Kasulis, 2017). Harm was construed as *kegare* (穢れ), or ritual pollution, which obstructed the harmonious flow between the human and divine realms (Kuroda, 1981). Purification rituals (*harai*, 祓い) and communal festivals (*matsuri*, 祭り) served as mechanisms to remedy such disruptions. This approach highlights the collective responsibility for maintaining the sanctity of both society and environment, anticipating modern frameworks of environmental stewardship. In the context of DNSH, Shinto-inspired ethics remind us that damage to the natural world can be seen not merely as a physical or economic loss but as a spiritual desecration, meriting reverential care and swift remediation.

III.II.II Buddhism in Asuka/Nara: Prince Shōtoku, Nanto Six Schools, Gyōki Bosatsu

Buddhism entered Japan most prominently during the Asuka (c. 592–710) and Nara (710–794) periods. Prince Shōtoku (574–622) laid a foundation of governance that blended Confucian, Buddhist, and indigenous (Shintō) ideas, famously elevating harmony (*wa*, 和) as a guiding political and ethical principle (Deal, 1999). During the Nara period, the so-called “Nanto Six Schools” (南都六宗), influenced by continental Buddhist traditions, contributed diverse doctrinal perspectives on suffering and liberation. Prominent among them was the Yogācāra tradition,

which emphasized the transformation of consciousness as the key to reducing harm (Begum, 2022).

A notable figure is Gyōki (668–749), sometimes referred to as Gyōki Bosatsu (“Bodhisattva Gyōki”) for his compassionate works. Gyōki led public infrastructure projects—building bridges, roads, and irrigation networks—and also advocated for the marginalized. Here, the notion of “harm” included neglect or indifference to the poor and to the physical hardships they faced (Augustine, 2005). In contemporary parallels, DNSH policies might emphasize inclusive growth, ensuring that large-scale projects do not perpetuate inequalities or environmental burdens. Gyōki’s legacy foreshadows modern “social license to operate,” suggesting that the moral legitimacy of a project depends on holistic harm-prevention, including social welfare dimensions.

III.II.III Heian and Kamakura Buddhism: Nichiren-shū, Jōdo Shinshū, Brief Mention of Zen

Buddhism in the Heian period (794–1185) was characterized by the esoteric Shingon and Tendai schools, which integrated local beliefs and engaged in court-sponsored rituals. However, the Kamakura period (1185–1333) sparked a wave of reformist movements seeking direct salvation amid social upheaval. Two schools notable for their stance on harm and social responsibility are Nichiren-shū and Jōdo Shinshū.

Nichiren (1222–1282) preached that chanting the *Daimoku* (“Nam myōhō renge kyō”) ensures not only individual salvation but also the socio-political flourishing of the realm. Harm, in Nichiren’s view, emerges from slander of the True Dharma and moral corruption in governance. Aligning with DNSH, Nichiren’s activism underscores the moral dimension of public policy: if leaders propagate harmful ideologies or neglect ethical responsibilities, collective suffering ensues.

Jōdo Shinshū, founded by Shinran (1173–1263), emphasized reliance on Amida Buddha’s salvific vow. While seemingly more introspective, Jōdo Shinshū also produced a distinctive lineage of practitioners who saw no conflict between personal devotion and social engagement. The *Myōkōnin*—ordinary but devout adherents—demonstrated radical compassion, often performing altruistic acts at personal cost (Suzuki, 1951). Such lived practice underscores that avoiding harm is not only a matter of institutional regulation but also of personal ethical commitment.

Zen schools (e.g., Rinzai and Sōtō) burgeoned in the Kamakura period, promoting meditation (*Zazen*) and direct insight into one’s nature. Though less explicit in their theories of harm, Zen’s emphasis on no-mind (無心, *mushin*) or non-attachment (無我, *muga*) and direct awareness can be construed as a preventive mechanism against harm: by remaining acutely aware of one’s intentions and actions, a practitioner is better able to anticipate and avoid harmful outcomes (Suzuki, 1996).

III.II.IV Kenji Miyazawa’s Perspective: “世界がぜんたい幸福にならないうちは個人の幸福はあり得ない”

Stepping into the modern era, the poet and social activist Kenji Miyazawa (1896–1933) famously declared, “世界がぜんたい幸福にならないうちは個人の幸福はあり得ない,” often translated as “Until the entire world attains happiness, no individual can be truly happy.” This statement resonates powerfully with broader Buddhist ideals of universal compassion and the interdependence of

all beings (Miyazawa, 1995/1926). From a policy perspective, it implies that localized or partial solutions to harm are insufficient if structural causes remain unaddressed. DNSH could likewise benefit from such universalist, compassionate outlooks, which call for vigilant attention to unintended externalities in far-flung regions or future generations.

III.II.V *Myōkōnin and the Kō (講)*

Myōkōnin, as noted earlier, were devout Jōdo Shinshū believers renowned for their boundless empathy and simple faith (Suzuki, 1951). They often exemplified a mode of moral living that eschewed legalistic definitions of right and wrong, focusing instead on spontaneous acts of kindness. This can be instructive for contemporary DNSH frameworks, which, while governed by legal statutes, also rely on a shared moral commitment to avoid causing harm.

Daisetz Teitaro (D. T.) Suzuki (1870–1966) rose to global prominence by elucidating Zen and Shin Buddhist thought for Western audiences. His works—ranging from *Zen Buddhism, Selected Writing* (Suzuki, 1996) to *Buddha of Infinite Light* (Suzuki, 2002)—underscore that the essence of harm often lies not in external conditions alone but in the deluded mind that fails to recognize universal interconnection. Thus, to “do no harm” requires both ethical guidelines and a spiritual or existential awakening to one’s place in the universe.

Also pivotal in Japanese religious culture are the lay associations or fraternities known as *kō* (講), in which believers gather for mutual edification and ritual (Reader & Tanabe, 1998; Suzuki, 1951). These grassroots communities historically organized pilgrimages, festivals, and charitable works, often stepping in to provide social welfare at times when state support was lacking. By bridging official mandates and local action, *kō* exemplify how a collective ethic of harm avoidance and mutual aid can arise spontaneously within communities, reinforcing the importance of culturally embedded networks in modern policy implementation.

III.III Historical Evolution in Korea

Korean cultural and religious traditions reflect a synthesis of indigenous beliefs (e.g., shamanism), Confucian social structures, Buddhist spirituality, and later Christian influences. Historically, Korea has been distinguished by its strong emphasis on communal ethics and a collective sense of identity, though specific understandings of harm have evolved across eras.

III.III.I *Hongik Ingan (홍익인간)*

A foundational concept in Korean thought is *Hongik Ingan* (홍익인간), often translated as “to broadly benefit humankind.” Rooted in the legendary founding ethos of Dangun, the progenitor of the Korean people, this maxim has historically guided moral and political frameworks (Grayson, 2002). If harm is the antithesis of “broad benefit,” then preventing harm becomes not just a matter of negative prohibition but an active duty to foster societal well-being. In policy terms, *Hongik Ingan* resonates with the aspirational tone of DNSH, orienting legislation and governance toward the public good and the conscientious avoidance of detrimental effects on vulnerable populations.

III.III.II *Neo-Confucianism in the Joseon Dynasty*

During the Joseon Dynasty (1392–1897), Neo-Confucianism was institutionalized as the state ideology, shaping family structures, social ethics, and the bureaucracy (Deuchler, 1992). Public

officials were expected to exemplify moral rectitude, with the well-known notion of the “Mandate of Heaven” (천명, *cheonmyeong*) implying that a ruler who allowed harm—be it war, famine, or corruption—to befall his subjects had lost legitimacy.

The emphasis on hierarchical but reciprocal relationships (king–subject, father–son, husband–wife) entailed obligations to minimize harm across social strata. Neglecting the welfare of the populace not only constituted an ethical breach but also risked cosmic retribution, as disharmony in the human realm was believed to provoke disturbances in the natural world. While modern secular governance in South Korea no longer adheres strictly to such cosmological assumptions, vestiges of this ethos persist, reinforcing the importance of moral stewardship as a bulwark against harm.

III.III.III Donghak Movement

Donghak (Eastern Learning) emerged in nineteenth-century Korea as a syncretic socio-religious movement that wove indigenous Korean thought together with Confucian and Buddhist elements. Central to its teaching was *innaecheon*—“human is Heaven”—which affirms each person’s intrinsic divinity and thus grounds a moral commitment to human dignity, equality, and social reform (Moon, 2017). *Innaecheon* developed to *mulmulcheon Sasacheon* encompassing all things and creatures in the universe as also embedding Heaven in them, to which human beings need to respect and be in harmony (Kim & Kim, 2022). From a Donghak perspective, harm occurs whenever people are exploited, oppressed, or denied this innate worth. Such an ethic dovetails with the social-justice dimension of DNSH, implying that public policies must guard not only against environmental damage but also against labor abuses, community disempowerment, and inequality and discrimination by social strata, class, sex, age, and wealth. Consequently, a Donghak-inspired assessment would scrutinize development projects for their broader social and cultural impacts rather than limiting evaluation to ecological metrics.

III.IV Historical Evolution in Taiwan

Taiwan’s religious and philosophical landscape is a dynamic amalgamation of Chinese Confucian, Daoist, and Buddhist influences, indigenous Austronesian traditions, and the legacy of Japanese colonial rule (1895–1945), as well as modern Western elements. This pluralistic milieu has generated localized interpretations of harm and communal responsibility.

III.IV.I Early Settlement and Indigenous Practices

Taiwan’s indigenous peoples (e.g., Amis, Atayal, Paiwan) have historically maintained animistic cosmologies that imbue the land, rivers, and forests with spiritual significance. These communities often view harm as a disturbance to sacred ecological relationships, requiring collective rituals for restoration (Liu, 2021). Although modern governance structures sometimes marginalize these beliefs, they continue to offer insights for environmental stewardship, emphasizing balance rather than dominance over nature.

III.IV.II Confucian-Daoist-Buddhist Syncretism

Following waves of Han migration from the 17th century onward, Taiwan saw the development of temples that syncretized Confucian, Daoist, and Buddhist practices. The resulting “popular

religion” integrated moral teachings, ancestor veneration, and the worship of local deities or bodhisattvas. Harm in these communities was not solely about legal transgression but was also understood as an affront to communal spirits or the moral harmony sustained by ritual and mutual aid (Katz, 1987). When communities faced natural disasters or epidemics, temple networks coordinated relief efforts and spiritual intercessions, reflecting a deeply rooted ethic of harm reduction and collective well-being.

III.IV.III Modern Developments: From Martial Law to Democratic Governance

Twentieth-century Taiwan underwent Japanese colonial rule, the retreat of the Republic of China government to the island in 1949, and an extended period of martial law (1949–1987). Throughout these upheavals, religious institutions often navigated restrictive policies that curtailed their public role. In the latter half of the 20th century, however, Taiwan democratized, and new forms of religious and civil society advocacy emerged. Buddhist organizations such as *Tzu Chi* (慈濟) grew rapidly, promoting charitable works, disaster relief, and environmental protection (Madsen, 2007). Their approach frames harm not just as physical destruction but also as moral and emotional trauma requiring compassion-based intervention.

III.IV.IV Implications for DNSH

In Taiwan’s context, the concept of “harm” frequently involves both formal legal frameworks inherited from Chinese legal tradition and the lived ethical norms of a pluralistic society. This duality manifests in contemporary debates over land development, energy policy, and cross-strait relations. Drawing on Confucian familial ethics (e.g. filial piety) and Buddhist compassion, Taiwanese civil society has increasingly demanded robust environmental assessments and participatory processes that align with “do no significant harm” principles. By insisting that new infrastructure or economic ventures uphold ecological balance and social equity, Taiwan’s ongoing experiments in democratic governance offer a case study of how East Asian ethical legacies can be integrated into modern policy frameworks (Weller & Hsiao, 1998). Efforts toward such integrative frameworks have already been undertaken in Taiwan. A notable example is the signing of “A New Partnership Between the Indigenous Peoples and the Government of Taiwan” in September 1999, which formally acknowledged the concept of the “natural sovereignty” of indigenous peoples (Gao, 2004). This agreement was endorsed by Chen Shui-bian, a prominent figure of the Democratic Progressive Party. Taiwan’s endeavor to reconcile indigenous epistemologies with the structures of modern legal systems, thereby fostering a model of coexistence, constitutes a significant case worthy of scholarly attention.

IV. Managing and Mitigating “Harm” in East Asia

Building upon the diverse historical and philosophical frameworks outlined in the preceding chapter, this section investigates how East Asian societies have operationalized the management and mitigation of harm in concrete practices, policies, and institutional arrangements. From traditional communal mechanisms to modern regulatory systems, East Asia offers valuable insights into bridging moral-communal imperatives with formal governance. These approaches can inform global attempts to implement the “Do No

Significant Harm” (DNSH) principle under EU regulations and other international sustainability agendas, including RE4GREEN and Horizon Europe.

IV.I Integrating Moral Frameworks into Policy

A hallmark of East Asian harm-mitigation strategies is the tendency to embed ethical principles—often derived from Confucian, Buddhist, or Daoist thought—into formal policy or communal practice. For example, in imperial China, the concept of the “benevolent government” (仁政, *ren zheng*) served as an overarching norm, stipulating that rulers must proactively ensure the welfare of their subjects (Angle, 2009). While modern China’s governance no longer rests explicitly on Confucian doctrine, vestiges of this tradition appear in initiatives aimed at social harmony (社会和谐, *shehui hexie*), which include environmental and social obligations alongside economic development (e.g., Geis & Holt, 2009; Huang & Westman, 2021; Rošker, 2013).

In Japan, a hybrid model of moral and legal obligations emerged through the *Ritsuryō* system (codified from the 7th century onward), which fused Confucian ethics into administrative law. Contemporary legislation, such as the Basic Environment Law (1993), continues to evoke a collective responsibility for nature, encouraging local governments and citizens to collaborate in preventing pollution and ecological degradation (Ministry of the Environment, Japan, 2021). These efforts echo Shinto’s communal ethos of ritual purification (*harai*) that seeks to cleanse harm at its roots, albeit now formalized within a secular regulatory framework. Although the Basic Environment Law (1993) contains no explicit references to Shintō or Buddhist doctrines, the secondary literature—Sonoda (1998), Kalland and Asquith (1997), Tucker, & Williams (1997)—indicates that Japan’s traditional views of nature, specifically Shintō reverence for the natural world and Buddhist ideals of compassion and non-self, have indirectly shaped the statute’s guiding principles of “coexistence with nature” and “the blessings of the environment.”

Crucially, these traditions imply that harm reduction extends beyond minimal compliance; it also encompasses a moral imperative to cultivate well-being in all stakeholders. Consequently, East Asian models can complement DNSH by underscoring the ethical ethos behind precautionary measures. Rather than conceiving of harm solely in contractual or utilitarian terms, policymakers might draw upon Confucian or Buddhist understandings that a violation of communal or ecological balance is an ethical breach requiring proactive remediation, not merely the avoidance of legal penalties (Tu, 1998).

IV.II Legal and Regulatory Instruments

IV.II.I China’s Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) Regime

Contemporary China has adopted numerous legal frameworks to manage environmental harm, including the Environmental Protection Law (amended 2014) and the Environmental Impact Assessment Law (2003). The EIA Law mandates that major development projects undergo rigorous evaluation to preempt damage to ecosystems and human communities (He et al., 2012). Although often compared to Western EIA systems, China’s approach retains a collective dimension consistent with Confucian paternalism—central authorities encourage local governments and industries to prioritize the “public interest,” rather than purely economic benefits (Dang, 2018).

In principle, the EIA Law aligns with the DNSH principle by requiring prospective analyses of potential harms, albeit enforcement inconsistencies and capacity gaps persist (Zhao, 2009). Nevertheless, given China's cultural emphasis on social stability, there is an argument that EIA processes—when effectively administered—reflect an effort to avert harm not only to the biophysical environment but also to social cohesion, thus broadening the scope of “harm” beyond environmental metrics alone.

IV.II.II Japan's Precautionary and Participatory Measures

In Japan, legal instruments for harm mitigation include the Basic Environment Law (1993), the Environmental Impact Assessment Law (1997), and a host of sector-specific regulations (e.g., for air or water quality). Policy scholars note that Japan's approach integrates precautionary principles with a tradition of local consultation (Imura & Schreurs, 2005). Historically, communal networks known as *kō* (講) or other citizen groups have engaged in grassroots environmental oversight, adding a participatory dynamic that aligns with Shinto-Buddhist notions of collective responsibility (Rots, 2015). This bottom-up dimension can reinforce DNSH aims by ensuring that affected communities have a voice in designating what constitutes “significant” harm.

Furthermore, Japan's reliance on consensus-driven decision-making resonates with the relational ethics of Confucianism, wherein communal harmony is paramount. For instance, municipal authorities often convene advisory councils of residents, business leaders, and academics to review local development proposals. Although the process can be time-consuming, it reflects a cultural investment in minimizing social disruptions—a key principle in the DNSH framework as it addresses stakeholder engagement and the distribution of risks (Dollinger, 1988).

IV.II.III Korea's Framework Act on Low Carbon, Green Growth

South Korea's Framework Act on Low Carbon, Green Growth (2010) exemplifies a proactive legislative measure to minimize harm by integrating economic development with environmental stewardship (Cho et al., 2014). Drawing on the Neo-Confucian legacy of moral governance, policymakers framed climate change mitigation and renewable energy adoption as national imperatives crucial to public welfare. This Act mandates cross-ministerial cooperation and compels industries to adopt cleaner technologies.

In line with *Hongik Ingan* (홍익인간)—the ethos of maximizing public good—policymakers emphasize that unchecked climate change and environmental degradation violate the communal duty to care for vulnerable populations and future generations (Kim et al., 2020). Such a perspective dovetails with DNSH, which seeks to prevent significant environmental and social harm across multiple sectors. By specifying emission-reduction targets and green technology incentives, the Korean model advances a holistic interpretation of harm that addresses both immediate pollution and long-term climate risks.

IV.II.IV Taiwan's Democratic Innovations

Democratization in Taiwan after the late 1980s unleashed a wave of environmental activism that transformed policy. Grassroots protests and new NGOs pressured the state to strengthen environmental laws. For example, Taiwan's EPA was created in 1987 and, over the next decade,

a series of green statutes was enacted under the new democratic era. In particular, the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) Act of 1994 (modeled on NEPA) institutionalized public involvement – EIAs must be published and full public hearings held on major projects. Scholars note that these reforms were driven by civic pressure: Tang and Tang (1997) argue that democratization “promote[d] the formulation of laws and...administrative systems for environmental management” in response to popular protests. Indeed, after 1987 Taiwan saw dozens of local self-help groups and island-wide NGOs (e.g. the Taiwan Environmental Protection Union) emerge, giving communities formal channels to contest pollution.

Although Taiwan’s Constitution contains no explicit right to a healthy environment, courts have embraced environmental protection as part of fundamental rights. In interpreting the 1994 amendment that “environmental and ecological protection shall be given equal consideration with economic development,” the Constitutional Court affirmed that a sound ecosystem is “one of the important tasks of the State” and essential to citizens’ life and health . In practice then, Taiwan’s democracy has embedded environmental and social concerns into law and procedure – even as civic input plays a direct role in policy decisions (Tang & Tang, 1997; Tang & Tang, 2000; Tang, Tang & Lo, 2005; Grano, 2015).

IV.III Research Ethics, Climate Ethics, and Technology

IV.III.I Balancing Innovation and Caution

East Asian countries’ rapid tech advances – from smart-city projects to renewable energy – can indeed yield unintended side effects. In fact, technological innovations often “create as many problems as they solve,” leading to unforeseen environmental or social risks that must be managed (Li & Piachaud, 2019). Historically, Daoist and Buddhist admonitions against hubris suggest that harm often emerges when human interventions become overly assertive or fail to respect natural processes (Ames & Hall, 2003). In modern contexts, these insights underscore the ethical necessity of balancing progress with precaution, akin to DNSH protocols in EU Taxonomy (Article 17).

For instance, South Korea’s push for 5G and AI-driven solutions must grapple with data privacy concerns, energy consumption, and potential labor displacement. East Asian ethical traditions, emphasizing relational obligations and compassion, can inform technology governance structures that anticipate indirect harms—particularly those disproportionately affecting marginalized groups (Goodman, 2023). In this respect, “research ethics” extends beyond academic compliance to encompass a broader sense of socio-environmental responsibility.

IV.III.II Case Study: Japan’s Fukushima Aftermath

The Fukushima Daiichi nuclear disaster (2011) starkly illustrates the intersection of technology, governance, and harm. While nuclear energy was promoted as a clean solution to meet Japan’s power needs, unforeseen natural disasters and potential design inadequacies led to catastrophic contamination. Post-disaster analyses suggest that a failure to properly integrate precautionary principles, local knowledge, and community feedback contributed to both the initial crisis and protracted recovery issues (Funabashi & Kitazawa, 2012).

From an East Asian ethical standpoint, the disaster can be read as a violation of harmonious coexistence with nature. Reflecting on this event, many Japanese policymakers and civil

society groups have advocated for transparent risk communication, enhanced regulatory oversight, and robust disaster preparedness. These measures align with DNSH by aiming to preclude far-reaching environmental and social harm. In the context of RE4GREEN or Horizon Europe, the Fukushima experience serves as a cautionary tale for any region undertaking large-scale energy or infrastructure projects without fully accounting for the worst-case scenario.

IV.IV Community Engagement and Civil Society

Historically, East Asian communities have managed harm through collective mechanisms—rituals, fraternities (*kō*), or lay associations—which not only tackled immediate crises but also built social capital and moral cohesion (Lindsey, 2005; Haddad, 2020). Contemporary civil society actors—NGOs, religious organizations, and grassroots networks—continue this function, influencing policy and public opinion on environmental justice, climate action, and social welfare (Madsen, 2007).

Such communal participation resonates with DNSH’s emphasis on inclusivity and stakeholder engagement. While EU directives and guidelines encourage transparency and consultation in project design (European Commission, 2021), East Asian traditions can reinforce the notion that authentic dialogue with affected communities is indispensable for truly avoiding “significant harm.” Thus, whether addressing air pollution in China’s megacities or nuclear waste disposal in Japan, grassroots involvement enhances the moral and social legitimacy of policy interventions.

IV.V Policy-Level Implications for DNSH

East Asia’s track record in managing harm reveals several policy-level takeaways that could refine or expand DNSH applications:

- **Holistic Definition of “Harm”:** By interpreting harm as disruptions to social, moral, and ecological harmony, policymakers may need to adapt environmental assessments to capture intangible or long-term effects.
- **Strong Ethical Underpinnings:** Integrating Buddhist or Confucian ethics can foster a deep sense of responsibility among government officials, businesses, and citizens, reinforcing DNSH compliance as a moral, not merely legal, obligation.
- **Community-Centric Approaches:** Lessons from communal networks (e.g., *kō* in Japan, temple associations in Taiwan) and civil society movements show how grassroots engagement can substantively enhance early detection of potential harm.
- **Adaptive Regulations:** Drawing on Daoist notions of flexibility, regulators might benefit from adopting adaptive management strategies—adjusting rules as conditions change, thereby preempting unintended harm.
- **Long-Term Vision:** Echoing Kenji Miyazawa’s insistence that no one can be truly happy unless the entire world is happy, East Asian ethics remind policymakers to adopt long-range perspectives that transcend immediate fiscal or political cycles.

When incorporated into DNSH frameworks—particularly in contexts like the EU Taxonomy, RE4GREEN, or Horizon Europe—these insights can strengthen environmental and social

safeguards. They also highlight the value of cultural diversity in shaping policies that resonate with local populations while advancing universal sustainability goals.

V. Determining “Significance” in “Harm”

The concept of “harm” in the DNSH principle raises the question of **significance**: which types or degrees of harm are deemed sufficiently grave to trigger preventive or mitigative interventions? Western legal and policy frameworks often approach the question of “significant harm” through quantitative thresholds—such as emissions caps, risk assessment models, or cost-benefit analyses (Leonelli, 2021). However, as the preceding chapters indicate, East Asian philosophical, religious, and cultural traditions underscore additional parameters that render “harm” significant, including communal well-being, moral cohesion, and spiritual or cosmological disturbances. This chapter explores how the determination of “significance” might be broadened through East Asian insights, thereby refining the DNSH principle for global sustainability and climate ethics.

V.I From Thresholds to Relational Evaluations

In many contemporary policy frameworks, “significance” is tied to measurable impacts: for instance, an activity is considered harmful if it surpasses a given pollution limit or yields negative outcomes exceeding a permissible margin (European Commission, 2020). Yet East Asian paradigms—rooted in Confucian relational ethics, Buddhist compassion, and Shinto cosmology—point to forms of harm that may not be captured by purely quantitative indices.

- **Moral-Communal Rupture:** Confucian texts emphasize social harmony (和) and benevolence (仁) as foundational values. A “significant harm” could thus include the breakdown of trust within a community—an intangible yet powerful indicator that standard environmental or economic metrics rarely account for (Shahab et al., 2025; Tan, 2023; Wee, 2011).
- **Spiritual Disruption:** In Shinto, harm can manifest as *kegare* (穢れ), a spiritual pollution that estranges humans from the *kami* (神). While not measurable through conventional data, such disruption may hold profound implications for communal identity, cultural integrity, and environmental stewardship (Kuroda, 1981).
- **Long-Term Ecological Interdependence:** Buddhism and Daoism emphasize the subtle, interwoven nature of all phenomena. A small perturbation may yield disproportionate harm over time due to relational interdependencies (Suzuki, 2002). Consequently, a minor increase in greenhouse gas emissions could become “significant” once it is contextualized within broader planetary feedback loops.

In practice, broadening “significance” to include relational, moral, and spiritual dimensions calls for more integrative appraisal models. Such models could incorporate stakeholder perceptions, sociocultural values, and ecological connectivity, ensuring that policy decisions account for both tangible and intangible harms.

V.II Cultural Variability in Defining “Significance”

A critical challenge for DNSH is reconciling culturally divergent notions of what constitutes “significant” harm. In diverse East Asian societies—where Confucian ethics coexist with Buddhist, Daoist, Shinto, and indigenous frameworks—multiple lenses for evaluating harm can

coexist within the same jurisdiction (Liang, 2024). This pluralism necessitates context-sensitive policymaking.

- **Contextual Dialogues:** East Asian traditions often employ consensus-building through communal gatherings, advisory councils, or ritual practices. Engaging such forums during impact assessments could help define thresholds of harm that align with local moral sentiments (Bodde & Morris, 1967).
- **Dynamic Adaptation:** Daoist principles of *wuwei* (无为, non-action) and spontaneity encourage flexible responses to evolving conditions. Rather than relying on static criteria for “significance,” regulators might adopt adaptive frameworks that evolve with new data, shifting community priorities, or emergent ecological stressors (Ames & Hall, 2003).
- **Spiritual-Cultural Safeguards:** In Japan and Taiwan, local temples or shrine networks often act as protectors of ecological sanctuaries or culturally sacred sites (Funahashi & Shibata, 2023; Shih, 2012; Weller, 2011). Environmental impact assessments, therefore, might need to engage spiritual leaders who can articulate forms of harm invisible to conventional analytics.

By embracing these culturally informed processes, DNSH can more accurately reflect the lived realities and ethical frameworks of affected populations. This ensures that “significance” is neither imposed externally nor evaluated solely by quantitative data, but rather emerges from multi-layered consultations that balance local wisdom with scientific expertise.

V.III Policy Comparisons: EU Taxonomy and East Asian Legal Traditions

Under the EU Taxonomy Regulation, an activity is said to “significantly harm” an environmental objective if it violates one or more sustainability pillars (European Commission, 2020). Although sufficiently comprehensive in its environmental scope—covering climate mitigation, adaptation, water management, circular economy, pollution prevention, and biodiversity—it may give less explicit weight to cultural or relational harms. By contrast, certain East Asian regulations echo more holistic perspectives:

- **China’s Ecological Civilization Initiative:** China’s leadership has increasingly referred to “ecological civilization” (*shengtai wenming*, 生态文明) as a guiding principle, implying that “significant harm” extends to any disruption of systemic ecological equilibrium and social stability (Hansen & Liu, 2018).
- **Japan’s Basic Environment Law (1993):** While not explicitly labeled “DNSH,” this article commits the nation to “comprehensive and systematic measures” for environmental conservation, hinting at a broad interpretation of harm that may include intangible cultural elements (Ministry of the Environment, Japan, 2021).
- **Korea’s Constitution and Green Growth Acts:** South Korea’s constitutional framework underscores the welfare of the people and the duty of the state to protect it, potentially classifying a wide array of environmental and social impacts as legally and morally significant (Deuchler, 1992; Kook, 2014).
- **Taiwan’s Environmental Impact Assessment Act (1994):** Taiwan’s EIA law mandates public participation, offering a forum in which local or indigenous interpretations of harm can be

voiced. This participatory mechanism can reveal cultural factors that would otherwise remain overlooked (Ho, 2019).

A key insight here is that East Asian legal instruments, while diverse, exhibit a recurring emphasis on social harmony and collective well-being. For DNSH, adopting or adapting similar provisions might mean incorporating broader sociocultural impact studies, mandatory consultation with indigenous groups, and an extended timeline for public debate before final decisions are made.

V.IV Significance Through the Lens of Future Generations

East Asian philosophies often emphasize the continuity of past, present, and future—a perspective embodied in Confucian ancestor veneration, Buddhist concern for karmic consequences, and Shinto genealogical ties (Callicott & Ames, 1989). This long-term orientation enlarges the temporal scope of what might be deemed “significant harm”:

- **Intergenerational Ethics:** From a Confucian standpoint, today’s leaders owe a debt to past generations and have obligations to secure the well-being of descendants (Bell & Hahm, 2003). Such moral reasoning suggests that policies cannot discount cumulative effects on future societies.
- **Karmic Accumulation:** Buddhist doctrines highlight how actions produce karmic results that may manifest well beyond one’s current lifespan (Harvey, 2000). Ecologically, this echoes scientific warnings about tipping points and irreversible damage. A “significant” harm might be one that sets off negative environmental cascades persisting across generations.
- **Shinto’s Lineage Continuity:** In Shinto tradition, natural features and ancestral spirits are intertwined with communal identity. Significant harm thus includes ecological destructions that break the chain of reverential connection and deprive future generations of their spiritual heritage (Kuroda, 1981).

In the context of DNSH, these notions encourage robust “long-term thinking” mechanisms. Policymakers could formalize intergenerational impact assessments or require scenario planning that spans multiple decades. By evaluating the potential harm to future communities—even if such harm is not immediately measurable—governments and stakeholders can align more closely with East Asian ethical sensibilities.

V.V Measuring the Unmeasurable: Toward a Composite Metric of Harm

The challenge remains: how can intangible or relational harms be systematically incorporated into policy assessments? Scholars and practitioners have proposed multi-dimensional frameworks that combine quantitative and qualitative indicators:

- **Social Impact and Cohesion Indices:** Surveys of community trust, social capital, and levels of conflict can serve as proxies for communal harmony.
- **Cultural Heritage Indicators:** Inventories of sacred sites, local customs, and intangible cultural practices can inform environmental impact statements, ensuring protection against symbolic or spiritual harm (Ashrafi et al., 2022; Page, 2017).

- **Adaptive Capacity Wheel:** Building on Daoist principles, this framework assesses a system's capacity to respond flexibly to unforeseen challenges, capturing how quickly institutions can mitigate emerging forms of harm (Gupta et al., 2010; Miller, 2017).
- **Long-Term Ecological Monitoring:** Data on biodiversity, soil health, and water quality collected over extended periods can reveal slow-moving changes that might become significant if left unchecked (Holling & Gunderson, 2002).

The incorporation of these metrics would require cross-sectoral collaboration—among policymakers, local communities, scholars, and civil society. Although such complexity introduces logistical difficulties, it offers a more accurate depiction of “significance,” reflecting both the cultural depth of East Asian philosophies and the rigorous data-driven approach valued in global governance.

As Bernstein et al. (2023) argue, “Matters of harm and their significance are questions that emerge at the intersections of social, technical, political, and environmental concerns of a multitude of actors. As such, matters of significant harm invite high levels of imprecision and ambiguity or uncertainty; states that will all change over time.” This perspective highlights the necessity of moving beyond purely technical or quantitative approaches to harm assessment, and instead adopting more relational and context-sensitive frameworks.

V.VI Conclusion: Expanding the Lens of “Significance”

Determining “significance” in “harm” demands a blend of objective measurement and culturally grounded moral judgment. As shown throughout this chapter, East Asian traditions offer a relational, long-term, and often spiritual lens for evaluating how substantial an impact must be to trigger concern or remediation. Integrating these perspectives with Western policy frameworks under DNSH could lead to more inclusive, equitable, and future-oriented outcomes.

Rather than conceptualizing significance as a binary threshold, a more nuanced approach—enriched by Confucian emphasis on relational ethics, Buddhist compassion for all sentient beings, Shinto reverence for the sacred natural world, and Daoist caution against overreach—can deepen global sustainability frameworks. This expansion not only aligns with the ethical plurality of our interconnected world but also resonates with the pressing need for holistic responses to environmental and social crises.

In the subsequent chapter, we will synthesize these insights and propose specific ways in which East Asian philosophies might shape or refine the DNSH principle in practice, offering a blueprint for collaborative policymaking that transcends cultural boundaries.

VI. Insights from an East Asian Perspective on DNSH

East Asian philosophical and religious traditions provide rich conceptual resources that, if integrated into contemporary sustainability governance, could both broaden and deepen the implementation of the “Do No Significant Harm” (DNSH) principle. As discussed throughout this paper, DNSH as articulated in the European Union (EU) Taxonomy Regulation—particularly in Articles 9 and 17, which outline environmental objectives and define “significant

harm,” respectively—serves as an overarching mechanism ensuring that economic activities labeled “sustainable” do not undermine ecological or social goals (European Commission, 2020). Meanwhile, complementary programme and project contexts such as Horizon Europe and RE4GREEN bring DNSH considerations into research, innovation, and technology deployment. This chapter synthesizes how East Asian modes of thought might shape or refine these frameworks, offering fresh perspectives on climate ethics, environmental justice, and the interplay between ecology, technology, and innovation.

VI.I The Relational and Communal Ethos in DNSH

A key insight from East Asian traditions—whether derived from Confucian relational ethics, Buddhist compassion, or Shinto communal rites—is that “harm” cannot be understood in purely individualistic terms. Instead, social and ecological well-being emerges from a web of interdependence, and disruptions often reverberate beyond the immediately affected parties. This interconnected worldview resonates with the EU Taxonomy’s principle that an activity contributing to one environmental objective (e.g., climate change mitigation) must not significantly harm another objective (e.g., water and marine resources protection). Yet East Asian perspectives suggest an even broader relational scope:

- **Holistic Assessments:** Instead of restricting DNSH assessments to measurable biophysical or economic parameters, a relational ethos invites considerations of cultural integrity, social cohesion, and generational continuity. For example, policy reviews might include community consultations rooted in Confucian respect for local elders or Buddhist compassion for marginalized stakeholders. When evaluating a new waste-management facility under Horizon Europe guidelines, decision-makers could incorporate intangible elements—such as communal trust, spiritual significance of land, and historical usage patterns—in determining whether the project causes “significant” harm.
- **Community-Based Models:** East Asian communal networks—exemplified by the *kō* (講) in Japan or temple associations in Taiwan—demonstrate that grassroots participation can play a decisive role in identifying and forestalling harm (Reader & Tanabe, 1998; Ho, 2005). Where the EU’s delegated acts under the Taxonomy Regulation require stakeholder engagement, these East Asian models illustrate how such engagement can be deeply integrated into the moral and cultural fabric of local societies. Rather than treating stakeholder input as a formal requirement, these traditions suggest that ongoing dialogue is indispensable for maintaining harmony. This continuous consultative process can be integrated into EU-funded research and innovation projects, including Horizon Europe projects such as RE4GREEN, ensuring that local communities help shape environmental and technological initiatives in real time.
- **Moral Accountability for Institutions:** Traditional Confucian governance demanded high standards of moral rectitude from rulers, given that breaches of benevolent governance led to social discord. Analogously, the DNSH principle can be reinforced by emphasizing the moral accountability of corporations and state agencies. Whether funding comes from Horizon Europe or successor frameworks, adopting an ethos of Confucian paternalism—where leaders see themselves as stewards of both people and nature—could elevate corporate social responsibility from a legal necessity to a moral imperative.

VI.II Expanding Temporal Horizons and Intergenerational Ethics

Climate change and environmental degradation are quintessential long-term challenges, often inflicting harms on future generations who have no immediate say in current policy decisions. East Asian philosophies have long grappled with the moral duty owed to descendants—through Confucian ancestor veneration, Buddhist notions of karmic consequences, Shinto’s worldview, and so on. This extended temporal lens offers concrete insights for DNSH:

- **Integrating Future Generations in Policy:** Article 17 of the EU Taxonomy Regulation describes “significant harm” to future sustainability objectives, but it does not explicitly detail how to weigh intergenerational impacts. East Asian perspectives emphasize the continuity between past, present, and future communities (Bell & Hahm, 2003). Incorporating this viewpoint, DNSH protocols could require scenario planning over multiple decades or centuries, assessing whether today’s development might yield harm that cascades through future generations. For instance, large-scale infrastructure supported under broader EU public funding instruments might be evaluated for its potential to saddle future societies with unmanageable costs or environmental risks.
- **Fiduciary Responsibility and Climate Ethics:** Confucian tradition envisions rulers (or leaders) as trustees of the public good, responsible for ensuring that future subjects inherit a stable, flourishing realm. By analogy, corporate boards or research consortia receiving Horizon Europe funding might adopt a similar fiduciary ethic toward long-term environmental stewardship. This ethic would complement existing EU guidelines on sustainability, reinforcing the moral and existential weight of intergenerational harm.
- **Karmic Perspectives on Innovation:** Though karmic doctrine is not typically invoked in secular policy, it underscores how even minor actions can accumulate profound effects over time (Harvey, 2000). Translated into climate ethics, this principle warns that seemingly negligible emissions or pollution incidents can, in aggregate, contribute to severe global tipping points. The DNSH principle might draw upon karmic logic to caution against incremental harm, urging strict precaution even when immediate negative outcomes appear small.

VI.III Confronting Technological and Environmental Complexities

The EU’s DNSH principle is especially relevant in the context of emerging technologies and large-scale infrastructure projects. Horizon Europe and related programs emphasize innovation for climate resilience and environmental sustainability, yet advanced technologies also harbor risks of unintended harm—whether through energy-intensive data centers or disruptions to labor markets. Here, East Asian traditions offer cautionary tales and adaptive strategies:

- **Daoist Minimalism and Technology:** Daoist teachings on *wuwei* (无为) highlight non-forcible, harmonizing action rather than overreach (Ames & Hall, 2003). Applied to technology policy, this ethic advises humility and restraint, urging that new technologies be introduced only after thorough impact assessments. In the framework of DNSH, a “Daoist lens” might encourage incremental, carefully monitored tech rollouts, ensuring that robust safeguards are in place before widespread deployment. For instance, if Horizon Europe funds an AI-driven agricultural

system, Daoist caution might demand pilot projects and community consultations, mitigating potentially disruptive economic or social harm.

- **Buddhist Compassion and Climate Justice:** The principle of compassion in Mahāyāna Buddhism underscores the interconnectedness of all beings, advocating for equitable distribution of risks and benefits (Harvey, 2000). When implementing DNSH in climate-related investments, policymakers could prioritize strategies that shield disadvantaged populations from disproportionate harm—a stance echoing climate justice concerns. For example, it might be required that renewable energy projects in developing regions guarantee local employment, capacity-building, and pollution reduction. This approach aligns with the Buddhist impulse to minimize suffering, ensuring that “harm” is not offloaded onto vulnerable communities.
- **Shinto Reverence for Nature and Environmental Integrity:** Shinto traditions affirm that natural sites embody living *kami*, demanding respect and careful stewardship (Kuroda, 1981). In a DNSH context, this perspective heightens sensitivity to landscape transformations—such as deforestation, wetland draining, or the destruction of sacred sites. Policy measures under the EU Taxonomy might include specialized cultural-environmental assessments that consider not only biodiversity loss but also the spiritual or cultural significance of ecologically critical areas. By requiring developers to consult local religious or cultural institutions—mirroring Shinto communal rites—DNSH compliance could be broadened to account for intangible yet deeply felt forms of harm.

VI.IV Practical Mechanisms for Policy Integration

Translating East Asian insights into concrete policy mechanisms can strengthen DNSH’s global applicability. Below are four proposals:

1. **Supplementary Guidelines and Localized Indicators:** Within the EU Taxonomy’s delegated acts, regulators could introduce supplementary guidelines that reflect East Asian relational and spiritual perspectives. These might include localized indicators—for instance, measuring changes in community trust (reflective of Confucian harmony) or gauging intangible cultural assets (aligned with Shinto purification ideals). Such indicators would align with existing social impact assessment protocols while capturing the nuance of East Asian harm conceptions.
2. **Multi-Stakeholder Panels with Ethical Experts:** Horizon Europe projects could establish multi-stakeholder panels that include not only environmental scientists and economists but also scholars of East Asian ethics or representatives from relevant cultural traditions. These panels would evaluate potential harms through a broader lens, ensuring that intangible and long-term consequences are well understood. By embedding “cultural-ethical experts,” policymakers would operationalize a truly holistic DNSH approach.
3. **Cultural Heritage Safeguarding Clauses:** Regulation (EU) No 1291/2013 establishing Horizon 2020 frames cultural heritage as an important research and innovation priority (European Parliament and Council, 2013), but it does not explicitly mandate avoiding harm to cultural heritage. Similarly, the EU Taxonomy introduces broad “do no significant harm” provisions that, while not explicitly referencing cultural heritage, could conceptually extend to safeguarding cultural sites and traditions. These existing provisions could be further strengthened by drawing on Shinto, Confucian, and Buddhist notions of reverence for sacred sites and spiritually significant traditions.
4. **Adaptive Management Protocols:** Reflecting Daoist fluidity, DNSH could benefit from adaptive management protocols that allow for iterative revisions based on new data,

community feedback, or unforeseen challenges. This approach resonates with East Asian philosophies, which favor responsive governance and continuous dialogue over rigid regulations (Ames & Hall, 2003). If, for example, a renewable energy infrastructure project begins to exhibit unanticipated ecological or social harms, adaptive management clauses would require prompt mitigation or redesign rather than waiting for the harm to become entrenched.

Bernstein et al. (2023) propose a "situated approach" to DNSH, which "would start by taking a broad gaze with regards to determining relevant temporalities, geographies, and species potentially harmed, and take-seriously the need for a plurality of perspectives when making these judgements." Such an approach can enrich the legitimacy and effectiveness of harm assessment in research and innovation policy.

VI.V Implications for Environmental and Climate Justice

Concerns about environmental justice, climate justice, and the equitable distribution of technological benefits are integral to modern ethical debates on sustainability (Schlosberg, 2013; Sovacool, & Dworkin, 2015). East Asian moral traditions, with their emphasis on community, harmony, and compassion, amplify these concerns in several ways:

- **Equitable Burden-Sharing:** From the Confucian perspective, a ruler—or by extension, a government—bears moral responsibility for ensuring that burdens do not fall unfairly on the less powerful (Bell & Hahn, 2003). This resonates with global calls for climate justice, wherein wealthier nations must assume a proportionally larger role in mitigating harm. DNSH assessments in cross-border contexts (e.g., supply chains for critical raw materials) could adopt a Confucian lens, mandating that multinational corporations address the social costs inflicted on distant communities.
- **Collective Well-Being as a Core Objective:** The Buddhist adage of seeking collective liberation from suffering parallels the notion of environmental justice, wherein systemic inequalities—such as disproportionate exposure to pollution—constitute significant harm. Implementing DNSH would entail mapping vulnerable populations and tailoring interventions to safeguard them first. In so doing, the principle of “Do No Significant Harm” becomes not merely about avoiding negative outcomes but proactively about securing justice and well-being for all.
- **Technological Innovation with Empathy:** Emerging green technologies should be pursued with mindfulness and compassion. Buddhist ethics, for example, stress compassion and non-harm toward all beings in an interconnected world – a perspective that urges innovators to anticipate and prevent downstream harm to ecosystems and communities (Capper, 2024). Daoist principles of harmony and *wuwei* (non-action) similarly counsel caution, reinforcing that innovation is not an end in itself but must align with ethical harmony with nature. The DNSH stipulations already embed precaution, but East Asian ethics reinforce the moral impetus behind that precaution.

VI.VI Conclusion: Toward a Global, Pluralistic DNSH

The DNSH principle is most effective when it acknowledges diverse cultural and ethical standpoints. East Asia’s heritage—shaped by Confucian relational ethics, Buddhist compassion, Daoist harmony, and Shinto reverence—pushes policymakers to consider broader and deeper dimensions of harm. In doing so, it strengthens and complements the EU

Taxonomy, Horizon Europe, and RE4GREEN, particularly in addressing the pressing imperatives of climate ethics, environmental justice, and responsible innovation.

By embedding East Asian insights into DNSH, international policymakers can move beyond a narrow, checklist-driven paradigm toward a genuinely pluralistic, context-sensitive, and future-oriented sustainability governance. Such an evolution would not only honor the moral and spiritual dimensions of environmental stewardship but also foster cross-cultural solidarity in confronting existential challenges like climate change and biodiversity loss. In the upcoming conclusion, we distill the paper's overarching argument and reaffirm the call for collaborative policy innovation, blending Western and East Asian traditions for a more harmonious and equitable global future.

VII. Conclusion

This paper has examined the concept of “harm” in East Asia from philosophical, religious, and cultural standpoints, exploring how these perspectives might illuminate and enrich the European Union’s “Do No Significant Harm” (DNSH) principle. The central argument is that East Asian traditions—rooted in Confucian relational ethics, Buddhist compassion and interdependence, Daoist non-intrusiveness, and Shinto reverence for nature—provide nuanced frameworks that extend beyond purely individualistic or quantitatively driven notions of harm. Their shared emphasis on communal well-being, intergenerational responsibility, moral obligation, and long-term ecological harmony resonates strongly with the ambitions of DNSH, particularly when applied to global challenges in climate ethics, environmental justice, and sustainable innovation.

VII.I Key Contributions of East Asian Philosophical Traditions

Relational Understanding of Harm

A recurrent theme in Confucian, Buddhist, and Shinto thought is the primacy of relationships—whether among humans, between humanity and nature, or across ancestral lineages. As such, harm is rarely construed as a discrete violation of individual rights alone. Instead, it signifies a disruption of moral, social, and ecological harmony. DNSH implementations may benefit from this relational orientation by broadening assessments of “significant harm” to include intangible but serious disruptions to social cohesion, cultural heritage, or spiritual reverence for nature.

Long-Term and Intergenerational Focus

East Asian worldviews frequently emphasize responsibilities to ancestors and to future generations. Confucian frameworks stress the moral duty of leadership to foster enduring welfare, while Buddhist perspectives highlight karmic accumulations that unfold over extended timescales. These orientations dovetail with the DNA of DNSH, which aspires to protect both present and future ecological systems from untenable burdens. Embedding intergenerational ethics into regulatory language—and concretely into measures like the EU Taxonomy’s Article 17—would recognize harms that may only become “significant” after decades or centuries.

Holistic and Adaptive Governance

Daoist teachings, in particular, advocate a flexible approach to governance, whereby policies evolve in concert with unfolding conditions and natural rhythms. Applied to DNSH, this suggests adaptive management frameworks that allow for constant monitoring, community consultation, and course-correction in response to emergent harm. Such iterative governance is increasingly critical in tackling complex, unpredictable climate challenges.

VII.II Policy-Level Synthesis

Strengthening Stakeholder Engagement

The communal ethos at the heart of East Asian ethics implies that stakeholder consultations should be ongoing, substantive, and culturally informed. Projects under Horizon Europe, RE4GREEN, or other international sustainability initiatives could incorporate East Asian models of consensus-building, ensuring that local communities shape the metrics by which harm is identified and measured.

Integrating Moral and Spiritual Dimensions

Although environmental and social impact assessments often emphasize tangible criteria—such as emissions or water usage—East Asian perspectives highlight the salience of spiritual, ritual, and moral disruptions. For instance, in contexts where natural sites hold sacred significance, developers and regulators should explicitly consider the spiritual repercussions of their interventions. This ensures that DNSH processes align more closely with local cultural realities and avoid forms of harm that are otherwise overlooked by conventional assessments.

Codifying Broader Harm Criteria

Incorporating East Asian ideas could lead policymakers to codify broader criteria for “significance” in relevant legal instruments. Such criteria might address not only damage to biodiversity and human health but also risks to cultural continuity, communal trust, and moral rectitude. While operationalizing these intangible values can be challenging, multi-disciplinary methodologies—from qualitative stakeholder interviews to long-term ethnographic monitoring—can help capture them.

VII.III Future Directions and Collaborative Potential

East Asian traditions not only offer philosophical insights but also manifest in real-world policies. China’s evolving ecological civilization programs, Japan’s emphasis on precautionary and participatory environmental governance, Korea’s constitutionally grounded green growth strategy, and Taiwan’s community-driven approach to impact assessments all illustrate how a relational, long-term view of harm can be operationalized. The cross-fertilization of these approaches with EU frameworks like DNSH could yield inventive strategies for addressing global crises such as climate change, pollution, and biodiversity loss.

Looking ahead, deeper engagement between East Asian and Western policy communities could nurture:

- **Cross-Cultural Policy Exchanges:** Workshops or joint research initiatives that bring together experts in Confucian, Buddhist, Shinto, and Daoist ethics with EU policymakers and

environmental scientists.

- **Multi-Level Governance Mechanisms:** Collaborative governance models that blend top-down policy directives (e.g., the EU Taxonomy) with grassroots, community-based management techniques (e.g., local religious or civic networks).
- **Refined Ethical Frameworks for Technology and Innovation:** Guidelines for emerging technologies—ranging from AI to renewable energy systems—that incorporate relational ethics and consider the karmic “ripple effects” of seemingly marginal interventions.

VII.IV Concluding Reflections

The DNSH principle stands as a testament to the EU’s commitment to holistic sustainability—an approach that refuses to sacrifice certain ecological or social objectives in pursuit of others. By weaving in East Asian perspectives on harm, policymakers, corporate leaders, and civil society advocates can bolster this commitment with a relational, deeply moral, and intergenerational dimension. Whether through Confucius’s mandate to avoid inflicting upon others what one would not desire oneself, the Buddhist ethic of universal compassion, the Daoist model of ecological synergy, or Shinto reverence for the divine in nature, East Asia’s intellectual legacy underscores that harm extends beyond immediate physical damages. It can undermine communal harmony, spiritual purity, and the unbroken chain of life that weaves past, present, and future together.

In short, the confluence of East Asian ethical traditions with Western sustainability frameworks heralds a more inclusive and robust understanding of what it means to “do no significant harm.” It calls for moral, cultural, and ecological vigilance. It challenges policymakers to account for not only the quantifiable but also the immeasurable. And it envisions a world in which humanity’s technological and economic strides proceed hand in hand with a profound respect for the intertwined destinies of all beings—thereby paving the way for a genuinely global ethic of environmental and social responsibility.

Future research and policy should focus on developing more inclusive and reflexive mechanisms for evaluating harm, especially in transdisciplinary and international contexts. As Bernstein et al. (2023) argue, “A better approach would thus be to acknowledge the relational nature of harm and develop broad capabilities to engage and ‘stay with’ the harm.” This suggests that ongoing engagement with the complexity and ambiguity of harm is essential for the evolution of effective DNSH governance.

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